

What troubles or burns or consumes you . . .

inside out . . .

that gives you, NO peace or rest in mind-body-heart, your whole life ? ? ?

—
the conflagration / inferno of senses **Aggi-ind^o** OR the uncontrolled mind

pākat-indriya . . .

saccam kira Is it true . . . ? OR **na hi** not at all . . . ?

—
A possible remedy **bhesajja / pañichādī** to assuage **upasamati / milāpeti / vūpasanta**
the conflagration / inferno of senses OR the uncontrolled mind . . .

—
⊙ **The Tongue Seal, i.e Jivhā-Muddā / Khecarī-Mudrā** (Pali / Sanskrit) **WARNING :**
Practice in MODERATION (ie. Majjhimā Paṭipadā, or the Middle Way/Path) and
the SIMPLE STAGE ONLY! DANGEROUS WITHOUT GUIDANCE for
ADVANCED STAGES!

⊙ **Contentment (mainly of heart) Santuṭṭhi**

—
∅ to watch over the senses, i.e **Indriya-gutti . . .**

∅ to guard the senses, i.e **Indriya-gutta . . .**

∅ have knowledge ^o **ñāṇa** of what goes on in the senses of others, i.e **paropariyatti . . .**

∅ to restrain the uncontrolled **pākata / caṇḍa / asamāhita** senses and mind, i.e
Indriya-samvara . . .

∅ to cultivate the five, moral qualities, i.e **Indriya-bhāvanā . . .**

—
& further . . .

—
∅ act as an aid in looking at, i.e **anupassanā / anudarāana** (Pali / Sanskrit) . . .

∅ for cultivating inward vision, insight, i.e **vipassanā / vipaśyanā** (Pali / Buddhist
Sanskrit) . . .

∅ in the stillness of awareness . . .

shriprakash sinha

sinha.shriprakash@yandex.com

independent researcher

Postal Address : 104 - Madhurisha Heights Phase 1, Risali, Bhilai - 490006, Chhattisgarh, India

*Orcid id : 0000-0001-7027-5788, *

Tree structure : <https://linktr.ee/sinha.shriprakash>

Personal webpage : <https://sites.google.com/view/shriprakashsinha>

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Ode to . . .

—
*O Beloved Master, the absolute truth . . . Shunyata,
my Beloved Teacher Sakhyamuni Buddha,
my Beloved Trainer Jetsun Milarepa,
my Beloved Mother Nature . . .
what am i, without you . . . ?
Just a figment of imagination!*

—
*Moneyyaṃ te upaññissaṃ,
To learn the true wisdom regarding the use of the body as an instrument of action . . .
Khuradhārūpamo bhava;
"like walking on a razor sharp blade, cultivate;
Jivhāya tālumāhacca,
"The tongue touching the roof of the mouth . . .
Udare saññato siyā.
"thus, thoroughly restrain the stomach.*

*Alīnacitto ca siyā,
"Thus with an alert mind, without indolence . . .
Na cāpi bahu cintaye;
"Not quivering or wavering with plethora of thoughts / thinking . . .
Nirāmagandho asito,
Be healthy, unde-praved, without sin, virtuous, either enjoy / be satisfied or be unattached
/ independent / free from wrong desires / deeds!
Brahmacariyaparāyaṇo.
and thus, rest in or aim towards going through, a holy conduct / behaviour / life.*

*Ekāsanassa sikkhetha,
Train oneself while living alone . . .
Samaṇūpāsanassa ca;
attend / serve / honour, a wanderer / recluse / religieus;
Ekattaṃ monamakkhātāṃ,
Thus, be mercilessness, while living in unity / combination / concentration / loneliness,
with wisdom / character / self - possession.
Eko ce abhiramissasi;
Thus fond off / indulging in / enjoying oneself, in solitary . . .
Atha bhāhisi dasadisā.
And then, the ten directions, will shine / shine forth / fill with splendour.*

– SUTTA NIPĀTA 3.11, NĀLAKASUTTA (ABOUT NĀLAKA)¹

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Abstract

What troubles or burns or consumes you, inside out, that gives NO peace or rest in mind-body-heart ? ? ? We have been running and running and running . . . since birth itself. We run whole life, for the sake of fulfillment and yet, most exit frustrated, delusional and grief stricken, in misery! Some fulfillment here or there . . .

So said the Buddha -

Anekajātisaṃsāraṃ, sandhāvissaṃ anibbisāṃ,

Transmigrating or moving in circles, through countless births and rebirths in different genealogy . . .

while running through / transmigrating, not finding . . .

Gahakāraṃ gavesanto, dukkhā jāti punappunāṃ!

looking for the house builder (the one who builds on the craving / hunger / thirst, in the body) . . .

again and again, the countless births and rebirths in different genealogy, were fraught with pain / entailing sorrow or trouble / unpleasant / causing misery!

Gahakāraka diṭṭhosi! puna gehaṃ na kāhasi?

Now, grasped and seen, O! house builder (the one who builds on the craving / hunger / thirst, in the body) . . .

Where again? Will you, make enter / allow to enter / usher in OR leave behind / to give up, a dwelling / hut / house?

Sabbā te phāsukā bhaggā, gahakūṭaṃ visaṅkhatāṃ!

With all the ribs broken . . .

the topmost point or the a trap / a snare / falsehood / deceit, of the house, . . .

is lost / asundered / disturbed, that was put together / compounded / conditioned / produced by a combination of causes / created / brought about as effect of actions in former births!

Visaṅkhāragataṃ cittaṃ, taṇhānaṃ khayamajjhagā!

Thus, losing / asundering / disturbing, that was put together / compounded / conditioned / produced by a combination of causes / created / brought about as effect of actions in former births, . . .

now gone in a certain way / affected / behaved / fared / fated / being in or having come into a state or condition, . . .

of the heart (psychologically), i. e. the centre & focus of one's emotional nature and intellectual element which inheres in & accompanies its manifestations; i. e. thought . . .

i came to / got to / found / obtained / experienced, . . .

waste, destruction, consumption; decay, ruin, loss; of the passing away of night; with reference to the extinction of passions & such elements as condition, life, & rebirth, . . .

of craving / hunger / thirst!

– KHUDDAKANIKĀYA, DHAMMAPADA VERSES OF DHAMMA 146-156, JARĀVAGGA (CHAPTER ON DECAY, 11), VISĀKHĀYASAHAĪYIKĀNAMVATTHU, UDĀNAVATTHU

This craving / hunger / thirst, the UNCONTROLLED FIRE of which, burns your senses, mind and body, makes you run, ever, ever and ever . . . moment after moment, morning to evening, day by day, week by week, month by month, year by year! YOU JUST RUN! And NOT

ONLY in this life, you have been running in past lives also, as Siddhartha ran, and you will be running in future life times to come also, while burning yourself in craving and aversion / hunger / thirst, of this or that, fulfillment!

Now there is a way out, though long is the journey! In this work, i will begin with -

- 1 **Khandha** [Sanskrit. *skandha*] which constitutes *rūpa* (or material qualities / form), *vedanā* (the feeling or sensations that arise in rūpa), *saññā* (the perception of vedanā), *sankhārā* (the impressions formed by vedanā and saññā) and finally, *viññāṇa* (consciousness, which flows or remains still, due to the presence or absence of these sankhārā).
- 2 Next, **how because of the *Khandha or skandha* and *paṭiccasamuppāda* or dependent origination, that fire of craving / aversion or *taṇhā* makes you run?** is covered.
- 3 Next, a **POSSIBLE REMEDY** or *bhesajja / paṭicchādī to assuage or upasamati / milāpeti / vūpasanta*, the conflagration / inferno of senses OR the uncontrolled mind, . . . is proposed in the form of **The Tongue Seal**, i.e *Jivhā-Muddā (Pali) / Khecari-Mudrā* (Sanskrit), which MIGHT NOT completely DOUSE the fire of senses or the uncontrolled mind, but would ASSIST in cooling down one's mind-body-heart complex! In this context, the Tongue Seal is described in some detail for the practioners, who might want to test the efficacy of Jivhā-Muddā (Pali) / Khecari-Mudrā (Sanskrit).
- 4 Next, **a few personal insights are shared**, on what happens when this, The Tongue Seal, i.e Jivhā-Muddā (Pali) / Khecari-Mudrā (Sanskrit), is practised daily in **MODERATION** and **NOT in EXTREMES** or what the Buddha stressed on as *Majjhimāpatipadā* (Pali) / *Madhyamāpratipada* (Sanskrit) ! In the final teachings to the ascetic Siddhartha . . . from a conversation between a musician and pupil, on a passing boat, before Siddhartha, became the Buddha . . . **DO NOT STRETCH THE CORD TOO TIGHT, LEST IT WILL SNAP, NEITHER, SLACKEN THE CORD SUCH, THAT MUSIC WON'T PLAY! What is that cord? That cord is the mind-body-heart complex!** That cord of **NEEDs** to be maintained in the right tightness, as long as one has life! Not in extremes! In the middle way! Thus Siddhartha broke years of madness of extreme asceticism, and found what he was searching for . . . rest is history! **Samma Virya** (one component of the 8 fold path i.e *ariya atthaṅgika magga* (Pali) or *āryāṣṭāṅgamārga* (Sanskrit) by the Buddha) - the right effort! is **NEEDED**, for the practice of The Tongue Seal, i.e Jivhā-Muddā (Pali) / Khecari-Mudrā (Sanskrit)
- 5 Next, we **work through how, The Tongue Seal**, i.e Jivhā-Muddā (Pali) / Khecari-Mudrā (Sanskrit), **MIGHT help** ∅ to **watch over the senses**, i.e *Indriya-guttī* . . . ∅ to **guard the senses**, i.e *Indriya-gutta* . . . ∅ **have knowledge °ñāna** of what goes on in the senses of others, i.e *paropariyattī* . . . ∅ to **restrain the uncontrolled *pākata / caṇḍa / asamāhita* senses and mind**, i.e *Indriya-saṁvara* . . . and ∅ to **cultivate the five, moral qualities**, i.e *Indriya-bhāvanā*.
- 6 And also, **how, The Tongue Seal**, i.e Jivhā-Muddā (Pali) / Khecari-Mudrā (Sanskrit), further, the **practice of which can/might act as an aid** in ∅ **looking at**, i.e *anupassanā / anudaráana* (Pali / Sanskrit) . . . and ∅ for **cultivating inward vision, insight**, i.e *vipassanā / vipaśyanā* (Pali / Buddhist Sanskrit) . . . ∅ in the **stillness of awareness** . . . !

Lastly, **above all, the MOST IMPORTANT is CONTENTMENT of HEART**, is a requisite, from time to time, in daily life! As the Buddha said -

Ārogyaparamā lābhā, . . .

Absence of illness, . . .

is the highest / most excellent, receiving / getting / acquisition / gain / possession . . .

Santuṭṭhiparamam dhanam, . . .

Satisfaction / contentment (mainly of heart), . . .

is the highest / most excellent, receiving / getting / acquisition / gain / possession . . .

Vissāsaparamā ñāti . . .

**Trust / confidence / intimacy / mutual agreement (mainly the truth or dhamma) is a relation / relative, . . .
is the highest / most excellent, receiving / getting / acquisition / gain / possession . . .**

Nibbānaṃ paramaṃ sukhaṃ!

**The quenching or putting out of fire by other means of extinction than by blowing (which latter process rather tends to incite the fire than to extinguish it) is wellbeing / happiness / ease, . . .
is the highest / most excellent, receiving / getting / acquisition / gain / possession!**

– KHUDDAKANIKĀYA, DHAMMAPADA, SUKHAVAGGA, ÑĀTIKALAHAVŪPASAMANAVATTHU, PASENADIKOSALAVATTHU

Keywords: Tongue Seal, Senses, Mind, Body, Fire or conflagration of senses, Watching / Guarding / Having knowledge / Restraining the senses.

Contents

1	The <i>Khandhas</i> (Pali) or <i>Skandhas</i> (Sanskrit)	7
1.1	Etymology	7
1.2	<i>Khandhas</i> / <i>Skandhas</i>, in . . . Dasabalasutta (The Ten Powers), Dasabalavagga Saṃyutta Nikāya 12.21	16
1.3	The <i>Emptiness of Khandhas</i> / <i>Skandhas</i> in Prajna-Paramita-Hridaya/the Heart Sutra	18
1.3.1	T. Yang dey tse jang chub sem pa sem pa chen po pak pa chen re zik, wang chuk she rab kyi pa rol tu chin pa zab moy cho pa nyi la nam par ta zhing pung po nga po de dak la, yang rang zhin gyi tong par nam par tao/	18
1.3.2	T. De ne Sangye kyi tu tse dang den pa Sha ri bu jang chub sem pa sem pa chen po pak pa chen re zik wang chuk la di ke che me so/ Rik kyi bu am rik kyi bu mo gang la la she rab kyi pa rol tu chin pa zab moy cho pa che par do pa de ji tar lab par ja/ De ke che me pa dang/	20
1.3.3	T. Jang chub sem pa sem pa chen po pak pa chen re zik wang chuk gi tse dang den pa sha ra da ti bu la di ke che me so/ Sha ri bu rik kyi bu am rik kyi bu mo gang la la she rab kyi pa rol tu chin pa zab moy cho pa che par do pa de di tar nam par ta war ja te/	20
1.3.4	T. Pung po nga po de dak khyang rang zhin gyi tong par yang dak par je su tao/	20
1.3.5	T. Zuk tong pao/ Tong pa nyi zuk so/ Zuk le kyang tong pa nyi zhen ma yin/ Tong pa nyi le kyang zuk zhen ma yin no/	21
1.3.6	T. De zhin du tsor wa dang/ Du she dang/ Du je dang/ Nam par she pa nam tong pao/	21
1.3.7	T. Sharibu de ta we na cho tam che tong pa nyi de/ Tsen nyi me pa/	22
2	The Buddha, on <i>depend / interdepend</i> . . .	23
2.1	qualified to be called 'skilled in dependent origination' or ' <i>paṭicca-samuppāda</i> '? . .	23
2.2	Just the <i>basics of Paṭicca-samuppāda or dependent origination</i> from Sinha (2017) .	24

2.2.1	<i>Avijjā</i> - ignorance	25
2.2.2	<i>San̄khārā</i> - impressions	26
2.2.3	<i>viññāṇam</i> - consciousness	26
2.2.4	<i>Nāma-Rūpaṁ</i> - name (also meaning mind) and form (also meaning matter)	26
2.2.5	<i>saḷāyatana</i> - Senses and its interaction	26
2.2.6	<i>Phasso</i> - contact	26
2.2.7	<i>Vedanā</i> - sensation	26
2.2.8	<i>Taṇhā</i> - desire/craving/aversion	27
2.2.9	<i>Upādānam</i> - attachment	27
2.2.10	<i>Bhava</i> - existence	27
2.2.11	<i>Jāti</i> - birth	27
2.3	Grasping via example, . . . how because of the Khandha or skandha and paṭiccasamuppada or dependent origination, that fire or conflagration of craving / aversion or taṇhā makes you run?	27
2.4	The acknowledgement of 4 Noble Truths and the way out, via Vipassanā / vipaśyanā	28
2.5	T. She rab kyī pa rol tu chin pey ngak me pa/ <i>Tā ya ta om gate gate paragate parasam-gate bodhi soha/</i>	31
3	A possible remedy i.e bhesajja / paṭicchādī to assuage i.e upasamati / milāpeti / vūpasanta, the conflagration / inferno of senses OR the uncontrolled mind . . .	33
3.1	First of all, what happens due to and in the aftermath of the conflagration / inferno of senses i.e Aggi-ind^o OR i.e the uncontrolled mind i.e pākat-indriya	33
3.2	The Buddha on burning / blazing fire	33
3.3	Etymology of body, or related to body	36
3.4	Etymology of enjoyment and pleasures of senses	42
3.5	Etymology of having a say over senses of the body	47
3.6	Etymology of the uncontrolled	55
3.7	Etymology of disease	56
4	⊙ The Tongue Seal, i.e Jivhā-Muddā / Khecarī-Mudrā (Pali / Sanskrit)	56
4.1	Etymology of Jivhā and Muddā	56
4.2	The Tongue Seal	57
4.3	The Buddha on tongue	58
4.4	The practice of the Tongue Seal : a personal account	63
4.4.1	<i>First, how do i practice the Jivhā-Muddā / Khecarī-Mudrā?</i>	63
4.4.2	<i>What happens or happened due to the practice of Jivhā-Muddā / Khecarī-Mudrā?</i>	64
4.4.3	<i>What do i do with what happens while practicing Jivhā-Muddā / Khecarī-Mudrā?</i>	64
4.4.4	<i>A practical example (say, during driving / walking / sitting) while practicing Jivhā-Muddā / Khecarī-Mudrā?</i>	64
4.4.5	WARNING REPETITION!	65

5	⊕ Contentment (mainly of heart) i.e <i>Santuṭṭhi</i>	65
5.1	The <i>Buddha on contentment</i>	65
5.2	<i>A poetry for all of you</i>	66
6	A place to meditate . . . common in India	67
6.1	The <i>Buddha on secluded place of meditation</i>	67
6.2	The <i>Snapshot of a place where one could meditate</i> . . . quite common in India . . .	68
7	For those interested . . . a personal account	72
8	Conclusion	72
8.1	regarding development of wisdom and meditation	72
8.2	regarding NOT because someone has said so	73

1 The *Khandhas* (Pali) or *Skandhas* (Sanskrit)

1.1 Etymology

According to the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the online Pali dictionary at Univ. of Chicago, the word -

- **Khandha** [Sk. skandha] - I. Crude meaning: bulk, massiveness (gross) substance. A. esp. used (a) of an elephant: the bulk of the body, i. e. its back S i.95; vāraṇassa J iii.392; hatthi - khandha - vara - gata on the back of the state elephant J i.325; PvA 75. Also with ref. to an elephant (hatthināga) sañjāta° "to whom has grown bulk=a large back" Sn 53, expl. SnA 103 by sasanṭhitakkhandho "well endowed with bulk." - (b) of a person: the shoulder or back: nāgalaṃ khandhe karitvā S i.115 appl. to Māra; Vism 100; DhA iv.168 (ohita° - bhāra the load lifted off his shoulder). - - (c) of a tree: the trunk. rukkhassa PvA 114, also as rukkha° J i.324; tāla° the stem of a palm PvA 56; nigrodhassa khandhaja (see cpds.) S i.207=Sn 272; mūlaṃ atikkamma kh° ṃ sāraṃ pariyesitabbaṃ "one must go beyond the root and search the trunk for sweetness" S iv.94. - (d) as t.t. in exegetical literature: section, chapter, lit. material as collected into uniform bulk; freq. in postscripts to Texts and Commentaries. See also khandhaka. - B. More general as denoting bulk (-°); e. g. aggi° a great mass of fire M ii.34, 41; J iv.139; udaka° a mass of water (i. e. ocean) A iii.336; S iv.179; J i.324; PvA 62; puñña° a great accumulation of merit A iii.336=S v.400; bhoga° a store of wealth A v.84; J i.6; maṇi° an extraordinarily large jewel (possessing magic power) J ii.102 sq. - II. Applied meaning. - A. (-°) the body of, a collection of, mass, or parts of; in collective sense "all that is comprised under"; forming the substance of. - (a) dukkha° all that is comprised under "dukkha," all that goes to make up or forms the substance, the idea of "ill." Most prominent in phrase kevalassa dukkhakkhandhassa samudaya and nirodha (the origin & destruction of all that is suffering) with ref. to the paṭiccasamuppāda, the chain of causal existence (q. v.) Vin i.1; S ii.95; iii.14; A i.177; v. 184 & passim. Similarly: samudaya Vbh 135 sq. nirodha Nett 64; antakiriya A i.147; vyādhimaraṇatunnānaṃ dukkhakkhandhaṃ vyapānudi Th 2, 162. - (b) lobha° dosa° moha° the three ingredients or integrations of greed, suffering and bewilderment, lit. "the big bulk or mass of greed" (see also under padāleti), S v.88 (nibbijjhati through the satta bojjangā). - (c) vayo° a division of age, part of age, as threefold: purima°,

majjhima°, pacchima° Nd2 in def. of sadā. - (d) sīla (etc.) kh° the 3 (or 5) groups or parts which constitute the factors of right living (dhamma), viz. (1) sīla° the group dealing with the practice of morality; (2) samādhi° that dealing with the development of concentration; (3) paññā° that dealing with the development of true wisdom. They are also known under the terms of sīla - sampadā, citta°, paññā° D i.172 sq.; see sīla. - D i.206; Nett 64 sq.; 126. tīhi dhammehi samannāgato "possessed of the three qualities," viz. sīla - kkhandhesu, etc. It 51; cp. A i.291; v.326. tīhi khandhehi . . . aṭṭhangiko maggo sangahito M i.301; sīlakkhandhaṃ, etc. paripūreti "to fulfil the sīla - group" A i.125; ii.20, iii.15 sq. These 3 are completed to a set of 5 by (4) vimutti° the group dealing with the attainment of emancipation and (5) vimutti - ñāṇa - dassana° the group dealing with the realization of the achievement of emancipation. As 1 - 4 only at D iii.229 (misprint puñña for paññā); cp. A i.125. As 5 at S i.99=A i.162; S v.162; A iii.134, 271; v.16 (all loc.=S i.99); It 107, 108; Nd2 under sīla. B. (absolute) in individual sense: constituent element, factor, substantiality. More especially as khandhā (pl.) the elements or substrata of sensory existence, sensorial aggregates which condition the appearance of life in any form. Their character according to quality and value of life and body is evanescent, fraught with ills & leading to rebirth. Paraphrased by Bdgh. as rāsi, heap, e. g. Asl. 141; Vibh A 1 f.; cf. B. Psy. 42. 1. Unspecified. They are usually enumerated in the foll. stereotyped set of 5: rūpa° (material qualities), vedanā (feeling), saññā (perception), sankhārā (coefficients of consciousness), viññāṇa (consciousness). For further ref. see rūpa; cp. also Mrs. Rh. D. Dhs trsl. pp. 40 - 56. They are enumerated in a different order at S i.112, viz. rūpaṃ vedayitaṃ saññaṃ viññāṇaṃ yañ ca sankhataṃ n' eso 'ham asmi. Detailed discussions as to their nature see e. g. S iii.101 (=Vbh 1 - 61); S iii.47; iii.86. As being comprised in each of the dhātus, viz. kāma° rūpa° arūpa - dhātu Vbh 404 sq. (a) As factors of existence (cp. bhava). Their rôle as such is illustrated by the famous simile: "yathā hi angasambhārā hoti saddo ratho iti evaṃ khandhesu santesu hoti satto ti sammuti" "just as it is by the condition precedent of the co - existence of its various parts, that the word G chariot ' is used, just so it is that when the skandhas are there, we talk of a G being" (Rh. D.) (cp. Hardy, Man. Buddh. p. 425) S i.135=Miln 28. Their connotation "khandha" is discussed at S iii.101 =M iii.16: "kittāvatā nu kho khandhānaṃ khandhādhivacanaṃ? rūpaṃ (etc.) atītānāgatapaccuppannaṃ ajjhataṃ vā bahiddhā vā oḷārikaṃ," etc.: i.e. material qualities are equivalent terms for the kh. What causes the manifestation of each kh.? cattāro mahābhūtā . . . paccayo rūpa - khandhassa paññāpanāya; phasso . . . vedana°, saññā°, sankhārā°, etc.; nā- marūpaṃ . . . viññāṇa°: the material elements are the cause of rūpa, touch is that of vedanā, saññā, sankhārā, name and shape that of viññāṇa (S iii.101); cp. M i.138 sq., 234 sq. On the same principle rests their division in: rūpa - kāyo rūpakkhandho nāmakāyo cattāro arūpino khandhā "the material body forms the material factor (of existence), the individualized body the 4 immaterial factors" Nett 41; the rūpakkhandha only is kāmādhātu - pariyāpanno: Vbh 409; the 4 arūpino kh° discussed at Ps ii.74, also at Vbh 230, 407 sq. (grouped with what is apariyāpanna) -Being the "substantial" factors of existence, birth & death depend on the khandhas. They appear in every new conjuncture of individuality concerning their function in this paṭisandhi - kkhāṇe; see Ps ii.72 - 76. Thus the var. phases of life in transmigration are defined as - (jāti:) ya tesāṃ tesāṃ sattānaṃ tamhi tamhi satta - nikāye jāti sañjāti okkanti abhinibbatti khandhānaṃ pātubhāvo ā yatanānaṃ paṭilābho Nd2 on Sn 1052; cp. jāti dvī—hi khandhehi sangahitā ti VvA 29; khandhānaṃ pā-tubhāvo jāti S ii.3; Nett 29; khandhānaṃ nibbatti jāti Vism 199. - (maraṇaṃ:) yā tesāṃ tesāṃ sattānaṃ . . . cuti cavanaṭā bhedo antaradhānaṃ maccu maraṇaṃ

kālakiriyā khandhānaṃ bhedo kalevarassa nikkhepo M i.49=Vbh 137=S ii.3, 42. - vivatta - kkhanda (adj.) one whose khandhas have revolved (passed away), i. e. dead S i.121=iii.123. - kh^oanaṃ udaya - vyaya (or udayabbaya) the rising and passing of the kh., transmigration Dh 374=Th 1, 23, 379=It 120=KhA 82; Ps i.54 sq. - (b) Their relation to attachment and craving (kāma): sattisūlūpamā kāmā khandhānaṃ adhikuttanā S i.128=Th 2, 58, 141 (ThA 65: natthi tesam adhik^o?); craving is their cause & soil: hetupaṭicca sambhūtā kh. S i.134; the 4 arūpino kh. are based on lobha, dosa, moha Vbh 208. - (c) their annihilation: the kh. remain as long as the knowledge of their true character is not attained, i. e. of their cause & removal: yaṃ rūpaṃ, etc. . . . n' etaṃ mama n' eso 'ham asmi na m' eso attā ti; evaṃ etaṃ yathābhūtaṃ sammappaññāya passati; evaṃ kho jānato passato . . . ahankāramamankāra - mānānusayā na hontī ti S iii.103; - pañca - kkhanda pariññāya S iii.83; pañca - kkhanda pariññātā tiṭṭhanti chinnaṃ lakā Th 2, 106. See also S i.134. - (d) their relation to dhātu (the physical elements) and āyatana (the elements of sense - perception) is close, since they are all dependent on sensory experience. The 5 khandhas are frequently mentioned with the 18 dhātuyo & the 12 āyatanāni: khandhā ca dh^o cha ca āyatanā ime hetuṃ paṭicca sambhūtā hetubhaṅgā nirujjhare S i.134; kh^o - dh^o - āyatanāṃ sankhataṃ jātimūlaṃ Th 2, 472; dhammaṃ adesesi khandh' - āyatana - dhātuyo Th 2, 43 (cp. ThA 49). Enumerated under sabba- dhammā Ps i.101=ii.230; under dhammā (states) Dhs 121, as lokuttara - kkhanda, etc. Dhs 358, 528, 552. - khandhānaṃ khandhattho abhiññeyyo, dhātūnaṃ dhātuṭṭho, etc. Ps i.17; cp. i.132; ii.121, 157. In def. of kāmāvacarā bhūmi Ps i.83. In def. of dukkha and its recognition Nett 57. In def. of arahanto khīṇāsavā Nd2 on sankhāta - dhammā ("kh. sankhātā," etc.), on tiṇṇa ("khandha - (etc.) pariyaṇṇa"), & passim. - (e) their valuation & their bearing on the "soul" - conception is described in the terms of namama (na tumhākaṃ), anattā, aniccaṃ and dukkhaṃ (cp. upādāna-kkhandh^o infra and rūpa) rūpaṃ (etc.) . . . aniccaṃ, dukkhaṃ, n' eso 'ham asmi, n' eso me attā "material qualities (etc. kh. 2 - 5) are evanescent, bad, I am not this body, this body is not my soul" Vin i.14=S iv.382. n' eso 'ham asmi na m' eso attā S i.112; iii.103, 130 & passim; cp. kāyo na tumhākaṃ (anattā rūpaṃ) S ii.65; Nd2 680; and rūpaṃ na tumhākaṃ S iii.33 M i.140=Nd2 680. - rūpaṃ, etc. as anattā: Vin i.13; S iii.78, 132 - 134; A i.284= ii.171; 202; cp. S iii.101; Vin i.14. - as aniccaṃ: S iii.41, 52, 102, 122, 132 sq., 181 sq., 195 sq., 202 - 224, 227; A iv.147 (aniccānupassī dukkhānupassī); anicca dukkha roga, etc., Ps ii.238 sq.; Vbh 324. - 2. Specified as pañca upādāna-kkhandhā the factors of the fivefold clinging to existence. Defined & discussed in detail (rūpupādāna - kkhanda, etc.) S iii.47; 86 - 88; also Vin i.10; S iii.127 sq. Specified S iii.58 iii.100=M iii.16; S iii.114, 158 sq.; v.52, 60; A iv.458; Vism 443 sq. (in ch. xiv: Khandha - niddesa), 611 sq. (judged aniccato, etc.). - Mentioned as a set exemplifying the number 5: Kh iii.; Ps i.22, 122. Enumerated in var. connections S i.112; D iii.233; M i.190; A v.52; Kh iv. (expld KhA 82=A v.52); Miln 12 (var. references concerning the discussion of the kh. in the Abhidhamma). - What is said of the khandhas alone - see above 1 (a) - (e) - is equally applied to them in connection with upādāna. - (a) As regards their origin they are characterized as chandamūlakā "rooted in desire, or in wilful desire" S iii.100; cp. yo kho . . . pañcas' upādāna-kkhandhesu chandarāgo taṃ tattha upādānaṃ ti M i.300, 511. Therefore the foll. attributes are characteristic: kummo pañcann' etaṃ upād^o ānaṃ adhivacanaṃ M i.144; bhārā have pañcakkh^oā S iii.26; pañcavadhakā paccatthikā pañcann' . . . adhivacanaṃ S iv.174; pañc' upād^o . . . sakkāyo vutto M i.299= S iv.259. - (b) their contemplation leads to the recognition of their character as dukkha, anicca, anattā: na kiñci attānaṃ vā attaniyaṃ vā pañcasu upādāna-kkhandhesu S iii.128; rogato, etc. . .

. manasikātabbā pañc° S iii.167; pañcasu upād°esu aniccânupassī° ”realizing the evanescence in the 5 aggregates of attachment” A v.109; same with udayavyayânupassī° S iii.130; A ii.45, 90; iii.32; iv.153; and dhammânupassī° M i.61. Out of which realization follows their gradual destruction: pañc° . . . khandhānam samudayo atthangamo assādo, etc. S iii.31, 160 sq.; A ii.45, 90; iv.153; Nd2 under sankhārā. That they occupy a prominent position as determinants of dukkha is evident from their rôle in the exposition of dukkha as the first one of the noble truths: sankhittena pañc°upādānakkhandhā pi dukkhā ”in short, the 5 kh. are associated with pain” Vin i.10=M i.48=A i.177=S v.421; Ps i.37, 39; Vbh 101 & passim; cp. katamañ dukkham ariyasaccam? pañc°upād° ā tissa vacaniyam, seyyathidam . . . S iii.158=v.425; khandhādisā dukkhā Dh 202 (& expl. DhA iii.261). - 3. Separately mentioned: khandhā as tayo arūpino kh° (ved°, sañña°, sankh°) DhA i.22; viññāṇa - kh° (the skandha of discriminative consciousness) in Def. of manas: manindriyam viññāṇam viññ° - khandhotajjā manoviññāṇadhātu Nd2 on Sn 1142=Dhs 68.

- **Rūpa** (nt.) [cp. Vedic rūpa, connected etymologically with varpa (Grassmann). - The nom. pl. is rūpā & rūpāni] form, figure, appearance, principle of form, etc. - A. Definitions. According to P. expositors rūpa takes its designation fr. ruppatti, e. g. ”ruppanato rūpañ” Vism 588; ”ruppan’ atthena r.” VbhA 3; ”rūpa - rūpañ= ruppana sabhāvena yuttañ” Cpd. 1567 (where ruppatti is, not quite correctly, given as ”change”), ”ruppatī ti: tasmā rūpan ti vuccati” S iii.86; other defns are ”rūpayatī ti rūpañ” (with cakkhu & the other 10 āyatanas) VbhA 45; and more scientifically: ”paresu rūp’ ādisu cakkhu - paṭihanana lakkhaṇam rūpañ” Vism 446. - Of modern interpretations & discussions see e. g. Dhs. trsl. introd. ch. vi. (pp. 41 - 63, or 248 - 71); Dial. ii.244; Expos. 67n; Cpd. 270 sq. (where objections are raised to trsln ”form,” and as better (philosophical) terms ”matter,” ”material quality” are recommended). See also loka for similar etym.- B. (lit.) appearance, form, figure Dhs 597 sq. (=form either contrasted with what is unseen, or taken for both seen and unseen), 751; Mhvs 27, 30 (sīha - vyagghādirūpāni representations of lions, tigers etc.); 30, 68 (ravicaṇḍa - tāra - rūpāni id.); 36, 31 (loha° bronze statue); ThA 257. - Esp. beautiful form, beauty S iv.275= Pv ii.958 (as one of the 10 attributes, with sadda etc., of distinction: see also below D ii.a); Miln 285; Mhvs 20, 4 (rūpa - mānini° proud of her beauty); PvA 89. - surūpa very beautiful ThA 72; durūpa of evil form, ugly A ii.203 sq. (dubbaṇṇa+). - In phrase rūpañ sikkhati Vin i.77=iv.129 the meaning is doubtful; it may be ”to study drawing, or arts & craft,” or (with Mrs. Rh. D.) ”weights & measures,” or (w. Hardy) ”money changing.” It is said that through this occupation the eyes become bad; it is opposed to gaṇanā. - C. (-°) of such & such a form, like, kind, of a certain condition or appearance. In this appln very frequent & similar to E. - hood, or Ger. - heit, i. e. an abstract formation. Often untranslatable because of the latter character. It is similar to kāya (cp. expln of ātura - rūpa Vv 8314 by abhitunna -kāya Vva 328), but not so much with ref. to life & feeling as to appearance and looks. E. g. aneka° Sn 1079 (=anekavidha Nd2 54); adissamāna° invisible PvA 6 (lit. with invisible form); ummatta° as if mad, under the appearance of madness, like a madman Pv i.81; ii.63; eva° in such a condition Pv ii.15; tapassī° appearing to be an ascetic Pv i.32; tāra° the (shapes of the) stars Dhs 617; deva° as a deva PvA 92. Pleonastically e. g. in: anupatta° attaining Pv iv.166; taramāna° quickly Pv ii.62; yutta° fit PvA 157; sucitta° variegated Pv i.109. - Cases ad verbially: citta -rūpañ according to intention Vin iii.161; iv.177; cetabba - rūpañ fit to be thought upon J iv.157. (=°yuttakam C.). - atta -rūpena on my own account S iv.97; godha - rūpena as an iguana Mhvs

28, 9. - D. (as philos. t. t.) principle of (material) form, materiality, visibility. - There are var. groups of psychological and metaphysical systematizations, in which rūpa functions as the material, gross factor, by the side of other, more subtle factors. In all these representations of rūpa we find that an element of moral psychology overshadows the purely philosophical & speculative aspect. A detailed (Abhidhammatic) discussion of rūpa in var. aspects is to be found at Dhs § 585 - 980. - 1. rūpa as āyatana or sense object. It is the object of the activity or sphere of the organ of sight (cakkhu). As such it heads the list of the 6 bāhirāni āyatanāni (see e. g. Nd2 p. 238 A - E & āyatana3) with "cakkhunā rūpaṃ disvā" (the others: sota>sadda, ghāna>gandha, jivhā>rasa, kāya>phoṭṭhabba, mano>dhamma), cp. cakkhu - viññeyyā rūpā iṭṭhā kantā etc. D i.245; M i.266; cakkhunā rūpaṃ passati iṭṭha - rūpaṃ kanta - rūpaṃ etc. S iv.126; - see further: Vin i.34 (sabbaṃ ādittaṃ: cakkhum ādittaṃ, rūpa ādittā etc. with sequence of other āyatanas); D ii.308 sq., 336 sq.; M iii.18 (yaṃ kho rūpaṃ paṭicca uppajjati sukhaṃ somanassaṃ, ayaṃ rūpe assādo; cp. Ps ii.109 sq.), 291 (ye te cakkhu - viññeyyesu rūpesu avīta - rāgā etc.); Ps i.79; ii.38 (rūpī rūpāni passatī ti vimokkha); Dhs 617, 653, 878; Tikp 28. - 2. (metaphysically) as the representative of sensory or material existence: (a) universally as forming the corporeal stratum in the world of appearance or form (rūpa-bhava) as compared with the incorporeal (arūpa - bhava), being itself above, and yet including the kāma- bhava. (The kāmabhava is a subdivision of rūpabhava, which has got raised into a third main division.) This triad is also found in combns with loka or dhātu (see dhātu 2 a & d), or avacara. See e. g. D i.17; iii.215 (°dhātu), 216 (°bhava); Kvu 370 sq. (°dhātu); Dhs 499 (°āvacara), 585 (°dhātu); Vbh 17 (°āvacara), 25 (as garupariṇāma & dandha - nirodha compd with arūpa). A similar sequence rūpa arūpa & nirodha (i. e. nibbāna) in old verses at Sn 755; It 45, 62 (rūpehi arūpā santatarā, arūpehi nirodho santataro). On indriya - rūpa "faculty as form" see indriya B. - (b) individually in the sphere of saṃsāra as one (i. e. the material quality) of the substrata of sensory individual existence or the khandhas. They are the 5: rūpa - kkhanda, vedanā°, saññā°, sankhārā°, viññāṇa °; otherwise called rūp' ūpādāna-kkhandha etc. (e. g. D iii.223, 278; Vism 443). See khandha ii. B. - In this property rūpa consists of 28 subdivisions, viz. the 4 (great) dhātūs (mahābhūtāni or else bhūta - rūpa primary matter) and 24 upādārūpāni (i. e. derivative forms or accidentals). These are given in extenso in the rū - pakkhandha section of the Vism (pp. 443 - 450), also at Dhs 585; the 24 consist of: cakkhu, sota, ghāna, jivhā, kāya, rūpa, sadda, gandha, rasa, itthindriya, purisindriya, jīvitindriya, hadaya - vatthu, kāya - viññatti, vacī - viññatti, ākāsa - dhātu, (rūpassa) lahutā mudutā kammaññatā, upacaya santati jaratā aniccatā, kabaḷinkār' - āhāra; cp. defn at Nett 73: cātu - mahābhūtikaṃ rūpaṃ catunnaṃ ca mahābhūtānaṃ upādāya rūpassa paññatti. The rūpakkhandha shares with the others the qualities of soullessness, evanescence and ill (anattā, anicca, dukkha); e. g. rūpaṃ ca h' idaṃ attā abhavissa, na y' idaṃ rūpaṃ ābadhāya saṃvatteyya Vin i.13, cp. similarly M iii.282 sq.; S iii.66; quoted and expld in detail at Vism 610; rūpaṃ aniccaṃ Vin i.14; M i.228; iii.18 (also expld at Vism 610); S iii.48, 66, 88; rūpe anicc' ānupassanā Ps ii.186 sq. - See also D ii.301; iii.233; Ps i.23, 53, 104; ii.96, 102, 109 (rū - passa ādīnavo); Vbh 1. sq., 12 sq. (in detail); Kvu 11 sq.; Vism 443 sq.; Tikp 33; VbhA 2, 3, 32 sq.=S iii.142 (with var. similes); DhA iv.100. - (c) in the making up of the individuality as such (nāma-rūpa), where in contrast with nāma (as abstract, logical, invisible or mind - factor) rūpa represents the visible (material) factor, resembling kāya (cp. phrase nāma - kāya in same sense). The foll. are current defns of nāma - rūpa: nāma - (kāya)=vedanā, saññā, cetanā, phassa, man-asikāra (otherwise citta - sankhārā), rūpa(- kāya)=cattāro mahā - bhūtā catunnaṃ m - bhūtānaṃ

upādāya rūpaṃ (otherwise kāya - sankhārā) S ii.4; iii.59 sq.; Ps i.183; with explns at Vism 558 & VbhA 169. Defined at Nett 15: "ye phassa - pañcamakā dhammā: idaṃ nāmaṃ, yāni pañc' indriyāni rūpāni: idaṃ rūpaṃ, tad ubhayaṃ nāmarūpaṃ viññāṇa - sampayuttaṃ." Discussed in detail also at Vism 562 (=VbhA 173, 174), 587 - 597; cp. DhsA 392 (Expos. 500, where "mind - matter" is given as corresp. couple in trsln, do. Cpd. 271 sq. "mind and body"). See also under paṭicca - samuppāda. - 3. various references: D iii.102, 212, 225, 244, 273; M i.84 (Gotamo kāmānaṃ pariññaṃ paññāpeti, rūpā - naṃ, vedanānaṃ); S ii.198; iii.11 (evaṃ - rūpo siyaṃ, evaṃ vedano etc.), 101 (id., & the khandhas); Sn 867, 874, 943, 1037, 1121; Nd1 425; Tikp 36, 38, 54, 262; Vism 625 (uppaj-janaka°).

- **Vedanā** (f.) [fr. ved°: see vedeti; cp. Epic Sk. vedanā] feeling, sensation (see on term, e. g. Cpd. 14 Mrs. Rh. D. B. Psy., ch. iv.) D i.45; ii.58 (cp. Dial. ii.54), 66; iii.58, 77, 221, 228, 238 (°upādāna); S iii.86 sq.; A i.39, 122, 141; ii.79, 198, 256; iii.245 sq., 450; iv.301, 385; Kh iii. (tisso v.); Sn 435, 529, 739, 1111; Nd1 109; Nd2 551 (tisso v.); Ps i.6, 50 sq., 145 sq., 153 sq.; ii.109 sq., 181 sq.; Vbh 135 sq., 294, 401, 403 sq.; Dhs 3, 1348; Nett 27, 65 sq.; 83, 123, 126; Tikp 246, 317 sq., 345 sq.; Vism 460 sq.; DA i.125; VbhA 13 sq., 39 sq., 80, 178, 193, 221 (°ānupassanā, in detail), 263 sq., 382 (various). - Three modes of feeling (usually understood whenever mention is made of "tisso vedanā"): sukhā (pleasant), dukkhā (painful) adukkha-m-asukhā (indifferent) D iii.275; S ii.53, 82; iv.207; A iii.400; It 46; Tikp 317 sq. - or: kusalā, akusalā, avyākatā Vism 460. - Five vedanās: sukhaṃ, dukkhaṃ, somanassaṃ, domanassaṃ, upekkhā Vism 461. Categories of 2 to 108 modes of Vedanā, S iv.223 sq. - vedanā is one of the 5 khandhas (see khandha ii.B). - On relation of old and new sensations (purāṇa° & nava°) see e. g. A ii.40; iii.388; iv.167; Vism 33; and see formula under yātrā. - In the Paṭicasamuppāda (q. v.) vedanā stands between phassa as condition and taṇhā as result; see e. g. Vism 567 sq. - 2. (in special application) painful sensation, suffering, pain (i. e. dukkhavedanā) M i.59; A i.153 (sārīrikā bodily pain); ii.116 (id.); iii.143 (id.); Pv i.1015; Miln 253 (kāyikā & cetasikā); VbhA 101 (maraṇ' antikā v. agonies of death). - vedan' atta afflicted by pain Vin ii.61; iii.100; J i.293. - As adj. vedana suffering or to be suffered Pv iii.106 (=anub- hūyamāna PvA 214). - vedana at J iii.349 is to be read as vetana.
- **Saññā** (f.) [fr. sañ+jñā] (pl. saññāyo and saññā - e. g. M i.108) 1. sense, consciousness, perception, being the third khandha Vin i.13; M i.300; S iii.3 sq.; Dhs 40, 58, 61, 113; VbhA 42. - 2. sense, perception, discernment, recognition, assimilation of sensations, awareness M i.293; A iii.443 (nibbāna°); S iii.87; Sn 732 (saññāya uparodhanā dukkhakkhaya hoti; expld as "kāmasaññā" SnA); Miln 61; Dhs 4; DhsA 110, 200 (rūpa° perception of material qualities). - 3. consciousness D i.180 sq.; M i.108; Vbh 369 (nānatta° c. of diversity: see nānatta); Miln 159; J iv.391; is previous to ñāṇa D i.185; a constituent part of nāma S ii.3, cp. Sn 779; according to later teaching differs from viññāṇa and paññā only as a child's perceiving differs from (a) an adult's, (b) an expert's Vism 436 sq.; Dhs. trsln 7 n. 2, 17 n. 2. - nevasaññā - nāsaññā neither consciousness nor unconsciousness D iii.224, 262 sq.; M i.41, 160; ii.255; iii.28, 44; Ps i.36; Dhs 268, 582, 1417; Kvu 202; Nett 26, 29; Vism 571. - 4. conception, idea, notion D i.28; iii.289 (cp. Dial. iii.263: "concept rather than percept"); M iii.104; S i.107; Sn 802, 841; J i.368 (ambaphala saññāya in the notion or imagining of mango fruit); Vism 112 (rūpa° & atthika°). saññānaṃ karoti to imagine, to think J ii.71; to take notice, to mind J i.117. - 5. sign, gesture token, mark J i.287; ii.18; paṇṇa° a mark of leaves J i.153; rajjusaññā a rope used as a mark, a guiding rope, J i.287; rukkha - saññānaṃ pabbata

-0 saññaṃ karonto, using trees and hills as guiding marks J iv.91; saññaṃ dadāti to give the sign (with the whip, for the horse to start) J vi.302. - 6. sañña is twofold, paṭighasamphassajā and adhivacanasamphassajā i. e. sense impression and recognition (impression of something similar, "association by similarity," as when a seen person calls up some one we know), Vbh 6; VbhA 19 sq.; threefold, rū - pasaññā, paṭighasaññā, and nānattasaññā A ii.184; S ii.211; cp. Sn 535; or kāma°, vyāpāda°, vihiṃsā° (as nānatta°) Vbh 369, cp. VbhA 499; fivefold (pañca vimutti - paripācaniyā saññā); anicca°, anicce dukkha°, dukkhe anatta°, pahāna°, virāga° D iii.243, cp. A iii.334; there are six perceptions of rūpa, sadda, gandha, rasa, phoṭṭhabba, and dhamma, D ii.309; S iii.60; the sevenfold perception, anicca - , anatta - , asubha - , ādī - nava - , pahāna - , virāga - , and nirodha - saññā, D ii.79; cp. A iii.79; the tenfold perception, asubha - , maraṇa - , āhāre paṭikkūla - , sabbaloke anabhirata - , anicca - , anicce dukkha - , dukkhe anatta - , pahāna - , virāga - , nirodha - saññā A v.105; the one perception, āhāre paṭikkūlasaññā, Cpd. 21. - 7. See further (unclassified refs.): D i.180; ii.277 (papañca°); iii.33, 223; S ii.143; A ii.17; iv.312; Nd1 193, 207; Nett 27; Vism 111, 437, 461 sq. (in detail); VbhA 20 (pañca - dvārikā), 34; VvA 110; and on term Cpd. 40, 42.

- **Sankhāra** [fr. saṃ+kr, not Vedic, but as saṃskāra Epic & Class. Sk. meaning "preparation" and "sacrament," also in philosophical literature "former impression, disposition," cp. vāsanā] one of the most difficult terms in Buddhist meta physics, in which the blending of the subjective - objective view of the world and of happening, peculiar to the East, is so complete, that it is almost impossible for Occidental terminology to get at the root of its meaning in a translation. We can only convey an idea of its import by representing several sides of its application, without attempting to give a "word" as a def. trsln. - An exhaustive discussion of the term is given by Franke in his Dīgha translation (pp. 307 sq., esp. 311 sq.); see also the analysis in Cpd. 273 - 276. - Lit. "preparation, get up"; appld: coefficient (of consciousness as well as of physical life, cp. viññāṇa), constituent, constituent potentiality; (pl.) synergies, cause - combination, as in S iii.87; discussed, B. Psy., p. 50 sq. (cp. DhsA 156, where paraphrased in defn of sa-sankhāra with "ussāha, payoga, upāya, paccaya-gaḥaṇa"); composition, aggregate. 1. Aggregate of the conditions or essential properties for a given process or result - e. g. (i.) the sum of the conditions or properties making up or resulting in life or existence; the essentials or "element" of anything (-°), e. g. āyusaṅkhāra, life - element D ii.106; S ii.266; PvA 210; bhavasankhāra, jīvitasankhāra, D ii.99, 107. (ii.) Essential conditions, antecedents or synergy (co - ordinated activity), mental coefficients, requisite for act, speech, thought: kāya°, vacī°, citta°, or mano°, described respectively as "respiration," "attention and consideration," "percepts and feelings," "because these are (respectively) bound up with," or "precede" those M i.301 (cp. 56); S iv.293; Kvu 395 (cp. trsln 227); Vism 530 sq.; DhsA 8; VbhA 142 sq. - 2. One of the five khandhas, or constitutional elements of physical life (see khandha), comprising all the citta - sampayutta - cetasikā dhammā - i. e. the mental concomitants, or adjuncts which come, or tend to come, into consciousness at the uprising of a citta, or unit of cognition Dhs 1 (cp. M iii.25). As thus classified, the saṅkhāra's form the mental factor corresponding to the bodily aggregate or rūpakkhandha, and are in contrast to the three khandhas which represent a single mental function only. But just as kāya stands for both body and action, so do the concrete mental syntheses called saṅkhārā tend to take on the implication of synergies, of purposive intellection, connoted by the term abhisankhāra, q. v. - e. g. M iii.99, where saṅkhārā are a purposive, aspiring state of mind to induce a specific rebirth;

S ii.82, where puññam, opuññam, āṇeñjam s. abhisankharoti, is, in D iii.217 & Vbh 135, catalogued as the three classes of abhisankhāra; S ii.39, 360; A ii.157, where s. is tantamount to saācetanā; Miln 61, where s., as khandha, is replaced by cetanā (purposive conception). Thus, too, the ss. in the Paṭīcasamuppāda formula are considered as the aggregate of mental conditions which, under the law of kamma, bring about the inception of the paṭīsandhiviññāṇa, or first stirring of mental life in a newly begun individual. Lists of the psychologically, or logically distinguishable factors making up the composite saṅkhārakkhandha, with constants and variants, are given for each class of citta in Dhs 62, etc. (N.B. - Read cetanā for vedanā, § 338.) Phassa and cetanā are the two constant factors in the s - kkhandha. These lists may be compared with the later elaboration of the saṅkhāra - elements given at Vism 462 sq. - 3. saṅkhārā (pl.) in popular meaning. In the famous formula (and in many other connections, as e. g. sabbe saṅkhārā) "aniccā vata saṅkhārā up - pādavaya - dhammino" (D ii.157; S i.6, 158, 200; ii.193; Th 1, 1159; J i.392, cp. Vism 527), which is rendered by Mrs. Rh. D. (Brethren, p 385 e. g.) as "O, transient are our life's experiences! Their nature 'tis to rise and pass away," we have the use of s. in quite a general & popular sense of "life, physical or material life"; and sabbe saṅkhārā means "everything, all physical and visible life, all creation." Taken with caution the term "creation" may be applied as t.t. in the Paṭīcasamuppāda, when we regard avijjā as creating, i. e. producing by spontaneous causality the saṅkhāras, and saṅkhārā as "natura genita atque genitura" (the latter with ref. to the foll. viññāṇa). If we render it by "formations" (cp. Oldenberg's "Gestaltungen," Buddha 71920, p. 254), we imply the mental "constitutional" element as well as the physical, although the latter in customary materialistic popular philosophy is the predominant factor (cp. the discrepancies of "life eternal" and "life is extinct" in one & the same European term). None of the "links" in the Paṭīcasamuppāda meant to the people that which it meant or was supposed to mean in the subtle and schematic philosophy (dhammā duddasā nipuṇā!) of the dogmatists. - Thus saṅkhārā are in the widest sense the "world of phenomena" (cp. below °loka), all things which have been made up by pre - existing causes. - At PvA 71 we find saṅkhārā in lit. meaning as "things" (preparations) in defn of ye keci (bhogā) "whatever." The sabbe s. at S ii.178 (trsln "all the things of this world") denote all 5 aggregates exhausting all conditioned things; cp. Kvu 226 (trsln "things"); Mhvs iv.66 (: the material and transitory world); Dh 154 (vi - saṅkhāragataṃ cittam=mind divested of all material things); DhsA 304 (trsln "kamma activities," in connection avijjā - paccaya - s°); Cpd. 211, n. 3. - The defn of saṅkhārā at Vism 526 (as result of avijjā & cause of viññāṇa in the P. - S.) is: sankhataṃ abhisankharontī ti saṅkhārā. Api ca: avijjā - paccayā saṅkhārā saṅkhāra - saddena āgata - saṅkhārā ti duvidhā saṅkhārā; etc. with further def. of the 4 saṅkhāras. - 4. Var. passages for saṅkhāra in general: D ii. 213; iii.221 sq., M ii.223 (imassa dukkha - nidānassa saṅkhāraṃ padahato saṅkhāra - ppadhānā virāgo hoti); S iii.69 (ekanta - dukkhā saṅkhārā); iv.216 sq. (saṅkhārāṇaṃ khaya - dhammatā; id. with vaya°, virāga°, nirodha° etc.); Sn 731 (yaṃ kiñci dukkhaṃ sambhoti sabbaṃ saṅkhāra - paccayā; saṅkhārāṇaṃ nirodhena n'atthi dukkhassa sambhavo); Vism 453, 462 sq. (the 51), 529 sq.; DhA iii.264, 379; VbhA 134 (4 fold), 149 (3 fold), 192 (āyūhanā); PvA 41 (bhijjana - dhammā). - Of passages dealing with the saṅkhāras as aniccā, vayadhammā, anattā, dukkhā etc. the foll. may be mentioned: Vin i.13; S i.200; iii.24; iv.216, 259; v.56, 345; M iii.64, 108; A i.286; ii.150 sq.; iii.83, 143; iv.13, 100; It 38; Dh 277, 383; Ps i.37, 132; ii.48; 109 sq.; Nd2 444, 450; also Nd2 p. 259 (s. v. saṅkhārā).

- **Viññāna** (nt.) [fr. vi+jñā; cp. Vedic vijāna cognition] (as special term in Buddhist metaphysics) a mental quality as a constituent of individuality, the bearer of (individual) life, life - force (as extending also over rebirths), principle of conscious life, general consciousness (as function of mind and matter), regenerative force, animation, mind as transmigrant, as transforming (according to individual kamma) one individual life (after death) into the next. (See also below, c & d). In this (fundamental) application it may be characterized as the sensory and perceptive activity commonly expressed by "mind." It is difficult to give any one word for v., because there is much difference between the old Buddhist and our modern points of view, and there is a varying use of the term in the Canon itself. In what may be a very old Sutta S ii.95 v. is given as a synonym of citta (q. v.) and mano (q. v.), in opposition to kāya used to mean body. This simpler uneclesiastical, unscholastic popular meaning is met with in other suttas. E. g. the body (kāya) is when animated called sa-viññānaka (q. v. and cp. viññāṇatta). Again, v. was supposed, at the body's death, to pass over into another body (S i.122; iii.124) and so find a support or platform (paṭiṭṭhā). It was also held to be an immutable, persistent substance, a view strongly condemned (M i.258). Since, however, the persistence of v. from life to life is declared (D ii.68; S iii.54), we must judge that it is only the immutable persistence that is condemned. V. was justly conceived more as "minding" than as "mind." Its form is participial. For later variants of the foregoing cp. Miln 86; PvA 63, 219. Ecclesiastical scholastic dogmatic considers v. under the categories of (a) khandha; (b) dhātu; (c) paṭiccasamuppāda; (d) āhāra; (e) kāya. (a) V. as fifth of the five khandhas (q. v.) is never properly described or defined. It is an ultimate. But as a factor of animate existence it is said to be the discriminating (vijānāti) of e. g. tastes or sapid things (S iii.87), or, again, of pleasant or painful feeling (M i.292). It is in no wise considered as a condition, or a climax of the other incorporeal khandhās. It is just one phase among others of mental life. In mediaeval dogmatic it appears rather as the bare phenomenon of aroused attention, the other khandhās having been reduced to adjuncts or concomitants brought to pass by the arousing of v. (Cpd. 13), and as such classed under cetasikā, the older sankhārakkhandha. - (b) as dhātu, v. occurs only in the category of the four elements with space as a sixth element, and also where dhātu is substituted for khandha (S iii.10). - (c) In the chain of causation (Paṭicca-samuppāda) v. is conditioned by the sankhāras and is itself a necessary condition of nāma-rūpa (individuality). See e. g. S ii.4, 6, 8, 12 etc.; Vin i.1; Vism 545 sq.=VbhA 150; Vism 558 sq.; VbhA 169 sq.; 192. — At S ii.4=iii.61 viññāṇa (in the Paṭicca - samuppāda) is defined in a similar way to the defn under v. - ṭṭhiti (see c), viz. as a quality peculiar to (& underlying) each of the 6 senses: "katamaṃ viññāṇaṃ? cha - y - ime viññāṇa - kāyā (groups of v.), viz. cakkhu° sota° etc.," which means that viññāṇa is the apperceptual or energizing principle, so to speak the soul or life (substratum, animator, lifepotency) of the sensory side of individuality. It arises through the mutual relation of sense and sense - object (M iii.281, where also the 6 v. - kāyā). As such it forms a factor of rebirth, as it is grouped under upadhi (q. v.). Translations of S ii.4: Mrs. Rh. D. (K.S. ii.4) "consciousness"; Geiger (in Z. f. B. iv.62) "Erkennen." - (d) As one of the four āhāras (q. v.) v. is considered as the material, food or cause, through which comes rebirth (S ii.13; cp. B.Psy. p. 62). As such it is likened to seed in the field of action (kamma) A i.223, and as entering (a body) at rebirth the phrase viññāṇassa avakkanti is used (D ii.63; S ii.91). In this connection the expression paṭisandhi — viññāṇa first appears in Ps i.52, and then in the Commentaries (VbhA 192; cf. Vism 548, 659 paṭisandhicitta); in Vism 554=VbhA 163, the v., here said to be located in the heart, is

made out, at bodily death, "to quit its former G support ' and proceed (pavattati) to another by way of its mental object and other conditions." Another scholastic expression, both early and late, is abhisankhāra-v., or "endowment consciousness," viz. the individual transmigrant or transmitted function (viññāṇa) which supplies the next life with the accumulation of individual merit or demerit or indifference, as it is expressed at Nd2 569a in defn of v. (on Sn 1055: yaṃ kiñci sampajānāsi . . . panujja viññāṇaṃ bhava na tiṭṭhe): puññ' ābhisankhāra - sahaḡata - viññāṇaṃ, apuññ' . . . , ānejj' . . . - Under the same heading at Nd2 569b we find abhisankhāra v. with ref. to the sotāpatti - stage, i. e. the beginning of salvation, where it is said that by the gradual disappearance of abhis. - v. there are still 7 existences left before nāma - rūpa (individuality) entirely disappears. The climax of this development is "anupādi - sesa nibbāna - dhatu," or the nibbāna stage without a remainder (parinibbāna), which is characterized not by an abhisankhāra - v., but by the carimaka-v., or the final vital spark, which is now going to be extinct. This passage is referred to at DhsA 357, where the first half is quoted literally. - (e) As kāya i. e. group, v. is considered psycho - physically, as a factor in senseperception (D iii.243, M iii.281, etc.), namely, the contact between sense - organ and object (medium, $\mu \epsilon \tau \alpha \zeta \acute{u}$ was not taken into account) produces v. of sight, hearing etc. The three factors constitute the v. -kāya of the given sense. And the v. is thus bound to bodily process as a catseye is threaded on a string (D ii.76). Cp. above c. Other applications of the term v., both Canonical and mediaeval: on details as to attributes and functions, see Vin i.13 (as one of the khandhas in its quality of anattā, cp. S iv.166 sq.); D iii.223 (as khandha); S ii.101 sq. (°assa avakkanti); iii.53 sq. (°assa gati, āgati, cuti etc.); A i.223 sq.; iii.40; Sn 734 (yaṃ kiñci dukkhaṃ sambhoti, sabbaṃ viññāṇa - paccayā), 1037 (nāma - rūpa destroyed in consequence of v. destruction), 1073 (cavetha v. [so read for bhavetha]; v. at this passage expld as "punappaṭisandhi - v." at Nd2 569c); 1110 (uparujjhati); Ps i.53 sq., 153 sq.; ii.102; Vbh 9 sq., 53 sq., 86; Nett 15 (nāma - rūpa v. - sampayutta), 16 (v. - hetuka n. - r.), 17 (nirodha), 28, 79, 116 (as khandha); Vism 529 (as simple, twofold, fourfold etc.), 545=VbhA 150 sq. (in detail as product of sankhāras & in 32 groups); VbhA 172 (twofold: vipāka & avipāka); DhA iv.100.

1.2 **Khandhas / Skandhas, in . . . Dasabalasutta (The Ten Powers), Dasabalavagga Saṃyutta Nikāya 12.21**

- **Pali** : "Dasabalasamannāgato, bhikkhave, tathāgato catūhi ca vesārajjehi samannāgato āsabhaṃ ṭhānaṃ paṭijānāti, parisāsu sīhanādaṃ nadati, brahmacakkaā pavatteti - **English** : "Mendicants, a Realized One has ten powers and four kinds of self-assurance. With these he claims the bull's place, roars his lion's roar in the assemblies, and turns the divine wheel.
- **Pali** : *iti rūpaṃ iti rūpassa samudayo iti rūpassa atthaṅgamo*, **English** : Such is form, such is the origin of form, such is the ending of form.
- **Pali** : *iti vedanā iti vedanāya samudayo iti vedanāya atthaṅgamo*, **English** : Such is feeling, such is the origin of feeling, such is the ending of feeling.
- **Pali** : *iti saññā iti saññāya samudayo iti saññāya atthaṅgamo*, **English** : Such is perception, such is the origin of perception, such is the ending of perception.

- **Pali** : *iti saṅkhārā iti saṅkhārānaṃ samudayo iti saṅkhārānaṃ atthaṅgamo*, **English** : Such are choices, such is the origin of choices, such is the ending of choices.
- **Pali** : *iti viññāṇaṃ iti viññāṇassa samudayo iti viññāṇassa atthaṅgamo*. **English** : Such is consciousness, such is the origin of consciousness, such is the ending of consciousness.
- **Pali** : *Iti imasmiṃ sati idaṃ hoti, imassuppādā idaṃ uppajjati*. **English** : When this exists, that is; due to the arising of this, that arises.
- **Pali** : *Imasmiṃ asati idaṃ na hoti, imassa nirodhā idaṃ nirujjhati*. *Yadidaṃ* : **English** : When this doesn't exist, that is not; due to the cessation of this, that ceases. That is :
- **Pali** : *avijjāpaccayā saṅkhārā*; **English** : Ignorance is a condition for choices.
- **Pali** : *saṅkhārapaccayā viññāṇaṃ . . . pe . . .* **English** : Choices are a condition for consciousness. . . .
- **Pali** : *evametassa kevalassa dukkhakkhandhassa samudayo hoti*. **English** : That is how this entire mass of suffering originates.
- **Pali** : *Avijjāya tveva asesavirāganirodhā saṅkhāranirodho*; **English** : When ignorance fades away and ceases with nothing left over, choices cease.
- **Pali** : *saṅkhāranirodhā viññāṇanirodho . . . pe . . .* **English** : When choices cease, consciousness ceases. . . .
- **Pali** : *evametassa kevalassa dukkhakkhandhassa nirodho hoti*”ti. **English** : That is how this entire mass of suffering ceases.”

Since the Buddha is pointing to the impermanence of the 5 factors, it is said that the Khandha or [Sk. skandha] are empty by nature. Further, **in the context of the Mahayana**, THOUGH I DO NOT REMEMBER correctly which one(s), **the Buddha often communicated with Śāriputra regarding being immersed in the state/field of void or emptiness and also gave him instructions/insights related to the state/field of void or emptiness. This has been mentioned in multiple chapters of Paṭisambhidāmagga, in Khuddaka Nikaya of the Sutta Pitaka.**

According to the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the online Pali dictionary at Univ. of Chicago, the word -

- **Suññata** (adj.) [i. e. the abl. suññato used as adj. nom.] void, empty, devoid of lusts, evil dispositions, and karma, but especially of soul, ego Th 2, 46; ThA 50; Dhs 344; Mhvs 37, 7; nibbāna DhsA 221; phassa S iv.295; vimokkha Dh 92; DhA ii.172; Miln 413; vimokkha samādhī, and samāpatti Vin iii.92 sq.; iv.25 sq.; samādhī (contemplation of emptiness, see CpD. 216) D iii.219 (one of. three samādhīs); S iv.360, 363; Miln 337; anupassanā Ps ii.43 sq.
- **Suññatā** (f.) [abstr. fr. suñña] emptiness, "void," unsubstantiality, phenomenality; freedom from lust, ill - will, and dullness, Nibbāna M iii.111; Kvu 232; DhsA 221; Nett 118 sq., 123 sq., 126; Miln 16; Vism 333 (n'atthi; suñña; vivitta; i, e. abhāva, suññatā, vivitt' - ākāra), 578 (12 fold, relating to the Paṭiccasamuppāda), 653 sq.; VbhA 262 (atta°, attaniya°,

niccabhāva°). -pakāsana the gospel of emptiness DA i.99, 123; -paṭisamyutta relating to the Void, connected with Nibbāna A i.72=iii.107=S ii.267; DA i.100 sq.; Miln 16; -vihāra dwelling in the concept of emptiness Vin ii.304; M iii.104, 294. See on term e. g. Cpd. 69; Kvu trsln 142, n. 4.

1.3 The **Emptiness of Khandhas / Skandhas in Prajna-Paramita-Hridaya/the Heart Sutra**

This build up of material is actually to point to the Heart Sutra of the Mahayana. In the article titled - **Prajna-Paramita-Hridaya/the Heart Sutra: Bhagavati, the Heart of Transcendental Knowledge** by Sinha (2017), available @ <https://osf.io/8hn5e/files/6zpsv>, which forms a chapter of the book, titled - **In the stillness of awareness, let nature unfold as it is - Sit still and be : A collection of research papers and insights into Shakyamuni Buddha's teachings** (with ISBN (978-93-343-1848-7), i would like the readers to go through a section of this work on the emptiness of the skandhas, which i reproduce here for completeness -

1.3.1 T. Yang dey tse jang chub sem pa sem pa chen po pak pa chen re zik, wang chuk she rab kyi pa rol tu chin pa zab moy cho pa nyi la nam par ta zhing pung po nga po de dak la, yang rang zhin gyi tong par nam par tao/

T. And at the same time noble Avalokiteshvara, the bodhisattva-mahasattva, looking at the practice of profound transcendent knowledge, saw that those five *skandhas* are empty by nature.

N. *He looks at the practice of profound transcendent knowledge.* The practice of the way to enter *Samadhi* via meditation on form (i.e using support *alambana*) to meditation without form (i.e formless without support) in order to experience the truth of emptiness, has been stressed upon. He is looking at the practice first. The knowledge is there, but he is looking at the practice first. This is crucial. He is pointing to the fact that the practice is important. Without proper practice, it is not possible to acquire the deep knowledge. The way to acquire knowledge is absolutely essential.

Then, through the experience of the emptiness in heart, the bodhisattva experiences emptiness in *skandhas*. Experience in heart cannot be matched with limited understanding of the mind as they are beyond the mind.

Now, why does the sutta start with skandhas and not any other aspect? A stupid answer is that one has to start somewhere. But jokes apart, the spiritual journey begins with existence of constituents that form an important aspect of a cycle. Here, by experiential knowledge of the heart, the former Buddha acknowledges the existence of the cycle that is crucial for existence of cycle that is crucial for existence of samsara and later on uses the steps in the cycle to experience nirvana. So first there is recognition of existence of cycle through the experiential knowledge and then the cycle is used to unlock this process of repeated births and deaths. He does not say that the cycle is bad. If one notices, Siddhartha as Buddha starts his final journey as Bodhisattva some 534 life times back (as in Jataka Tales) and uses this knowledge of *Samsara* (the inherent cycle), birth after birth to enter *parinirvana*. Again, he is not condemning the cycle. There is an acknowledgement in experience. *If one has not experienced the fundamentals of the nature of the cycle by which things are working in Samsara, then it is not easy to grasp the way to unlock this cycle.*

Q. **What are these five skandhas?**

Exposition - The five skandhas or aggregates that constitutes the various aspects of samsara or the world i.e the form (*rupa*), sensations or feelings (*vedana*), perceptions (*samjna*), mental forma-

tions (*sankhara*), and consciousness (*vijnana*). There is form or body (*rupa*) and within the form are sensations (*vedana*). The perception (*samjna*) of these sensations exists and repeated perceptions (*samjna*) of the sensations lead to impressions (*sankhara*) in the mind body complex. And in the flow of consciousness (*vijnana*) the impressions (*sankhara*) pushes one to take the next action in order to maintain the cycle. These are fundamental elements which form an integral aspect of a greater cycle of *Samsara*. In a deeper sense *Samsara* or the world is a projection either dynamic or static and neither dynamic nor static aspects which has the property to veil and superimpose the universal truths regarding life and not allow one to see the way things are (i.e *yatha-bhuta*). There are two kinds of truths, namely - *paramartha* or the absolute truth and the *samvritta* or the relative truths of the world. One finds contradictions in the relative truths but the absolute is beyond the relative. Now this doesn't mean that the relative truths are of no value and *Samsara* is bad. It is *Samsara* which prepares one to transcend into the higher states of truth and leads to *nirvana*. Thus *Samsara* is a means or a school where one passes one step at a time to finally merge into the absolute. This is a way of expressing in the relative terms but note that the *Samsara* is connected to *nirvana* through and through. The goal (*nirvana*) and the way to the goal (in *Samsara*) are here and now as the river and the ocean is connected through and through. *Again, it is important to value the path that is there in this Samsara.*

Now again, there are two aspects of the journey. Mostly one is focused on the goal, but rarely one is focused on the way to the goal. The second is extremely rare case where the journey is more important than the goal. Kamalasila explains in his profound and deep treatise on *Bhavanakrama* (the steps of meditation) that there are usually two kinds of mindsets in enlightened ones. The first is the *pranidhi-chitta* or the mind fixed on the goal and the second is the *prasthanachitta* or the mind aware of the journey to the goal. This second one is an extremely rare case where a being is more focused on the journey rather than the goal and is referred to as entering the path of *anuttara-samyak-sambodhi*.

So to recapitulate, the five *skandhas* or aggregates, that constitutes the various aspects of *samsara* or the world are the form (*rupa*), sensations or feelings (*vedana*), perceptions (*samjna*), mental formations (*sankhara*), and consciousness (*vijnana*). Form (*rupa*) can be any image in any dimension that contains a boundary and gives the perception (*samjna*) of a compounded formation. Perception helps in the cognition of a form (*rupa*) and repeated perceptions of a phenomena or object of perception through sensations (*vedana*) towards the object of perception, in the flow of consciousness (*vijnana*) leads to mental formations (*sankhara*). Thus a cycle is formed. A cycle which leads one from birth to death to birth and so on!

Q. [What is the procedure of seeing emptiness?](#)

But before delving deeply into how the cycle works, it is important to know how one sees emptiness in all these five *skandhas*. Seeing is not through the ordinary eyes. It is through the heart. When the heart experiences and absorbs a knowledge through awareness, then the heart sees through the nature of the object under investigation. Thus the way is simple. It is by letting emptiness come to awareness and dissolving the individuality completely into emptiness. This happens through meditation. *Now one does not create emptiness. Emptiness is not an object of meditation. It is already there but it has not been experienced in the heart.* When the essence of emptiness or *shunyata* is experienced in the heart through meditation (i.e *bhavanamayi-prajna*), one experiences the emptiness in form (*rupa*), sensations or feelings (*vedana*), perceptions (*samjna*), mental formations (*sankhara*) and consciousness (*vijnana*). A more detailed explanation of experiencing emptiness is given in latter exposition below. That is how one sees emptiness in the *skandhas*. Finally, emptiness cannot

be described in words as it is directly connected to the *paramartha* or the absolute truth. Being not connected to the relative truths or *samvritti*, it can only be experienced in heart. Emptiness in heart, leads to emptiness in mind.

1.3.2 T. De ne Sangye kyi tu tse dang den pa Sha ri bu jang chub sem pa sem pa chen po pak pa chen re zik wang chuk la di ke che me so/ Rik kyi bu am rik kyi bu mo gang la la she rab kyi pa rol tu chin pa zab moy cho pa che par do pa de ji tar lab par ja/ De ke che me pa dang/

T. Then through the power of the Buddha, venerable Shariputra said to noble Avalokiteshvara, the bodhisattva-mahasattva, “How should those noble men and women learn, who wish to follow the practice of profound transcendent knowledge?” Thus he spoke.

N. *How should noble men and women learn this?* Already the quality of people who would learn this knowledge has been stated. See, this is not for everybody as qualification has already set. There needs to be nobility and maturity, that has been developed by merit. Without this it might not be possible grasp this knowledge. This knowledge is highly advanced. The practice of the profound transcendent knowledge, is the way to meditate where one uses the the cycle and the constituents of *samsara* to experience the absolute truths and finally unlock the cycle to get completely absorbed into *parinirvana*. See, there is a wish to learn. It is not a desire but a need as the heart has already experienced something. They are looking for a way out. Also, the Buddha raises Avalokitesvara to a higher platform by asking him to share and teach. He does not say that ”i am higher than you and thus you can’t teach!” He is lifting the other being up to a higher level.

1.3.3 T. Jang chub sem pa sem pa chen po pak pa chen re zik wang chuk gi tse dang den pa sha ra da ti bu la di ke che me so/ Sha ri bu rik kyi bu am rik kyi bu mo gang la la she rab kyi pa rol tu chin pa zab moy cho pa che par do pa de di tar nam par ta war ja te/

T. And noble Avalokiteshvara, the bodhisattva-mahasattva, answered the venerable Shariputra with these words: ”Shariputra, those noble men and women who wish to follow the practice of profound transcendent knowledge should look at it like this :”

1.3.4 T. Pung po nga po de dak khyang rang zhin gyi tong par yang dak par je su tao/

T. The five skandhas should be seen correctly to be empty by nature.

Q. *Again, how does one see the nature of emptiness in the skandhas?*

N. This has already been dealt with in the earlier exposition above but to recapitulate, it is through meditation and letting one’s identity dissolve in emptiness. By the process of meditation one lets the myriads of phenomena and objects come into awareness and pass off thus clearing the mind and making it transparent enough to let the emptiness shine forth. Also, when these myriads of phenomena and objects rises to awareness and makes its presence felt and then moves away, during that period of experience of the phenomena or object, the empty nature of the phenomena or object manifests itself. It is because of the empty nature of the phenomena or the object that it slowly and steadily dissolves in awareness after making its presence felt. Thus by merging oneself completely into emptiness, one sees the empty nature of the *skandhas*.

So, if a form (*rupa*) appears in awareness, its intensity rises to a peak and then dissolves. In that duration of appearance, the empty nature of the form is experienced in the heart. Due to the empty

nature, it does not hold (that is the grip of form) for long and dissolves in awareness. Similarly, for any kind of sensation (i.e. *vedana*) appearing in the body complex rises to a peak in awareness and then subsides. The related perception (*samjna*) of the sensation also follows the same principle. Repeated perceptions of the sensations lead to mental formations (or *sankharas*) which again appear in awareness as one sits to meditate after a long gap.

Finally, in the flow of consciousness (i.e. *vijnanam*) the impressions and the sensations lead to flow of next action. Consciousness itself is revealed in awareness. It is not possible to express consciousness in words but its presence is experienced in awareness. Now the nature of all these aggregates is revealed when emptiness consumes the individuality and what remains is universal awareness that shines forth and shows the nature of the aggregates.

Now, emptiness does not mean that one is devoid of anything. Emptiness encompasses everything. Emptiness makes one lose the individuality and in awareness the nature of the different phenomena manifest. This again is experienced in the heart and mere intellectual or mental repetition will not help. The knowledge is to be absorbed in the heart. Why? Emptiness cannot be described in words as it is directly connected to the *paramartha* or the absolute truth. Being not connected to the relative truths or *samvritti*, it can only be experienced in heart.

Emptiness in heart, leads to emptiness in mind. Emptiness cleans you inside out. Emptiness is already there but there is a layer that covers the mind and heart from experiencing emptiness. An important note is that awareness is needed to experience the absolute truth. If there is no awareness, then it might not be possible to acquire the required knowledge. Awareness is there in each and every individual but there is a casing over it. In deep meditations, the individuality is lost and universal nature of awareness shines forth. Refining this life after life, the bodhisattvas move to buddhahood thus having universal awareness. Finally, entering *parinirvana*, one leaves the field of universal awareness also as one is absorbed in the absolute truth.

1.3.5 T. Zuk tong pao/ Tong pa nyi zuk so/ Zuk le kyang tong pa nyi zhen ma yin/ Tong pa nyi le kyang zuk zhen ma yin no/

T. Form (*rupa*) is emptiness, emptiness itself is form; emptiness is no other than form, form is no other than emptiness.

N. It is easy to know that form (*rupa*) is emptiness in meditation. But how does one acquire the knowledge that emptiness is form itself? In the previous paragraph it is expressed that emptiness encompasses everything. There are stages in deep meditation when emptiness is experienced in complete totality and it is in those moments that emptiness is experienced as basis of all forms. In turn, by experience one concludes that emptiness is form itself as it is the basis of all phenomena and objects of perception. In slightly more paradoxical term it is the formless form! (through experience)

1.3.6 T. De zhin du tsor wa dang/ Du she dang/ Du je dang/ Nam par she pa nam tong pao/

T. In the same way feeling, perception, formation and consciousness are empty.

N. Again, how to observe the emptiness in all these has already covered in the foregoing paragraphs. But note that experiencing emptiness in subtle phenomena as perception and consciousness requires many years of deep meditative seatings. Mere words will not help. So consider this as a precautionary measure and remember that the procedure to see the emptiness in

the various aspects remains the same. Also, some experiential knowledge can only be transferred in silence. Thus, feeling/perception/consciousness is emptiness. Similarly, emptiness is feeling/perception/consciousness.

1.3.7 T. Sharibu de ta we na cho tam che tong pa nyi de/ Tsen nyi me pa/

T. Thus, Shariputra, all *dharmas* are emptiness and have no characteristics.

N. Now before we begin to comprehend this, note that this is a highly paradoxical statement. In the beginning of the journey in into the realms of enlightenment, one takes on vows and precepts which are an integral part of the *dharmas* (they also mean the discipline that one takes on oneself in order to progress on the path and live in accordance with the universal laws of nature in a harmonious manner). But here it is stated that all *dharmas* are emptiness and have no characteristic in themselves. "Look! *Dharma* has no characteristics. Why meditate? Why discipline? Throw everything off! Let's eat 5 times a day and see what happens!"

The first thing to understand is that the statement is given by a being who has already crossed certain stage in spiritual realm and is expressing the essence of the teachings of the heart sutra after the experience has already transpired and insight has dawned in the heart. If a person has not crossed certain realms and considers and applies the knowledge that is presented here in day to day life, it will lead to troubles in life. So one needs to carefully understand and absorb the fact that appreciating the knowledge here is through the experience in the heart and not just blind application of what is being stated in the *sutta*. Now the main issue of emptiness in the *dharmas*. What happens when one meditates and delves oneself in the realms of the emptiness? Slowly and steadily the *dharmas* which have protected one on the path to enlightenment fade away as one crosses the bridge of enlightenment. In that sense, after crossing the bridge of enlightenment, as emptiness dawns within oneself, one sees the emptiness in the *dharmas*. But by no means does it say that it is condemning the *dharmas* or for that matter any object or phenomena that comes to awareness. Here one investigates completely yet honouring all that has come to awareness. In day to day life, one honours all that comes to awareness, but in meditation, one finds the emptiness in each an every one. This paradoxical experience can be a bit shocking to people who are new to such knowledge or they might miss it completely if the spirit behind the words has not been grasped properly, thus making fun of the words in the *sutta*. So be careful while reading these *suttas*. Finally, there is another aspect to view the essence of these teachings. Initially, one takes an object or support (i.e. *alambana*) for the process of meditation. But as one delves into the emptiness, in awareness, the identity and the characteristics of the support (*alambana*) simply dissolves. Again, this doesn't mean that the *alambana* should be treated with disrespect and should be thrown away. They are a means of progress in one's spiritual journey. One is sitting still and the fields of ignorance in the form of body (*kaya*), sensations (*vedana*), mind and flow of mind (*chitta*), the *dharmas* come into awareness and makes its presence felt and slowly dissolve into emptiness (in meditation). So one is using the constituents of ignorance as a support in *samsara* to unlock the cycle and enter the formless state of meditation. One uses the four ways of *anupashyanas* life after life to enter truth by erasing layers of *sankhara*!

The *dharmas* are emptiness and have no characteristics, holds true, when emptiness is experienced. The experiential knowledge never leaves a being, but the heard or contemplated knowledge might.

2 The Buddha, on **depend / interdepend** . . .

imasmiṃ sati, in . . . Bahudhātukasutta (Many Elements), Majjhima Nikāya (115 Middle Discourses)

2.1 qualified to be called 'skilled in dependent origination' or '**paṭicca-samuppāda**'?

- **Pali** : "Kittāvatā pana, bhante, 'paṭiccasamuppādakusalo bhikkhū'ti alamvacanāyā"ti? **English** : "But sir, how is a mendicant qualified to be called 'skilled in dependent origination'?"
- **Pali** : "Idhānanda, bhikkhu evaṃ pajānāti : **English** : "It's when a mendicant understands:
- **Pali** : '**imasmiṃ sati idaṃ hoti, imassuppādā idaṃ uppajjati**, **English** : 'When this exists, that is; due to the arising of this, that arises.
- **Pali** : **imasmiṃ asati idaṃ na hoti, imassa nirodhā idaṃ nirujjhati, yadidaṃ** - **English** : When this doesn't exist, that is not; due to the cessation of this, that ceases. **That is** :
- **Pali** : **avijjāpaccayā saṅkhārā**, **English** : Ignorance is a condition for impressions.
- **Pali** : **saṅkhārapaccayā viññānaṃ**, **English** : Impressions are conditions for consciousness.
- **Pali** : **viññānapaccayā nāmarūpaṃ**, **English** : Consciousness is a condition for name and form.
- **Pali** : **nāmarūpapaccayā saḷāyatanāṃ**, **English** : Name and form are conditions for the six sense fields.
- **Pali** : **saḷāyatanapaccayā phasso**, **English** : The six sense fields are conditions for contact.
- **Pali** : **phassapaccayā vedanā**, **English** : Contact is a condition for feeling.
- **Pali** : **vedanāpaccayā taṇhā**, **English** : Feeling is a condition for craving.
- **Pali** : **taṇhāpaccayā upādānaṃ**, **English** : Craving is a condition for grasping.
- **Pali** : **upādānapaccayā bhavo**, **English** : Grasping is a condition for continued existence.
- **Pali** : **bhavapaccayā jāti**, **English** : Continued existence is a condition for rebirth.
- **Pali** : **jātipaccayā jarāmarāṇaṃ sokaparidevadukkhadomanassūpāyāsā sambhavanti**. **English** : Rebirth is a condition for old age and death, sorrow, lamentation, pain, sadness, and distress to come to be.
- **Pali** : **Evametassa kevalassa dukkhakkhandhassa samudayo hoti**. **English** : That is how this entire mass of suffering originates.
- **Pali** : **Avijjāya tveva asesavirāganirodhā saṅkhāranirodho**, **English** : When ignorance fades away and ceases with nothing left over, choices cease.
- **Pali** : **saṅkhāranirodhā viññānanirodho**, **English** : When choices cease, consciousness ceases.

- **Pali** : *viññāṇanirodhā nāmarūpanirodho*, **English** : When consciousness ceases, name and form cease.
- **Pali** : *nāmarūpanirodhā saḷāyatanirodho*, **English** : When name and form cease, the six sense fields cease.
- **Pali** : *saḷāyatanirodhā phassanirodho*, **English** : When the six sense fields cease, contact ceases.
- **Pali** : *phassanirodhā vedanānirodho*, **English** : When contact ceases, feeling ceases.
- **Pali** : *vedanānirodhā taṇhānirodho*, **English** : When feeling ceases, craving ceases.
- **Pali** : *taṇhānirodhā upādānanirodho*, **English** : When craving ceases, grasping ceases.
- **Pali** : *upādānanirodhā bhavanirodho*, **English** : When grasping ceases, continued existence ceases.
- **Pali** : *bhavanirodhā jātinirodho*, **English** : When continued existence ceases, rebirth ceases.
- **Pali** : *jātinirodhā jarāmaṇaṃ sokaparidevadukkhadomanassūpāyāsā nirujjhanti*. **English** : When rebirth ceases, old age and death, sorrow, lamentation, pain, sadness, and distress cease.
- **Pali** : *Evametassa kevalassa dukkhakkhandhassa nirodho hoti.* **English** : That is how this entire mass of suffering ceases.’
- **Pali** : *Ettāvata kho, ānanda, ’paṭiccasamuppādakusalo bhikkhū’ti alaṃvacanāyā’ti.* **English** : *That’s how a mendicant is qualified to be called ‘skilled in dependent origination’.*”

2.2 Just the **basics of Paṭicca-samuppāda or dependent origination** from Sinha (2017)

In the Saṃyutta Nikāya 12.1, Buddhavagga, Paṭiccasamuppādasutta (Dependent Origination) . . .

Bhagavā etad avoca:

The Buddha said this:

paṭiccasamuppādaṃ vo, bhikkhave, desessāmi.

”Bhikkhus, I will teach you dependent origination”.

Taṃ suṇātha, sādhukaṃ manasi karotha, bhāsissāmi’ti.

”Listen and apply your mind well, I will speak”.

’Katamo ca, bhikkhave, paṭiccasamuppādo?’

”And what, bhikkhus, is dependent origination?”

Avijjā-paccayā, bhikkhave, saṅkhārā,

Ignorance, bhikkhus, causes impressions,

saṅkhāra-paccayā viññāṇaṃ;

impressions causes flow in consciousness,

viññāṇa-paccayā nāmarūpaṃ;

the flow of consciousness causes the appearance of name and form,

nāma-rūpa-paccayā saḷāyatanam;

with name and form arise the senses and the complex interactions,

saḷāyatana-paccayā phasso;

due to the senses and complex interactions arise contact,

phassa-paccayā vedanā;

due to contact arises sensation,

vedanā-paccayā taṇhā;

with sensation arises desire (craving and aversion),

taṇhā-paccayā upādānam;

with desire arises attachment,

upādāna-paccayā bhavo;

with attachment comes existence,

bhava-paccayā jāti;

due to existence birth happens,

jāti-paccayā jarā-maraṇam-soka-parideva-dukkha-domanassupāyāsā sambhavanti.

with birth comes old age, death, grief, lamentation, sorrow (physical, mental and spiritual), bitterness of mind and other tribulations.

Evametassa kevalassa dukkhakkhandhassa samudayo hoti.

Thus by this arises the chunks of sorrow in life . . .

Ayam vuccati, bhikkhave, paṭiccasamuppādo.

This is called dependent origination.

Of utmost importance is the fact that Siddhartha sets on the journey, by acknowledging the existence of cycle that leads to *samsāra*, while experiencing the knowledge and puts forth in words. The cycle begins with the words ignorance. Please remember this!

2.2.1 Avijjā - ignorance

What is ignorance? What are the properties which makes one recognize ignorance and what are the ingredients which constitutes ignorance? The spirit behind the word ignorance is to capture the nature of compounded materials that blocks awareness from (1) observing the way things are as well as (2) recognizing itself as awareness. These compounded materials can be classified into three divisions, namely (1) the gross materials composed of natural elements of earth, water, fire, air and space. These materials help in constituting the physical bodies of many life forms (both sentient and non sentient beings) (2) the mental materials that constitute various faculties by which different life forms exhibit different temperaments and behaviour. These temperaments and behaviour are often reflected in action through the physical bodies. Note that there are beings without physical bodies also, whose presence comes to awareness (in case the awareness is refined). (3) Finally, the third material is the spiritual matter that constitutes aspects of life as life force in different forms of sentient and insentient beings. Thus there exist the physical, mental and spiritual bodies (compounded materials or ignorance) of a being, each finer than the other.

All these compounded materials work in tandem with a few more dimensions like time, energy, will and nature. Working in parallel with all these dimensions, ignorance has the property to superimpose layers which do not allow awareness to observe the way things are and also to veil or obstruct awareness from recognizing itself as awareness.

2.2.2 *Saṅkhārā* - impressions

It is these layers (superimpositions) and obstructions (veils) that are like impressions which is referred to as *saṅkhārā*. Now awareness is universal in nature, but depending on the amount of *saṅkhārā* and the individuality reflected in ego, awareness gets restricted in recognizing its own universal nature. *Saṅkhārā* or layers of impressions can be of various types and intensity. It is due to the intensity of the *saṅkhārā* that the cycle of birth and death is maintained. The maintenance of the circulating nature of the cycle is done by consciousness or *viññāṇam*.

2.2.3 *viññāṇam* - consciousness

Consciousness helps in maintaining the flow in nature. It has that ability to store the impressions and propel a being into next cycle based on those impressions and their strengths. These impressions can be favourable /pleasant or unfavourable/ unpleasant. Depending on the kinds of accumulated impression the formation of the new identity and form is established. Some impressions lead to merit filled life and others to demerit filled life. The formation of new identity and form is referred to as *nāma-rūpaṃ*.

2.2.4 *Nāma-Rūpaṃ* - name (also meaning mind) and form (also meaning matter)

The name and form has an identity attached to it. For example, the symbol 0, the name of 0 as zero and the meaning as its identity attached to it. The form is the system that helps carry the current impressions and that of the past. It is also this form and the identity attached to it which interacts with the different stimuli via the different senses simultaneously. The individual identity is a mental aspect at a particular cycle. This along with the form interacts through the senses. This complex interaction through the senses is referred to as *saḷāyatanaṃ*.

2.2.5 *saḷāyatana* - Senses and its interaction

The senses and its complex interaction happens through contact with the different stimuli from the external environment and the internal working of the mind-body complex or *nāma-rūpa*. This contact is referred to as *phasso*.

2.2.6 *Phasso* - contact

Contact can happen at three different realms (1) the physical realm and the senses of physical dimensions (2) mental realm and the faculties of mental dimension and (3) spiritual realm and the faculties of spiritual dimension. Due to this contact arises sensation with the mind-body complex. The sensation(s) are referred to as *vedanā*.

2.2.7 *Vedanā* - sensation

Vedanā is sensation within the frame work of mind-body complex or naam-rupa. Also, the sensation might arise due to many of the infinite phenomena occurring in nature. These sensations can be labeled as favourable/pleasant or unfavourable/unpleasant depending on one's structure of the mind-body complex. Note that this complex can also constitute the life forces which form the spiritual body of a sentient/insentient being. Depending on the quality of sensation craving or aversion arises.

Example - One sees an ice-cream and contact has been made. This contact leads to sensations in mind and body, which either have a force of desire for or against the object of contact. Based on repeated perception, *Sañkhāra* of ice-cream happens in the flow of consciousness. At the end, one consumes so much ice-cream that body becomes sick in nature.

2.2.8 *Taṇhā* - desire/craving/aversion

The desire and the craving and aversion associated is referred to as *taṇhā*. It is this craving and aversion that keeps a being from being free. Depending on the intensity of sensation, craving and aversion appear in equivalent intensity. With craving/aversion attachment dawns towards object of craving/ aversion. This object can be of any form i.e material, mental or spiritual. The composition of this object is again based on the building blocks of material, mental and spiritual components that constitutes ignorance. Thus the *skandhas* are an integral part of explanation and appear in the beginning of the *sutta*.

2.2.9 *Upādānaṃ* - attachment

The attachment towards object of craving/aversion is upadan. Attachment here means affinity towards object of craving/ aversion. This affinity is a direct connection to the object in attention either through the force of craving or through the force of aversion. For example, "i like ice-cream" - the strength behind liking connects one to the object ice-cream in an attractive way. On the other hand, "i don't like ice-cream" - the strength behind not liking connects one to the object ice-cream in a repulsive way (Deeper explanation will follow below). Similarly, attachment can be for any phenomena/being in the existential world.

2.2.10 *Bhava* - existence

The existence that happens due to the attachment is called as bhava. The attachment forces one to come into existence. This existence happens through the formation of spiritual body, the mental body and then the material/physical body.

2.2.11 *Jāti* - birth

This formation of spiritual/mental/physical body is nothing but birth and referred to as jati. Due to birth (*jāti*) arises old age (*jarā*), death (*marañan*), grief (*soka*), lamentation (*paridev*), sorrow physical, mental and spiritual (*dukkha*), bitter mindedness (*domanassa*) all come through. It is because of this that the entire mass of sorrow arises.

2.3 Grasping via example, . . . how because of the Khandha or skandha and paṭiccasamuppada or dependent origination, that fire or conflagration of craving / aversion or taṇhā makes you run?

Lets take the example of an ice-cream. Suppose one is walking and see an ice-cream photo and the vendor standing by (may be for the first time OR a repetition).

One sees via eyes, that is one of the 6 *saḷāyatana*, which is a part of *nāma-rūpa*. This sight of the ice-cream, is phassa or contact, . . . the *saññā* or perception of which, . . . causes (*paccayā*), *vedanā*

or sensations in mind and body. Due to these sensations, within the mind-body-heart complex, . . . *taṇhā* i.e desire and the craving for or aversion against, the ice-cream arises within. Now this force of desire, either for or against, and the grip of the desire, lead to *upādānaṃ* or attachment, either in loving the object of *saññā* (perception) or hating the object of *saññā* (perception). Based on this, either one consumes the ice-cream or does not eat it! Further, based on repeated *saññā* or perception, *saṅkhārā* of ice-cream, registers within the mind-body-heart of a being and these *saṅkhārā*'s lead to a flow of *viññārā* consciousness.

Thus, this fire or conflagration of desire or *taṇhā*, based on the impressions or *saṅkhārā*, which burns one's senses or *salāyatana*, as one repeats the process of enjoyment, makes one run, and run and run . . .

At the end, one consumes or enjoys so much ice-cream that body and mind becomes full of *roga* or sickness in nature, as age progresses.

2.4 The **acknowledgement of 4 Noble Truths and the way out, via Vipassanā / vipaśyanā**

Thus begins the *acknowledgement of the first truth, i.e there is misery in life*. This acknowledgement can only happen when one realizes through ones heart and not just via knowledge gained through senses or through intellectual curiosity. *Next, this misery is due to a cause which forms the second truth*. Since *misery is not perennial, there is the cause which can be eliminated; the third truth*. Finally, the *fourth truth is the revelation that there is "a" way out. It is not "the" way out, but there is "a" way out. There is no force here, but an acknowledgement of an existence of a way out of this misery and the countless cycles of birth and death*.

These four truths reveal the fundamental nature of phenomena that occurs in a life form (sentient/insentient). The solution to the issues encountered in the four truths are revealed in the next four truths. These truths are basically processes going through which leads to breaking of the cycle of birth and death as well as the miseries associated with it.

To begin with, the essence is to sit still and be. To sit not like a rigid stone on a ground, but as a lotus flower resting on the surface of a pond. Note that the spinal cord needs to be erect with head straight and eyes closed. Now, what happens when one sits still and be? Whatever phenomena in the mind-body-consciousness complex manifests with strongest intensity, comes to awareness. Depending on the structure of one's body, texture of mind and the quality of consciousness, a corresponding experience comes to awareness. For example, if one sits still after having a nice exercise, the temperature of the body comes to awareness. The awareness experiences the intensity of the temperature of the body rising to a peak and then passing off, as a wave rises to a peak and then falls off. Similarly, the density of the body, the throbbing of the heart, the flux of the blood, the flow of the natural breath comes to awareness. The silent untampered experiential acknowledgement or observation by the awareness of the happening phenomena in the gross body is referred to as *kayanupaschyana*.

Longer sittings lead to refinement in awareness when the sensations in the body mainly in the form of currents in the nervous system are experienced. Due to the texture of mind-body complex at a particular moment in time, these subtle sensations might appear as extremely painful, stressful, soothing or blissful (to name a few) in awareness. Again, the silent untampered experiential acknowledgement or observation by the awareness of the happening phenomena is referred to as *vedananupaschyana*.

Deeper sittings lead to further refinement in awareness when the flow of the thoughts or the texture of the mind is experience. Anger, greed, happiness, bitterness, gratefulness, a child like nature, lust to name a few, comes to awareness. The texture of the mind comes to awareness. Silent untampered experiential acknowledgement or observation by the awareness of the happening phenomena is referred to as *chittanupaschayana*.

Further, when the awareness reaches a more refined state after continued practice, the natural laws pertaining to the mind-body-consciousness complex comes to awareness. The rise, the persistence and the gradual decay of the any phenomena appearing on the complex comes to awareness. If a peaceful nature arises, persists and passes off on this complex, it comes to awareness. This silent untampered experiential acknowledgement or observation by the awareness of the natural rise-persistence-decay law is referred to as *dhammanupaschayana*.

Note that these might happen in any order depending on the nature of the mind-body-consciousness complex at a particular moment in time. Again, advanced sittings lead to a state of awareness when one's discriminative intellect, emotions and individual ego comes to awareness. These arise, persist and gradually dissolve into nothingness. The individuality of the ego is of atomic nature in comparison to the vastness of the universal awareness. Steady continued practice leads to loss of individuality which reveal the nature of universal awareness with innumerable qualities like that of purity, benevolence, compassion, love etc.

But does one see the essence of the teachings? The former buddha is now using the stepping stones of the great cycle which he has already experienced and uses his own body as a foundation stone to unlock the cycle. The kaya or body which is a form of ignorance has now become the stepping stone for meditation. The grip of the body comes to awareness and passes off. So on and so forth with the other aspects of sensations and mind.

A stage comes when there are no wants to go for, no search to go on, no journey to be taken and no effort to be put forth. There is nothing to say, nothing to do and nothing to become. Even the search for nirvana stops. In those moments, the inexplicable state of nirvana manifests. Awareness tastes some nectars in silence. Contentment dawns in awareness and so does abundance as one re-enters the limited domain of nature. Now, even if nirvana happens once, the mind can still be impure and this is not the fully liberated stage. This stage is called Saupadisesa-nibbana. Depending on the individual further stages pass by in time. This journey is long and a slow process for those who wish to walk the slow and a natural path.

It has been heard that Siddhartha begins his journey many life times back to the stage of bodhisattva (*nirvana* experienced for the first time). As a bodhisattva, he begins perfecting the knowledge of unlocking the cycle of *samsara*, life after life. In the last life as Siddhartha, buddhahood dawns in him. *Now an important point is this. If you want to become a Buddha you will never become. But when the heart experiences and realizes that there is nothing to become, then the journey into buddhahood has already begun. He wants to enter parinirvana at the age of 36, but extends his life for a few more years for the benefit of others.* Finally, living a life of Buddha for just one life time, he enters *parinirvana*. *There is/was no desire to live many lives as a Buddha also. The journey ends as truth absorbs him completely, erasing his entire existence. So, nirvana has already been experienced, but previous impressions force the being to again enter the school of samsara to finish what needs to be finished (stage of saupadisesa-nibbana). Life flips between samsara and nirvana as the balance is maintained. Entering parinirvana, this flipping stops.*

Initially, while sitting still, the four (kaya - body, vedana - sensation, chit - mind and dhamma - rise/persistence/decay of natural laws) truths of silent untampered experiential acknowledgement

or observation (*paschyana*) by the awareness are an optimistic, rewarding and a highly scientific way to evolve out of misery.

Extremely important is the way of observation. Neither to be averse with pleasant/unpleasant nor to crave for pleasant/unpleasant phenomena that has come to awareness. In case aversion or craving arises, then there is formation of impressions (sankharas) in the flow of consciousness. Silent untampered experiential acknowledgement or observation leads to dissolution of impressions and liberation from misery. Not in fighting but in silent experiential acknowledgement or observation of the untampered passage of the phenomena in the mind- body-consciousness complex is the way out.

Thus, the words go deep, in Khuddakanikāya, Dhammapada 277-279 Maggavagga 20. Pañcasatabhikkhuvatthu (Aniccalakkhaṇavatthu, Dukkhalakkhaṇavatthu, Anattalakkhaṇavatthu) -

Sabbe saṅkhārā aniccā”ti,

All impressions are impermanent,

yadā paññāya passati;

if observation happens with wisdom (i.e silent untampered experiential acknowledgement or observation)

Atha nibbindati dukkhe,

thus leading to being disgusted with / avoiding / shunning / turn away from suffering,

esa maggo visuddhiyā. this is the path to purity.

Sabbe saṅkhārā dukkhā”ti, All impressions are suffering,

yadā paññāya passati; if observation happens with wisdom (i.e silent untampered experiential acknowledgement or observation)

Atha nibbindati dukkhe, thus leading to being disgusted with / avoiding / shunning / turn away from suffering,

esa maggo visuddhiyā. this is the path to purity.

”Sabbe dhammā anattā”ti, All dhammās do not have an existential identity or are non-self,

yadā paññāya passati; if observation happens with wisdom (i.e silent untampered experiential acknowledgement or observation)

Atha nibbindati dukkhe, thus leading to being disgusted with / avoiding / shunning / turn away from suffering,

esa maggo visuddhiyā. this is the path to purity.

The *flowing thoughts of mind like ”oh i have to observe” when experienced by awareness indicates chittanupaschyana. Right observation breaks this flow. External complexities of life fade away when impurities of one’s own words, deeds and actions in life come to awareness which are a result of the impression of mind-body-consciousness complex.*

Here ends the exposition of the eight truths. The Mahā-saṭṭipātthan sutta will be of great help to those interested. But such knowledge needs a certain level of maturity. And this maturity dawns when one has experienced from one’s heart that there is misery in life. It is only then that the journey begins, in search for freedom from misery. Even some practice to sit still and be, might save one from the misery one finds in. An important aspect to note is that as one sits still, automatically the different aspects of body, sensations, mind and the laws of nature starts coming into awareness. Ob-

ervation happens naturally, without effort. The path is long and here the processes occur naturally. One cannot force one's way here. As a flower blossoms naturally so does advancement towards enlightenment.

Thus the sayings of Kabir goes well -

Dhere dhere re chala re mana,
Slowly slowly o mind,
dhere sabkuch howay,
slowly everything happens in nature,
mali seeche saw ghara,
the gardener waters a hundred pots,
ritu aaye phal howay . . .
when the weather is right, the fruits will arrive . . .

The *initial teachings begin with the description of the misery, the cause of misery, the possibility of elimination of the cause and the way out of it. But note that the advanced stages described in prajna-paramita-sutta does not contradict the initial teachings. Please keep this note in mind when the paradoxical view is reached later on. Finally, the journey is not via negativa. It appears to be so but in fact it is not. Samsara and its constituents are a school that help one prepare for nirvana. The school is not filled with misery. The school provides comfort to move into higher and simpler dimension.* "Oh! Samsara is bad." i am chanting 10,000 times or meditating in silence and a dog comes out of love in my presence and i kick it & say "may all sentient beings be happy!" And again start chanting the mantra. "Nirvana! Nirvana! Quick! The fastest way." Let's have so much focus that i break the rules of samsara. If a queue is there, i get in the middle as i need to finish work by the power of mantra! "Samsara is bad!" My dear! It is the same samsara which has given clothes. Why wear them? Throw them off and walk naked. See what happens! If the flower (*nirvana*) is beautiful then how can mud and water and minerals (*samsara* the school) nourishing the lotus is so bad? Now i am not saying you eat mud. Experience the balance of the paradoxical opposites as they will be revealed in the journey!

2.5 T. She rab kyi pa rol tu chin pey ngak me pa/ *Ta ya ta om gate gate paragate parasamgate bodhi soha/*

T. The mantra of transcendent knowledge is proclaimed : *Ta ya ta om gate gate paragate parasamgate bodhi soha.*

N. Usually one can chant *gate gate paragate parasamgate bodhi soha.* It means the following -

gate gate - going going
paragate - going beyond
parasamgate - transcending all fields
bodhi soha - one merges into the fully liberated state of enlightenment!

How does one go about? Where does one go? Does one keep running around the planet from country to country, or from one planet to the other? One goes in meditation and travels through the myriads of phenomena in meditation. The travel is the journey of the individual to the loss the individuality. One goes beyond the realms of the measurable and the certain and passes that also,

transcending all fields of existences that has to be transcended, to finally merge into the fully liberated state of enlightenment where universal awareness and the truths are all absorbed completely. The individuality is lost completely and truth takes over.

Such is the potency that the mantra carries with it if absorbed properly in time. An *extremely important aspect of this sutta* is the following - The *Hinayana* path which often takes into account the teachings of the *Mahā-saṭṭipāthana sutta* takes the body (*kaya*), sensations (*vedana*), mind and its flow (*chitta*) and the natural laws (*dhamma*) as objects/tools of meditation to help move one from field to another (body, to sensation, to mind, to dhamma) and transcending these fields one after another and going beyond all these, one enters the bodhi enlightened state which is established in emptiness (*shunayata*). Now note that one is using the tools that constitute the samsara (that is which changing, measurable and relative) to dive into nirvana. It is not that *samsara* is separate from *nirvana*; they are connected. *Samsara* is the school that prepares you for *nirvana*. From the use of meditation based on forms/objects/tools to meditation without form or formless meditation where emptiness is the essence of all, one merges into bodhi state. Now the Mahayana path which talks about emptiness is extremely important as it connects to the Hinayana very well. So stating that *Hinayana* and *Mahayana* are different is not correct, as both are connected deeply. There is no division, yet there is no unity in meaning!

The deepest secret of the sutta is one does not go anywhere but sits still with a content heart. Myriads of fields passes in awareness. When samsara is erased, nirvana is experienced. In nirvana, the individual identity is lost. The experiential knowledge of fields of kaya, vedana, chitta, dharma, rising and dissolving in awareness in meditation is the chanting of the sutta without expressing it in words. If one looks at the time when nirvana happens in the Siddharta, he is sitting still under a tree. It is important to note that he sits still. There is no one (human contact) with him in the forest and he sits still. He is not running around, he not chanting mantra or doing this worship or that worship. He sits still. Every aspect appears in awareness and passes of and finally the grip of all phenomenas moves away and nirvana happens in him. The body, the sensations, the flow of mind and the rise and fall of the dharmas come to awareness and pass off. See that he is not running anywhere. He sits still and the various fields pass away in his awareness. The grip of the fields loosens its affect and one nears to the higher or the simpler dimensions of the truth. He is not search for it. The is no journey to take as he sits still. It is crucial. There is no search for power, there is no search for spiritual greatness. He has already acquired it in previous life times and then he leaves everything. There is contentment in the heart as he has finished every thing that he had started. He sits still. There is no want to go for, no search to go on, no journey to be taken and no effort to be put forth. Nothing to say, nothing to do and nothing to become. He just sits still and nirvana happens in him. Yet the mind body complex is still there in Samsara. The deep paradox reflects itself. The mind body complex is there in Samara and yet the other side of the blade that is Nirvana is happening in emptiness. The deep balance is already there. But it has taken him so many lifetimes of hard work in Samsara. Life after life he toils through and acquires merits after merits. He gets defeated but he does not gives up. See the devotion and see the hard work. The journey is so important, and he knows the value of the journey. But we only see the final life. To him the journey was important.

3 A possible remedy i.e bhesajja / pañicchādī to assuage i.e upasamati / milāpeti / vūpasanta, the conflagration / inferno of senses OR the uncontrolled mind . . .

3.1 First of all, what happens due to and in the aftermath of the conflagration / inferno of senses i.e Aggi-ind° OR i.e the uncontrolled mind i.e pākat-indriya . . .

Please read the section 2.3, to revisit what has been explained regarding the senses and its mechanics of how to it makes one propel to act.

3.2 The Buddha on burning / blazing fire

In the Pali transliterations have been represented in <https://theravadan.org/>, by Ben Lawrence, which are the transliterations from Bhante Sujato available under the Creative Commons Zero (CC0 1.0 Universal) from <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>, available at <https://suttacentral.net/?lang=en>; from Bhikkhu Brahmali, translation, in Theravāda Vinayapiṭaka, Mahāvagga (The Great Division), Mahākhandhaka (The great chapter), -

”Sabbam, bhikkhave, ādittam.

“Everything is burning.

Kiñca, bhikkhave, sabbam ādittam?

What is that everything that is burning?

Cakkhu ādittam, rūpā ādittā, cakkhuvīññānam ādittam, cakkhusamphasso āditto, yamidaṃ cakkhusamphassapaccayā uppajjati vedayitam sukham vā dukkham vā adukkhamasukham vā tampi ādittam.

The eye is burning. Sights are burning. Eye consciousness is burning. Eye contact is burning. Whatever feeling arises because of eye contact - whether pleasant, painful, or neither-pleasant-nor-painful - that too is burning.

Kena ādittam?

Burning with what?

Rāgagginā dosagginā mohagginā ādittam, jātiyā jarāya maraṇena sokehi paridevehi dukkhehi domanassehi upāyāsehi ādittanti vadāmi.

Burning with the fire of sensual desire, the fire of ill will, and the fire of confusion; burning with birth, old age, and death; burning with grief, sorrow, pain, aversion, and distress, I say.

Sotam ādittam, saddā ādittā, sotaviññānam ādittam, sotasamphasso āditto, yamidaṃ sotasamphassapaccayā uppajjati vedayitam sukham vā dukkham vā adukkhamasukham vā tampi ādittam.

The ear is burning. Sounds are burning. Ear consciousness is burning. Ear contact is burning. Whatever feeling arises because of ear contact - whether pleasant, painful, or neither-pleasant-nor-painful - that too is burning.

Kena ādittam?

Burning with what?

Rāgagginā dosagginā mohagginā ādittam, jātiyā jarāya maraṇena sokehi paridevehi dukkhehi domanassehi upāyāsehi ādittanti vadāmi.

Burning with the fire of sensual desire, the fire of ill will, and the fire of confusion; burning with birth, old age, and death; burning with grief, sorrow, pain, aversion, and distress, I say.

Ghānaṃ ādittaṃ, gandhā ādittā, ghānaviññāṇaṃ ādittaṃ, ghānasamphasso āditto, yamidaṃ ghānasamphassapaccayā uppajjati vedayitaṃ sukhaṃ vā dukkhaṃ vā adukkhamasukhaṃ vā tampi ādittaṃ.

The nose is burning. Smells are burning. Nose consciousness is burning. Nose contact is burning. Whatever feeling arises because of nose contact - whether pleasant, painful, or neither-pleasant-nor-painful - that too is burning.

Kena ādittaṃ?

Burning with what?

Rāgagginā dosagginā mohagginā ādittaṃ, jātiyā jarāya maraṇena sokehi paridevehi dukkhehi domanassehi upāyāsehi ādittanti vadāmi.

Burning with the fire of sensual desire, the fire of ill will, and the fire of confusion; burning with birth, old age, and death; burning with grief, sorrow, pain, aversion, and distress, I say.

Jivhā ādittā, rasā ādittā, jivhāviññāṇaṃ ādittaṃ jivhāsamphasso āditto, yamidaṃ jivhāsamphassapaccayā uppajjati vedayitaṃ sukhaṃ vā dukkhaṃ vā adukkhamasukhaṃ vā tampi ādittaṃ.

The tongue is burning. Tastes are burning. Tongue consciousness is burning. Tongue contact is burning. Whatever feeling arises because of tongue contact - whether pleasant, painful, or neither-pleasant-nor-painful - that too is burning.

Kena ādittaṃ?

Burning with what?

Rāgagginā dosagginā mohagginā ādittaṃ, jātiyā jarāya maraṇena sokehi paridevehi dukkhehi domanassehi upāyāsehi ādittanti vadāmi.

Burning with the fire of sensual desire, the fire of ill will, and the fire of confusion; burning with birth, old age, and death; burning with grief, sorrow, pain, aversion, and distress, I say.

Kāyo āditto, phoṭṭhabbā ādittā, kāyaviññāṇaṃ ādittaṃ kāyasamphasso āditto, yamidaṃ kāyasamphassapaccayā uppajjati vedayitaṃ sukhaṃ vā dukkhaṃ vā adukkhamasukhaṃ vā tampi ādittaṃ.

The body is burning. Touches are burning. Body consciousness is burning. Body contact is burning. Whatever feeling arises because of body contact - whether pleasant, painful, or neither-pleasant-nor-painful - that too is burning.

Kena ādittaṃ?

Burning with what?

Rāgagginā dosagginā mohagginā ādittaṃ, jātiyā jarāya maraṇena sokehi paridevehi dukkhehi domanassehi upāyāsehi ādittanti vadāmi.

Burning with the fire of sensual desire, the fire of ill will, and the fire of confusion; burning with birth, old age, and death; burning with grief, sorrow, pain, aversion, and distress, I say.

Mano āditto, dhammā ādittā, manoviññāṇaṃ ādittaṃ manosamphasso āditto, yamidaṃ manosamphassapaccayā uppajjati vedayitaṃ sukhaṃ vā dukkhaṃ vā adukkhamasukhaṃ vā tampi ādittaṃ.

The mind is burning. Mental phenomena are burning. Mind consciousness is burning.

Mind contact is burning. Whatever feeling arises because of mind contact - whether pleasant, painful, or neither-pleasant-nor-painful - that too is burning.

Kena ādittam?

Burning with what?

Rāgagginā dosagginā mohagginā ādittam, jātiyā jarāya maraṇena sokehi paridevehi dukkhehi domanassehi upāyāsehi ādittanti vadāmi.

Burning with the fire of sensual desire, the fire of ill will, and the fire of confusion; burning with birth, old age, and death; burning with grief, sorrow, pain, aversion, and distress, I say.

and translations by Bhikkhu Bodhi, in Saṃyutta Nikāya 3.1 Paṭhamavagga (Shackles), Daharasutta (Young), it is said -

Pahūtabhakkham jālina',

A blazing fire that devours much,

pāvaka' kaṇhavattaniṃ;

A conflagration with blackened trail:

Daharoti nāvajāneyya,

As 'young', not realizing,

na nam paribhave naro.

A man should not disparage it.

Laddhā hi so upādānam,

For if it gains a stock of fuel,

mahā hutvāna pāvako;

Having become a conflagration,

So āsajja ḍahe bālam,

It may attack and burn the fool, *naram nāriṇca ekadā;*

Whether a man or a woman.

Tasmā tam parivajjeyya,

One should avoid it,

rakkham jīvitamattano.

guarding one's own life.

Vanam yadaggi ḍahati,

“When a fire burns down a forest -

pāvako kaṇhavattani;

That conflagration with blackened trail -

Jāyanti tattha pārōhā,

The shoots there spring to life once more

ahorattānamaccaye.

As the days and nights pass by.

Yāna kho sīlasampanno,

But if one of perfect virtue

bhikkhu ḍahati tejasā;

A bhikkhu burns one with [his virtue's] fire,

Na tassa puttā pasavo,

One does not gain sons and cattle,
dāyādā vindare dhanam;
 Nor do one's heirs acquire wealth.
Anapaccā adāyādā,
 Childless and heirless they become,
tālāvattū bhavanti te.
 Like stumps of palmyra trees.
Tasmā hi paṇḍito poso,
 "Therefore a person who is wise,
sampassam atthamattano;
 Out of regard for his own good:
Bhujāgamam pāvakañca,
 A fierce serpent and a blazing fire
khattiyāñca yasassinam;
 A famous khattiya,
Bhikkhuñca sīlasampannam,
 And a bhikkhu of perfect virtue.
sammadeva samācare"ti.
 One should always treat these properly."

3.3 Etymology of body, or related to body . . .

According to the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the online Pali dictionary at Univ. of Chicago, *these words in pali might be of immense use, while trying to grasp the exposition in section 2.3 -*

- **Indriya** F. Some compounds: -**gutta** *one who restrains & watches his senses* S i.154; Dh 375. -**gutti** *keeping watch over the senses, self - restraint* DhA iv.111.a **paropariya, b paropariyatta & c paropariyatti** (°ñāṇa) *(knowledge of) what goes on in the senses and intentions of others* a J i.78; b A v.34, 38; b Ps i.121 sq., 133 sq.; ii.158, 175; b Vbh 340, 342; c S v.205; c Nett 101. See remark under paropariya. -**bhāvanā** *cultivation of the (five, see above Cd) moral qualities* Vin i.294 (+ balabhāvanā); M iii.298. -**saṁvara** *restraint or subjugation of the senses* D ii.281; M i.269, 346; S i.54; A iii.360; iv.99; v.113 sq., 136, 206; Nd1 483; Nett 27, 121 sq; Vism 20 sq.
- **Kāyika** (adj.) [fr. kāya] 1. *belonging to the body, i. e. felt by the body (experienced by the senses), or resulting from the body, i.e. done by the body* (=acted as opposed to spoken or thought). sukhaṁ physical happiness (opp. cetasika°) S v.209; A i.81; dukkhaṁ D ii.306; M i.302 (opp. cetasikaṁ); kāyikaṁ (sc. dhammaṁ) sikkhati to teach the conduct of body (opp. vācasikaṁ) Vin ii.248. In comb. with vācasika also at S i.190; Pug 21; Vism 18 (of anācara); PvA 119 (of saṁyama, control) Shhp 55; Bdhd 26, 134; referring to diff. kinds of amusements Nd2 219=SnA 86. 2. - ° (of devas) belonging to the company of - : ° D i.220; gandhabba ° PvA 119.
- **Kāya** [der. probably fr. ci, cinoti to heap up, cp. nikāya heaping up, accumulation or collection; Sk. kāya] *group, heap, collection, aggregate, body*. - Definitions and synonyms. -

SnA 31 gives the foll. synonyms and similes of kāya: kuṭī, guhā (Sn 772), deha, sandeha (Dh 148=Th 1, 20), nāvā (Dh 369), ratha (S iv.292), dhaja, vammīka (M i.144), kuṭīkā (Th 1, 1); and at KhA 38 the foll. def.: kāye ti sarīre, sarīraṃ hi asucisañcayato kucchitānaṃ vā kesādīnaṃ āyabhūtaṃ kāyo ti vuccati . . . It is equivalent to deha: S i.27; PvA 10; to sarīra KhA 38; PvA 63, to nikāya (deva°) D iii.264; and cp. formula of jāti: sattānaṃ tamhi tamhi sattanikāye jāti . . . Nd2 257. Literal meaning.- 1. mahājana - kāya a collection of people, a crowd S iv.191; v.170; VvA 78; - bala° a great crowd Sn p. 105; DhA i.193, 398. - 2. group or division: satta kāyā akatā, etc. (seven eternal groups or principles) D i.56=M i.517=S iii.211 (in Pakudha Kaccāyana's theory); with reference to groups of sensations or sense - organs, as vedanā - kāya, saññā°, viññāṇa°, phassa°, etc. S iii.60, 61; D iii.243, 244; taṇhā° D iii.244; appl. to hatthi°, ratha°, patti°, groups of elephants, carriages or soldiers S i.72. - A good idea of the extensive meaning of kāya may be gathered from the classification of the 7 kāyas at J ii.91, viz. camma°, dāru°, loha°, ayo°, vāluka°, udaka°, phalaka°, or "bodies" (great masses, substances) of skin, wood, copper, iron, sand, water, and planks. - Var. other combns: Asura° A i.143; D iii.7; Ābhassara° ("world of radiance") D i.17=iii.29, 84; Deva° S i.27, 30; D iii.264 (°nikāya); dibbā kāyā A i.143; Tāvatiṃsa° D iii.15. Applied meaning. - I. Kāya under the physical aspect is an aggregate of a multiplicity of elements which finally can be reduced to the four "great" elements, viz. earth, water, fire, and air (D i.55). This "heap," in the valuation of the Wise (muni), shares with all other objects the qualities of such elements, and is therefore regarded as contemptible, as something which one has to get rid of, as a source of impurity. It is subject to time and change, it is built up and kept alive by cravings, and with death it is disintegrated into the elements. But the kamma which determined the appearance of this physical body has naturally been renewed and assumes a new form. II. Kāya under the psychological aspect is the seat of sensation (Dhs §§613-16), and represents the fundamental organ of touch which underlies all other sensation. Developed only in later thought DhsA. 311 cf. Mrs. Rhys Davids, Bud. Psy. Ethics lvi. ff.; Bud. Psy. 143, 185 f. I. (Physical). - (a) Understanding of the body is attained through introspection (sati). In the group of the four sati - paṭṭhānas, the foundations of introspection, the recognition of the true character of "body" comes first (see Vbh 193). The standing formula of this recognition is kāye kāyānupassī . . . contemplating body as an accumulation, on which follows the description of this aggregate: "he sees that the body is clothed in skin, full of all kinds of dirty matter, and that in this body there are hair, nails, teeth," etc. (the enumeration of the 32 ākāras, as given Kh iii.). The conclusions drawn from this meditation give a man the right attitude. The formula occurs frequently, both in full and abridged, e. g. D ii.293, 294; iii.104, 141; A iii.323=v.109; S iv.111=v.278; Vbh 193, 194; Nett 83, 123; with slight variation: kāye asubhānupassī... A iii.142 sq.; v.109 (under asubhasaññā); It 81; cp. kāye aniccānupassī S iv.211; and kāyagatā sati. - This accumulation is described in another formula with: ayaṃ... kāyo rūpī cātum(m)ahābhūtika mātā - pettika - sambhavo odana - kummās' upacayo, etc. "this body has form (i. e. is material, visible), is born from mother and father, is a heap of gruel and sour milk, is subject to constant dressing and tending, to breaking up and decay," etc., with inferences D i.55=S iii.207; S ii.94; iv.194; v.282, 370; D i.76, 209; M i.144, 500; ii.17; A iv.386=S iv.83. (b) Various qualities and functions of the material body. As trunk of the body (opposed to pakkhā and sīsa) S ii.231; also at Pv i.83; as depending on nourishment (āhāra - tṭhitika, etc.) Sv.64; A ii.145 (with taṇhā, māna, methuna); as needing attention: see °parihārika. As saviññāṇaka, having consciousness A iv.53= S ii.252=S iii.80,

103, 136, 169; cp. āyu usmā ca viññānaṃ yadā kāyaṃ jahant' imaṃ S iii.143. As in need of breathing assāsa - passāsa S v.330, 336; as tired, fatigued (kilanta - kāya) kilanta - kāyā kilanta - cittā te devā tamhā kāyā cavanti "tired in body, tired in mind these gods fall out of this assembly" (D i.20; iii.32≈); in other connection PvA 43; see also kilanta. kāyo kilanto D iii.255 sq.;=A iv.332; S v.317; M i.116; jñāssa me . . . kāyo na paleti Sn 1144; ātura - kāyo S iii.1 (cittam anāturaṃ); paripuṇṇa - k° suruci sujāto, etc., with a perfect body (of the Buddha) Sn 548= Th 1, 818; cp. mahā - k° (of Brahmins) Sn 298. The body of a Buddha is said to be endowed with the 32 signs of a great man: Bhagavato kāye dvattimsa mahāpurisa - lakkhaṇāni . . . Sn p. 107, cp. 549. The Tathāgata is said to be dhamma - kāyo "author and speaker of Doctrine," in the same sense Brahma - kāyo "the best body" (i. e. of Doctrine) D iii.84 (Dial. iii, 81). (c) Valuation of physical body. From the contemplating of its true character (kāyānupassī) follows its estimation as a transient, decaying, and repulsive object. - kāye anicc' ānu- passī S iv.211 (and vay' ānupassī, nirodh' ānupassī), so also asubhānupassī It 81; kāyaṃ ca bhindantaṃ ñatvā It 69; evaṃdhammo (i. e. a heap of changing elements) A iii.324; aciraṃ vat' ayaṃ kāyo paṭhavim adhisessati chuddho apeta viññāṇo niratthaṃ va kalingaraṃ Dh 41. pittaṃ semhaṃ ca vamaṃ kāyamhā Sn 198. As bahu - dukkha bahuādīnavo A v.109; as anicca dukkha, etc. M i.500; ii.17; kāyena aṭṭiyamānā harayamānā S iv.62; v.320; dissati imassa kāyassa ācayo pi apacayo pi ādānam pi nikkhepanam pi S ii.94. - This body is eaten by crows and vultures after its death: S v.370. Represented as pūti° foul S i.131; iii.120. - Bdgh. at Vism 240 defines kāya as "catu - mahābhūtika pūti - kāya" (cp. similar passages on p. 367: patthaddho bhavati kāyo, pūtika bhavati kāyo). (d) Similes. - Out of the great number of epithets (adhivacanāni) and comparisons only a few can be mentioned (cp. above under def. & syn.): The body is compared to an abscess (gaṇḍa) S iv.83=A iv.386; a city (nagara) S iv.194; a cart (ratha) S iv.292; an anthill (vammīka) M i.144; all in ref- erence to its consisting of the four fundamental elements, cp. also: pheṇ' ūpamaṃ kāyaṃ imaṃ viditvā "knowing that the body is like froth" Dh 46; kumbh' ūpamaṃ kāyaṃ imaṃ viditvā nagar' ū pamaṃ cittaṃ idaṃ tṭapetvā Dh 40: the body is as fragile as a water - pot. (e) Dissolution of the body is expressed in the standard phrase: kāyassa bhedaṃ paraṃ maraṇā . . . , i. e. after death... upon which usually follows the mention of one of the gatis, the destinies which the new kāya has to experience, e. g. D i.82, 107, 143, 162, 245, 247, 252; iii.96, 97, 146, 181, 235; M i.22; S i.94; iii.241; Dh 140; It 12, 14; J i.152; PvA 27, etc., etc. Cp. also iv. II. (Psychological). - As the seat of feeling, kāya is the fifth in the enumeration of the senses (āyatanāni). It is ajjhattika as sense (i. e. subjective) and its object is the tan- gible (phoṭṭhabba). The contact between subject and object consists either in touching (phusitvā) or in sensing (viññeyya). The formulas vary, but are in essence the same all through, e. g. kāya - viññeyyā phoṭṭhabbā D i.245; kāyena phoṭṭhab- baṃ phusitvā D iii.226, 250, 269; M i.33; ii.42; S iv.104, 112; kāyena phusitvā A v.11; kāyo c' eva phoṭṭhabbā ca D iii.102. Best to be grouped here is an application of kāya in the sense of the self as experiencing a great joy; the whole being, the "inner sense," or heart. This realization of intense happiness (such as it is while it lasts), pīti - sukha, is the result of the four stages of meditation, and as such it is always mentioned after the jhānas in the formula: so imaṃ eva kāyaṃ vivekajena pīti - sukkena abhisandeti . . . "His very body does he so pervade with the joy and ease born of detachment from worldliness" D i.73 sq.=M i.277; A ii.41, etc. - A similar context is that in which kāya is represented as passaddha, calmed down, i. e. in a state which is free from worldly attachment (vivekaja). This "peace" of the body (may be translated as "my senses, my spirits" in this connection)

flows out of the peace of the mind and this is born out of the joy accompanying complete satisfaction (pamuditā) in attaining the desired end. The formula is pamuditassa pīti jāyati pītimanassa kāyo passambhati, passad-dhakāyo sukhaṃ vedeti, sukhino cittaṃ samādhiyati D iii.241, 288; S iv.351; M i.37; A iii.21, 285; iv.176; v.3, 333; Vbh 227. - Similarly: pamuditāya pīti jāyati, pītimanāya kāyo p°, pas-sadhakāyā sukhaṃ ved° Vin i.294 (cp. Vin. Texts ii.224: "all my frame will be at peace," or "individuality"; see note) passaddhakāya - sankhāra mentioned at A v.29 sq. is one of the ten ariya - vāsā, the noblest conditions. A quasi - analogy between kāya and kāma is apparent from a number of other passages: kāya - chando - °sneho - °anvayatā pahīyati M i.500; ajjhatañ ca bahiddha ca kāye chandaṃ virājaye Sn 203; kāye avigata - rāgo hoti (kāme, rūpe) D iii.238=A iii.249; madhurakajāto viya kāyo S iii.106; A iii.69. III. (Ethical). - Kāya is one of the three channels by which a man's personality is connected with his environment & by which his character is judged, viz. action, the three being kāya, vacī (vāca) and manas. These three kammantas, activities or agents, form the three subdivisions of the sīla, the rules of conduct. Kāya is the first and most conspicuous agent, or the principle of action κ α' τ ε ζ ο Ξ η ν, character in its pregnant sense. Kāya as one of a triad. - Its usual combination is in the formula mentioned, and as such found in the whole of the Pāli Canon. But there is also another combination, found only in the older texts, viz. kayenā vācāya uda cetasā: yañ ca karoti kāyena vācāya uda cetasā tañ hi tassa sakam hoti tañ ca ādāya gacchati S i.93 yo dhammacārī kāyena vācāya uda cetasā idh eva nam pasamsanti pacca sagge pamodati S i.102. - So also at A i.63; Sn 232. Besides in formula arakkhitena kāyena a° vācāya a° cittena S ii.231=271; iv.112. - With su- and ducarita the combn is extremely frequent, e. g. S i.71, 72; M i.22, etc., etc. In other comb. we have kāya - (v°, m°) kamma, moneyya, soceyya, etc. - k°. v°. m°. hiṃsati S i.165; saṃsappati A v.289 sq.; kāye (v°. m°) sati kāya - sañcetanā - hetu uppajjati S ii.39 sq.; The variations of k - in the ethics of the Dhamma under this view of k°. v°. m°. are manifold, all based on the fundamental distinctions between good and bad, all being the raison d'être of kamma: yañ . . . etarahi kammaṃ karoti kāyena v. m. idaṃ vuccati navakammaṃ S iv.132. - Passages with reference to good works are e. g. D iii.245; A i.151; v.302 sq.; (see also Kamma ii.2 b. c.). - With reference to evil: S iii.241, 247; A i.201; kin nu kāyena vācāya manasā dukkaṭaṃ kataṃ Pv ii.13 and passim. Assutavā puthujjano tīhi ṭhānehi micchā paṭipajjati kāyena v. m. S ii.151; pāpaṃ na kayirā vacasā manasā kāyena vā kiñcana sabbaloke S i.12=31; yassa kāyena vācāya manasā n'atthi dukkaṭaṃ samvutaṃ tīhi ṭhānehi, tam ahaṃ brūmi brāhmaṇaṃ Dh 391=Nett 183. Kāyena saṃvaro sādhu sādhu vācāya saṃvaro manasā saṃvaro sādhu sādhu sabbattha saṃvaro Dh 361=S i.73= Miln 399; ye ca kāyena v. m. ca susaṃvutā na te Māravasānugā, na te Mārassa paccagū S i.104; vācānurakkhī manasā susaṃvuto kāyena ca akusalaṃ na kayirā Dh 281=Nett 183. Kāya as one of a dyad: vācā and kāya: S i.172 (°gutta) M i.461 (rakkhita and a°); Pv i.22 (°saññatā and opp.); Vism 28 (k° - vacī - kamma); PvA 98. Kāya alone as a collective expression for the three: A i.54; Dh 259, 391; Sn 206, 407; kāye avitarāgo M i.101; A iii.249; iv.461 sq.; ° - samācāra S v.354; kāyaṃ pañidhāya Ps i.175; Vbh 244=252; bhāvita° and a° M i.239; A i.250; iii.106 sq., cp.: kāya-ppakopaṃ rakkheyya, kāyena saṃvuto siyā kāyaduccharitaṃ hitvā, kāyena sucaritaṃ care Dh 231. Ahimsakā ye munayo niccaṃ kāyena saṃvutā Dh 225. Kāya in combn with citta: ṭhito va kāyo hoti ṭhitaṃ cittaṃ . . . S v.74; anikaṭṭha - kāyo nikaṭṭha - citto A ii.137; sāraddha - kāyo sankiliṭṭha - citto A v.93=95= 97; bhāvita - kāyo, °sīlo, °citto, °pañño S iv.111; A iv.111; v.42 sq. Apakassa kāyaṃ apakassa cittaṃ S ii.198. Kāya - citta - passaddhi, etc. Dhs §§29 - 51. In these six

couples (or yu- galas) later Abhidhamma distinguished kāya as=the cetasikas (mental properties, or the vedanā, saññā and sankhārā khandhas), body being excluded. Cpd. 96. See also combn kilantakāya, kilanta - citta under kilamati. IV. (Various). - Kāyena (i. e. "visibly") aññamaññam passitum A ii.61; as nānatta° and ekatta° at A iv.39 =Nd2 570. The relation between rūpa - kāya (=cātumahābhūtika), and nāma - kāya, the mental compound (=vedanā saññā, etc.) is discussed at Nett 77, 78, and Ps i.183 sq., see also S ii.24. K. is anattā, i. e. k. has no soul A v.109; S iv.166. n'āyaṃ kāyo tumhākaṃ n'āpi paresaṃ, purāṇaṃ idaṃ kammaṃ . . . "neither is this body yours, nor anyone else's: it is (the appearance of) former karma" S ii.64, 65=Nd2 680. Dissamānena kāyena and upaḍḍha - dissamānena S i.156. - Manomaya - kāya a body made by the mind (cp. VvA 10 and DA i.110, 120, 222) according to Bdgh only at the time of jhāna S v.282 sq.; manomaya pīti - bhakkha sayarūpabha D i.17=VvA 10; manomayaṃ kāyaṃ abhinimmināya... D i.77; m°sabbanga - paccangī D i.34, 77, 186, 195. - Under the control of psychic powers (iddhi): kāyena va saṃvatteti he does as he likes with his body, i. e. he walks on water, is ubiquitous, etc. (yāva brahmalokā pi: even up to heaven) S v.265= D i.78=A i.170: see also S v.283, 284. - In the various stages of Saṃsāra; kāyānikkhipati he lays down his (old) body S iv.60, 400; cp. S iii.241 (ossatṭha - kāya); referring to continuous change of body during day and night (of a Petī) Pv ii.1211 . - **kammaññatā** *wildness, alertness of the bodily senses included under nāmakāya* Dhs 46, 277, 326. - **passaddhi** *serenity or quietude of the senses* S iv.125 (cp. iv.351 and above); v.66, 104; Dhs 40, 277, 320; DhsA 130; Bdhd 16, 19, 29; - **dvāra** *the channel or out-let of bodily senses* J i.276; iv.14; VvA 73; DhA iv.85; Bdhd 69;

- **Indriya** (nt.) [Vedic indriya adj. only in meaning "belonging to Indra"; nt. strength, might (cp. inda), but in specific pāli sense "belonging to the ruler", i. e. governing, ruling nt. governing, ruling or controlling principle] A. On term: Indriya is one of the most comprehensive & important categories of Buddhist psychological philosophy & ethics, meaning "*controlling principle, directive force*, élan, δ ú v α μ ι ζ", *in the foll. applications: (a) with reference to sense - perceptibility "faculty, function", often wrongly interpreted as "organ"; (b) w. ref. to objective aspects of form and matter "kind, characteristic, determining principle, sign, mark" (cp. woman - hood, hood = Goth. haidus "kind, form"); (c) w. ref. to moods of sensation and (d) to moral powers or motives controlling action, "principle, controlling" force; (e) w. ref. to cognition & insight "category"*. - Definitions of indriya among others at DhsA 119; cp. Expositor 157; Dhs trsl. lvii; Cpd. 228, 229. B. *Classifications and groups of indriyāni. An exhaustive list comprises the indriyāni enumd under A a - e, thus establishing a canonical scheme of 22 Controlling Powers (bāvīsati indriyāni)*, running thus at Vbh 122 sq. (see trsl. at Cpd. 175, 176); and discussed in detail at Vism 491 sq. (a. *sensorial*) (1) *cakkh - undriya* ("the eye which is a power", Cpd. 228) *the eye or (personal potentiality of) vision*, (2) *sot - indriya* *the ear or hearing*, (3) *ghān°* *nose or smell*, (4) *jivh°* *tongue or taste*, (5) *kāy°* *body - sensibility*, (6) *man°* *mind*; (b. *material*) (7) *ithh°* *female sex or femininity*, (8) *puris°* *male sex or masculinity*, (9) *jīvit°* *life or vitality*; (c. *sensational*) (10) *sukh°* *pleasure*, (11) *dukkh°* *pain*, (12) *somanasa°* *joy*, (13) *domanass°* *grief*, (14) *upekh°* *hedonic indifference* (d. *moral*) (15) *saddh°* *faith*, (16) *viriy°* *energy*, (17) *sat°* *mindfulness*, (18) *samādh°* *concentration*, (19) *paññ°* *reason*; (e. *cognitional*) (20) *anaññāta-ñāssāmīt°* *the thought "I shall come to know the unknown"*, (21) *aññ°* (= *aññā*) *gnosis*, (22) *aññātā - v°* *one who knows*. - *Jīvitindriya* (no. 9) is in some redactions placed before *ithh°* (no. 7), e. g. at Ps i.7, 137. - From this list are de-

tached several groups, mentioned frequently and in various connections, no. 6 manas (mano, man - indriya) wavering in its function, being either included under (a) or (more frequently) omitted, so that the first set (a) is marked off as pañc' indriyāni, the 6th being silently included (see below). This uncertainty regarding manas deserves to be noted. The foll. groups may be mentioned here viz 19 (nos. 1 - 19) at Ps i.137; 10 (pañca rūpīni & pañca arūpīni) at Nett 69; three groups of five (nos. 1 - 5, 10 - 14, 15 - 19) at D iii.239, cp. 278; four (group d without paññā, i. e. nos. 15 - 18) at A ii.141; three (saddh°, samādh°, paññ°, i. e. nos. 15, 18, 19) at A i. 118 sq. Under atthavidham indriya - rūpaṃ (Cpd. 159) or rūpaṃ as indriyaṃ "form which is faculty" Dhs 661 (cp. trsl. p. 204) are understood the 5 sensitives (nos. 1 - 5), the 2 séx - states (nos. 7, 8) and the vital force (no. 9), i. e. groups a & b of enumn.; discussed & defined in detail at Dhs 709 - 717, 971 - 973. - It is often to be guessed from the context only, which of the sets of 5 indriyāni (usually either group a or d) is meant. These detached groups are classed as below under C. f. - Note. This system of 22 indriyāni reflects a revised & more elaborate form of the 25 (or 23) categories of the Sāṅkhya philosophy, with its 10 elements, 10 indri, īni & the isolated position of manas. C. Material in detail (grouped according to A a - e) (a) sensorial: (mentioned or referred to as set of 5 viz B. nos. 1 - 5): M i.295; S iii.46 (pañcannam °ānam avakanti), 225; iv.168; A ii.151 (as set of 6, viz. B. nos. 1 - 6): M i.9; S iv.176; v.74, 205, 230; A i.113; ii.16, 39, 152; iii.99, 163, 387 sq.; v.348. Specially referring to restraint & control of the senses in foll. phrases: in driyāni saṃvutāni S ii.231, 271; iv.112; pañcasu °esu saṃvuto Sn 340 (= lakkhaṇato pana chattham pi vuttam yeva hoti, i. e. the 6th as manas included, SnA 343); °esu susaṃvuta Th 2, 196 (= mana - chatthesu i° sutthu saṃvutā ThA 168) indriyesu guttadvāra & guttadvārātā D iii.107; S ii.218; iv.103, 112, 175; A i.25, 94, 113; ii.39; iii.70, 138, 173, 199, 449 sq.; iv.25, 166; v.134; It 23, 24; Nd1 14; Vbh 248, 360; DA i.182 (= manachattesu indriyesu pihita - dvāro hoti), i. vipasannāni S ii. 275; iii.2, 235; iv.294; v.301; A i.181; iii.380. °ānam samatā (v. l. samatha) A iii.375 sq. (see also f. below) °āni bhāvitāni Sn 516 (= cakkh' ādāni cha i. SnA 426); Nd2 475 B8. - Various: S i.26 (rakkhati), 48 (°ūpasame rato); iv.40, 140 (°samppanna); v.216, 217 sq. (independent in function, mano as referee); Ps. i.190 (man°); Vbh 13 (rūpa), 341 (mud° & tikkh°) 384 (ahīn°). - (b) physical: (above B 7 - 9) all three: S v.204; Vism 447; itthi° & purisa° A iv.57; Vbh 122, 415 sq.; puris° A iii.404; jīvit° Vbh 123, 137; Vism 230 (°upaccheda = maraṇa). See also under itthi, jīvita & purisa. - (c) sensational (above B 10 - 14): S v.207 sq. (see Cpd. 111 & cp. p. 15), 211 sq.; Vbh 15, 71; Nett 88. - (d) moral (above B 15- 19): S iii.96, 153; iv.36, 365 sq.; v.193 sq., 202, 219 (corresponding to pañcabalāni), 220 sq. (and amata), 223 sq. (their culture brings assurance of no rebirth), 227 sq. (paññā the chief one), 235, 237 (sevenfold fruit of), A iv.125 sq., 203, 225; v.56, 175; Ps ii.49, 51 sq., 86; Nd1 14; Nd2 628 (sat° + satibala); Kvu 589; Vbh 341; Nett 15, 28, 47, 54. Often in standard combn. with satipatthāna, sammappadhāna. iddhipāda, indriya, bala, bojjhanga, magga (see Nd2 s. v. p. 263) D ii.120; Vin iii. 93, Ps ii.166 & passim. As set of 4 indriyāni (nos. 16- 19) at Nett 83. - (e) cognitional (above B 20 - 22) D iii.219 = S v.204 (as peculiar to Arahantship); It 53; Ps i.115; ii.30. - (f) collectively, either two or more of groups a - e, also var. peculiar uses: personal; esp. physical faculties. S i.61 (pākat°), 204 (id.); iii.207 (ākāsam °āni sankamanti); iv.294 (vipari - bhinnāni); A iii.441 (°ānam avekallatā). magic power A iv.264 sq. (okkhipati °āni). indriyānam paripāko (moral or physical) over - ripeness of faculties S ii.2, 42; A v.203; Nd2 252 (in def. of jarā); Vbh 137. moral forces Vin i.183 (°ānam samatā, + viriyānam s. as sign of Arahant); ii.240 (pañc°). principle of life ekindriyaṃ jīvaṃ Vin iii.156; Miln 259.

heart or seat of feeling in phrase °āni paricāreti to satisfy one's heart PvA 16, 58, 77. obligation, duty, vow in phrase °āni bhinditvā breaking one's vow J ii.274; iv.190. D. Unclassified material D i 77 (ahīn°); iii 239 (domanass° & somanass°) M i.437 (vemattatā), 453 (id.); ii. 11, 106; iii.296; S iii.225; v.209 (dukkh°, domanass°); A i.39, 42 sq., 297; ii.38 (sant°), 149 sq.; iii.277, 282; Ps i.16, 21, 88, 180; ii.1 sq, 13, 84, 119, 132, 143, 145, 110, 223; Nd1 45 (°dhīra), 171 (°kusala), 341 (pucchā); Dhs 58, 121, 528, 556 (dukkh°), 560, 644. 736; Nett 18 (sotāpannessa), 28 (°vavatthāna), 162 (lok'uttara); Vism 350 (°vekallatā); Sdhp 280, 342, 364, 371, 449, 473. E. As adj. (-°) having one's senses, mind or heart as such & such S i.138 (tikkh° & mud°); iii.93 (pākat°); v.269 (id.); A i.70 (id) & passim (id.); A i.70 (samvut°) 266 (id.), 236 (gutt°); ii.6 (samāhit°); 8n 214 (susamāhit° his senses well - composed); PvA 70 (pīnit° joyful or gladdened of heart).

- **Dvāra** (nt.) [Ved. dvār (f.) & dvāra (nt.), base *dhvār, cp. Av. dvarGm; Gr. χ'υρ' α, χ u ρ' ω v; Lat. fores (gate), forum; Goth. daúr, Ohg. turi=Ger. tür, Ags. dor=E. door.] 1. lit. *an outer door, a gate, entrance* Vin i.15; S i.58, 138, 211; J i.346; ii.63; vi.330; Vbh 71 sq.; PvA 4, 67 (village gate), 79; Sdhp 54, 356. -That d. cannot be used for an inner door see Vin ii.215; on knocking at a d. see DA i.252; cp. DhA i.145 (dvāraṃ ākoṭeti); to open a door: āvarati; to shut: pidahati; to lock: thaketi. dvāraṃ alabhamāna unable to get out Vin ii.220. - *mahā° the main or city gate* J i.63; culla° J ii.114; catu° (adj.) having 4 doors (of niraya) Pv i.1013; *cha° with 6d. (nagaraṃ, w. ref. to the 6 doors of the senses, see below)* S iv.194; pure° the front d. J ii.153; pacchima° the back d. J vi.364; uttara° the E. gate (PvA 74); nagara° the city gate (J i.263; deva° DhA i.280); gāma° the village g. (Vin iii.52; J ii.110); ghara° (J iv.142; PvA 38) & geha° (PvA 61) the house door; antepura° the door of the inner chamber M ii.100; kula° the doors of the clan - people Sn 288. - metaph. of the door leading to Nibbāna: amata° S i.137; A v.346. - 2. (fig.) the doors=in - & *outlets of the mind, viz. the sense organs; in phrase indriyesu gutta-dvāra (adj.) guarding the doors with respect to the senses or faculties (of the mind):* see gutta (e. g. S ii.218; iv.103 & cp. Dhs. trsl. p. 175). - S iv.117, 194 (with simile of the 6 gates of a city); VvA 72 (kāya - vacī°). The nine gates of the body at Vism 346. Thus also in f. ab-str. *guttadvāratā the condition of well protected doors (see gutta).*
- **Dvārika** (-°) (adj.) *referring or belonging to the door of -; in cha °ā taṅhā, craving or fever, arising through the 6 doors (of the senses)* DhA iv.221, & *kāya° - samvara control over the "bodily" door, i. e. over action* (opp. speech) PvA 10 (so read for kāyañ cārika°).

3.4 Etymology of enjoyment and pleasures of senses . . .

According to the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the online Pali dictionary at Univ. of Chicago, *these words in pali might be of immense use, while trying to grasp the exposition in section 2.3 -*

- **Itṭha** (adj.) [pp. of icchati] pleasing, welcome, agreeable, pleasant, often in the idiomatic group *itṭha kanta manāpa (of objects pleasing to the senses)* D i.245; ii.192; M i.85; S iv.60, 158, 235 sq.; v.22, 60, 147; A ii.66 sq.; v.135 (dasa, dhammā etc., ten objects affording pleasure); Sn 759; It. 15; Vbh 2, 100, 337. - Alone as nt. meaning welfare, good state, pleasure, happiness at Sn 154 (+ anitṭha); Nett 28 (+ anitṭha); Vism 167 (id.); PvA 116 (=

bhadram), 140. -aniṭṭha unpleasant, disagreeable PvA 32, 52, 60, 116. - See also pariy°, in which iṭṭha stands for eṭṭha.

- **Kāma** (m. nt.) [Dhtp (603) & Dhtm (843) paraphrase by "icchāyam," cp. Vedic kāma, kam=Idg. *qā] to desire, cp. Lat. carus, Goth. hōrs, E whore. - 1. *Objective: pleasantness, pleasure - giving, an object of sensual enjoyment*; - 2. *subjective: (a) enjoyment, pleasure on occasion of sense, (b) sense - desire*. Buddhist commentators express 1 and 2 by kāmīyatī ti kāmo, and kameti ti kāmo Cpd. 81, n. 2. Kāma as sense - desire and enjoyment plus objects of the same is a collective name for all but the very higher or refined conditions of life. The *kāma - bhava or - loka (worlds of sensed desire) includes 4 of the 5 modes (gati's) of existence and part of the fifth or deva - loka*. See Bhava. The term is not found analyzed till the later books of the Canon are consulted, thus, Nd¹ 1 distinguishes (1) *vatthukāmā: desires relating to a base, i. e. physical organ or external object*, and (2) *kilesakāmā: desire considered subjectively*. So also Nd² 202, quoted DhA ii.162; iii.240; and very often as *ubho kāmā. A more logical definition is given by Dhammapāla on Vv 11 (VvA 11). He classifies as follows: 1. manāpiyā rūpādi - visayā. - 2. chandarāga. - 3. sabbasmim lobha. - 4. gāmadhamma. - 5. hitacchanda. - 6. seribhāva, i. e. k. concerned with (1) pleasant objects, (2) impulsive desire, (3) greed for anything, (4) sexual lust, (5) effort to do good, (6) self - determination. In all enumerations of obstacles to perfection, or of general divisions and definitions of mental conditions, kāma occupies the leading position. It is the first of the five obstacles (nī-varañāni), the three esanās (longings), the four upādānas (attachments), the four oghas (floods of worldly turbulence), the four āsavas (intoxicants of mind), the three taṇhās, the four yogas; and k. stands first on the list of the six factors of existence: kāmā, vedanā, saññā, āsavā, kamma, dukkha, which are discussed at A iii.410 sq. as regards their origin, difference, consequences, destruction and remedy. - Kāma is most frequently connected with rāga (passion), with chanda (impulse) and gedha (greed), all expressing the active, clinging, and impulsive character of desire. - The foll. is the list of synonyms given at various places for kāma - cchanda: (1) chanda, impulse; (2) rāga, excitement; (3) nandī, enjoyment; (4) taṇhā, thirst; (5) sineha, love; (6) pipāsā, thirst; (7) pariḷāha, consuming passion; (8) gedha, greed; (9) mucchā, swoon, or confused state of mind; (10) ajjhosāna, hanging on, or attachment Nd¹. At Nd2 200; Dhs 1097 (omitting No. 8), cp. DhsA 370; similarly at Vism 569 (omitting Nos. 6 and 8), cp. Dhs 1214; Vbh 375. This set of 10 characteristics is followed by kām - ogha, kāma - yoga, kām - upādāna at Nd2 200, cp. Vism 141 (kām - ogha, °āsava, °upādāna). Similarly at D iii.238: kāme avigata - rāga, °chanda, °pema, °pipāsā, °pariḷāha, °taṇha. See also kāma - chanda below under cpds. In connection with synonyms it may be noticed that most of the verbs used in a kāma - context are verbs the primary meaning of which is "adhering to" or "grasping," hence, attachment; viz. esanā (iṣ to Lat ira), upādāna (upa + ā + dā taking up), taṇhā (tṛṣ, Lat. torreo=thirst) pipāsā (the wish to drink), sineha (snih, Lat. nix=melting), etc. - On the other hand, the reaction of the passions on the subject is expressed by khajjati "to be eaten up" pariḍayhati "to be burnt," etc. The foll. passage also illustrates the various synonymic expressions: kāme paribhuñjati, kāmamajjhe vasati, kāma - pariḷāhena pariḍayhati, kāmavitakkehi khajjati, kāma - pariyesanāyā ussukko, A i.68; cp. M i.463; iii.129. Under this aspect kāma is essentially an evil, but to the popular view it is one of the indispensable attributes of bliss and happiness to be enjoyed as a reward of virtue in this world (mānussakāmā) as well as in the next (dibbā kāmā). See kāmāvacara about the various stages of next - world happiness.*

Numerous examples are to be found in Pv and Vv, where a standing Ep. of the Blest is *sab-bakā- masamiddha* "fully equipped with all objects of pleasure," e. g. Pv i.105; PvA 46. The other - world pleasures are greater than the earthly ones: S v.409; but to the Wise even these are unsatisfactory, since they still are signs of, and lead to, rebirth (*kāmûpapatti*, It (4): *api dibbesu kāmesu ratim so nâdhigacchati Dh 187; rāgam vinayetha mānusesu dibbesu kāmesu cāpi bhikkhu Sn 361, see also It 94. - Kāma as sensual pleasure finds its most marked application in the sphere of the sexual: kāmesu micchācārin, transgressing in lusts, sinning in the lusts of the flesh, or violating the third rule of conduct equivalent to abrahmacariyā, in chastity (see sīla) Pug 38, 39; It 63, etc. itthi - kāmehi paricāreti "he enjoys himself with the charms of woman" S iv.343. Kāmesu brahmacariyavā practising chastity Sn 1041. Kāmatthā for sexual amusement A iii.229. Redemption from kāma is to be effected by selfcontrol (samyama) and meditation (jhāna), by knowledge, right effort and renunciation. "To give up passion" as a practice of him who wishes to enter on the Path is expressed by: kāmānaṃ pahānaṃ, kāmasaññānaṃ pariññā, kāma - pipāsānaṃ - paṭivinayo, kāmavitakkānaṃ samugghāto kāma - pariḷāhānaṃ vūpasamo Vin iii.111; - kāmesu (ca) appaṭibaddhacitto "uddhaṃsoto" ti vuc-cati: *he whose mind is not in the bonds of desire is called "one who is above the stream"* Dh 218; cp. Th 2, 12; - tasmā jantu sadā sato kāmāni parivajjaye Sn 771; - yo kāme parivajjeti Sn 768=Nett 69. - nikkhamma gharā panujja kāme Sn 359; - ye ca kāme pariññāya caranti akutob- hayā te ve pāragatā loke ye pattā āsavakkhayaṃ A iii.69. - Kāmānaṃ pariññānaṃ paññāpeti Gotamo M i.84; cp. A v.64; kāme pajahati: S i.12=31; Sn 704; kāmānaṃ vip-pahāna S i.47; - ye kāme hitvā aghā caranti Sn 464; - kāmā nirujjhanti (through jhāna) A iv.410; kāme panudati Dh 383=S i.15 (context broken), cp. kāmasukhaṃ analaṃkaritvā Sn 59; - kāmesu anapekkhin Sn 166=Ś i.16 (abbrev.); S ii.281; Sn 857; - cp. rāgam vinayetha . . . Sn 361. *vivicc' eva kāmehi, aloof from sensuous joys is the prescription for all Jhāna - exercise. Applications of these expressions:* - kāmesu palāḷita A iii.5; kāmesu mucchita S i.74; kāmālaye asatta S i.33; kāmesu kathaṃ nameyya S i.117; kāmesu anikīḷitāvin S i.9 (cp. kela); kittassa munino carato kāmesu anapekkhino oghatiṇṇassa pihayanti kāmesu gathitā pajā Sn 823 (gadhitā Nd1); - kāmesu asaññata Sn 243; - yo na lippati kāmesu tam ahaṃ brūmi brāhmaṇaṃ Dh 401; - Muni santivādo agiddho kāme ca loke ca anūpalitto Sn 845; kāmesu giddha D iii.107; Sn 774; kāmesu gedhaṃ āpajjati S i.73; - na so rajjati kāmesu Sn 161; - kāmānaṃ vasam upāgamum Sn 315 (=kāmānaṃ āsattataṃ pāpunimsu SnA 325); kāme parivajjeti Sn 768, kāme anugijjhati Sn 769. Character of Kāmā. The pleasures of the senses are evanescent, transient (*sabbe kāmā aniccā, etc. A ii.177*), and of no real taste (*appāsādā*); they do not give permanent satisfaction; the happiness which they yield is only a deception, or a dream, from which the dreamer awakens with sorrow and regret. Therefore the Buddha says "Even though the pleasure is great, the regret is greater: *ādīnavo ettha bhīyyo*" (see k - sukha). Thus *kāmā as kālikā (needing time) S i.9, 117; aniccā (transitory) S i.22; kāmā citrā madhurā "pleasures are manifold and sweet" (i. e. tasty) Sn 50*; but also *appāsādā bahudukkhā bahupāyāsā: quot. M i.91; see Nd2 71. Another passage with var. descriptions and comparisons of kāma, beginning with app' assādā dukkhā kāmā is found at J iv.118. - atittam yeva kāmesu antako kurute vasaṃ Dh 48; - na kahāpaṇavassena titti kāmesu vijjati appāsādā dukkhā kāmā iti viññāya paṇḍito "not for showers of coins is satisfaction to be found in pleasures - of no taste and full of misery are pleasures: thus say the wise and they understand" Dh 186; cp. M i.130; Vin ii.25 (cp. Divy 224). - Kāmato jāyatī soko kāmato jāyatī bhayaṃ kāmato vippamuttassa n'atthi soko kuto bhayan ti "of pleasure is born sorrow,**

of pleasure is born fear” Dh 215. - *Kāmānam adhvācanāni, attributes of kāma are: bhaya, dukkha, roga, gaṇḍa, salla, sanga, panka, gabbha* A iv.289; Nd2 p. 62 on Sn 51; same, except salla & gabbha: A iii.310. *The misery of such pleasures is painted in vivid colours in the Buddha’s discourse on pains of pleasures* M i.85 and parallel passages (see e. g. Nd2 199), *how kāma is the cause of ego-ism, avarice, quarrels between kings, nations, families, how it leads to warfare, murder, lasciviousness, torture and madness. Kāmānam ādīnavo (the danger of passions)* M i.85 sq. =Nd2 199, quot. SnA 114 (on Sn 61); *as one of the five anupubbikathās*: K° ādīnavam okāram samkilesam A iv.186, 209, 439; - they are the leaders in the army of Māra: kāmā te paṭhamā senā Sn 436; - yo evamvādī . . . n’atthi kāmesu doso ti so kāmesu pātavyatam āpajjati A i.266=M i.305 sq. Similes. - In the foll. passage (following on appassādā bahudukkhā, etc.) the *pleasures of the senses are likened to: (1) atṭhi - kankhala, a chain of bones; - (2) māmsapesi, a piece of (decaying) flesh; - (3) tiṇ’ukkā, a torch of grass; (4) angāra - kāsu, a pit of glowing cinders; - (5) supina, a dream; (6) yācita, beggings; - (7) rukkhā - phala, the fruit of a tree; - (8) asisūna, a slaughter - house; - (9) satti - sūla, a sharp stake; - (10) sappā - sira, a snake’s head, i. e. the bite of a snake at Vin ii.25; M i.130; A iii.97 (where atṭhisankhala); Nd2 71 (leaving out No. 10).* Out of this list are taken single quotations of No. 4 at D iii.283; A iv.224=v.175; No. 5 at DhA iii.240; No. 8 at M i.144; No. 9 at S i.128=Th 2, 58 & 141 (with khandhānam for khandhāsam); No. 10 as āsīvisa (poisonous fangs of a snake) yesu mucchitā bālā Th 2, 451, and several at many other places of the Canon. Cases used adverbially: - kāmam acc. as adv. (a) yathā kāmam according to inclination, at will, as much as one chooses S i.227; J i.203; PvA 63, 113, 176; yena kāmam wherever he likes, just as he pleases A iv.194; Vv i.11 (=icchānurū-pam VvA 11) - (b) willingly, gladly, let it be that, usually with imper. S i.222; J i.233; iii.147; iv.273; VvA 95; kāmam taco nahāru ca atṭhi ca avasissatu (avasussatu in J) sarīre up- asussatu māmsa - lohitaṃ ”willingly shall skin, sinews and bone remain, whilst flesh and blood shall wither in the body” M i.481; A i.50; S ii.28; J i.71, 110; -kāmāsā (instr.) in same sense J iv.320; vi.181; -kāmēna (instr.) do. J v.222, 226; -kāmā for the love of, longing after (often with hi) J iii.466; iv.285, 365; v.294; vi.563, 589; cp. Mhv iii.18, 467. -akāmā unwillingly D i.94; J vi.506; involuntarily J v.237.-**bhoga** *enjoyment of sensual pleasures, gratification of desires* S i.74 (sāratta - °esu giddhā kāmesu mucchitā); Th 2, 464; It 94 (- °esu paṇḍito who discriminates in worldly pleasures); J ii.65; -**bhogin** *enjoying the pleasures of the senses* Vin i.203, 287; ii.136, 149; D iii.124, 125; Miln 243, 350, as Ep. of the kāmūpapatti - beings It 94; as ten kinds A v.177; as bringing evil, being blameworthy S i.78; cp. A iv.281, 438; S iv.333 sq.; A iii.351; Th 2, 486; J iii.154. ye keci kāmesu asaṇṇatā janā avītarāgā idha k - bhogino (etc.) A ii.6, cp. ii.17. kāmabhogī kām’ārāmo kāmārato kāma - sammudita A iv.439; - °seyyā sleeping at ease, way of lying down, the second of the four ways of sleeping (kāmabhogīseyyā vāmena passena) A ii.244; -**giddhin** f. °inī same Mhvs vi.3. -guṇā (pl.) always as pañca: *the five strands of sensual pleasures, viz., the pleasures which are to be enjoyed by means of the five senses; collectively all sensual pleasures.* Def. as cakkhu-viññeyyā rūpā, etc. A iii.411; D i.245; ii.271; iii.131, 234; Nd2 s. v.; Ps i.129; as manāpiyehi rūpādīhi pañcahi kāma - koṭṭhāsehi bandhanehi vā DA i.121, where it is also divided into two groups: mānusakā and dibbā. As constituents of kā-marāga at Nett 28; as vana (desire) Nett 81. - In the popular view they are also to be enjoyed in ”heaven”: saggam lokam upapajjissāmi tattha dibbehi pañcahi k - guṇehi samappito samangibhūto paricāressāmi ti Vin iii.72; mentioned as pleasures in Nandana S i.5; M i.505; A iii.40, iv.118; in various other connections S iv.202; Vv 307; Pv iii.71 (°ehi sobhasi; expl.

PvA 205 by kāma - kotṭhāsehi); PvA 58 (paricārenti); cp. also kāma - kāmin. As the highest joys of this earth they are the share of men of good fortune, like kings, etc. (mānusakā k^o guṇā) S v.409; A v.272, but the same passage with ”dibbehi pañcahi k^o - guṇehi samappita . . .” also refers to earthly pleasures, e. g. S i.79, 80 (of kings); S v.342 (of a Cakkavatti); A ii.125; iv.55, 239; v.203; of the soul D i.36; Vbh 379; other passages simply quoting k - g^o as worldly pleasures are e. g. S i.16=Sn 171; S i.92; iv.196. 326; A iii.69 (itthirūpasmim); D i.60, 104; Sdhp 261. In the estimation of the early Buddhists, however, this bundle of pleasures is to be banned from the thought of every earnest striver after perfection: their critique of the kāmaguṇā begins with ”pañc’ ime bhikkhave kāmaguṇā . . .” and is found at various places, e. g. in full at M i.85=Nd2 s. v.; M i.454; ii.42; iii.114; quoted at M i.92; A iii.411; iv.415, 430, 449, 458. Other expressions voicing the same view are: gedho pañcannaṃ k^o - guṇā-naṃ adhivacanaṃ A iii.312 sq.; asisūnā . . . adhivac^o M i.144; nivāpo... adhivac^o M i.155; sāvaṭṭo . . . adhivac^o It 114. In connection w. rata & giddha PvA 3; pahīna M iii.295; gathita & mucchita M i.173; mā te kāmaguṇe bhamassu cittaṃ ”Let not thy heart roam in the fivefold pleasures” Dh 371; cittassa vossaggo Vbh 370; asantuṭṭha Vbh 350. See also Sn 50, 51, 171, 284, 337. -guṇika consisting of fivefold desire, appl. to rāga S ii.99; J iv.220; Dhs A.371;

- **Paricarati** [pari+carati] to move about, in var. senses, viz. 1. to go about, look after A iii.94 (upatṭhahati+) J v.421; PvA 175. - 2. to worship (only in connection aggin p. to worship the fire) D i.101; S i.166; Dh 107; J i.494; Sn p. 79 (=payirupāsati SnA 401). - 3. to roam about, to feast one’s senses, to amuse oneself, play, sport PvA 77 (indriyāni=kīlāmi Pv ii.121). - We often find reading pariharati for paricarati, e. g. at DhA ii.232; cp. paricāreti for °hāreti PvA 175; paricaraṇā for °haraṇā PvA 219. - pp. pariciṇṇa; Caus. paricāreti (q. v.).
- **Paricāreti** [Caus. of paricarati] 1. to serve, wait on, attend upon, honour, worship [cp. BSk. paricārayati Divy 114 sq., 421] S i.124 (pāde); DhA iii.196 (id.); J i.81 (°cāritabba - ṭṭhāna place of worship); iv.274; v.9. - Pass. paricāriyati, ppr. °iyamāna M i.46, 504; J i.58. In this sense it may also be taken as ”being delighted or entertained by.” - 2. to amuse oneself, gratify one’s senses, to have recreation, find pleasure [cp. BSk. paricārayati Divy 1, and freq. phrase pañcahi kāmaguṇehi samarpitā samangibhūtā p. e. g. MVastu i.32] Vin ii.290; iii.72 (pañcahi kamaguṇehi samappitā etc.); D i.36 (id.), 104 (id.); M i.504 (id.); Th 1, 96 (saggesu); Pv i.116 (=yathā sukkhaṃ cārenti indriyāni PvA 58); iv.129 (read °cārayanti for °vārayanti, cp. PvA 228 indriyāni p.). - pp. paricārita q. v. See also parivāreti.
- **Muyhati** [Vedic muhyati, muh; defn Dhṭp 343: mucchā-yaṃ; 460: vecitte; cp. moha & momuha] to get bewildered, to be infatuated, to become dull in one’s senses, to be stupified. Justas rāga, dosa & moha form a set, so do the verbs rajjati, dussati, muyhati, e. g. Miln 386 (rajjasi rajjanīyesu, dussanīyesu dussasi, muyhase mohaniyesu). Otherwise rare as finite verb; only DhsA 254 (in defn of moha) & Sdhp 282, 605 (so read for mayhate).- pp. mūḷha & muddha¹.
- **Yācitaka** (adj.) [yācita+diminutive (disparaging) ending °ka] asked, begged, borrowed M i.365 (° m bhogaṃ); J iv.358=vi.127 (° m yānaṃ and ° m dhanāṃ, alluding to M i.365 - 366), with expln J iv.358: ”yaṃ parena dinnattā labbhati taṃ yācita - sadisam eva hoti.” - (nt.) anything borrowed, borrowed goods: yācitak’ ūpamā kāmā (in app’ assādā kāmā passage) ”the pleasures of the senses are like borrowed goods” Vin ii.25=M i.130= A iii.97=Th 2,

490=Nd2 71 (correct yācitan’); expld in detail at M i.365. - See also DhA i.403 (ye y. gahetvā na paṭidenti); ThA 288 (kāmā=yācītaka - bhaṇḍasadisā tāvakālik’ aṭṭhena).

- **Pañca** (adj. - num.) [Ved. pañca, Idg. *penque; cp. Gr. πέντε, Lat. quinque, Goth. fimf, Lith. penki, Oir. coic] number 5. - Cases: gen. dat. pañcannaṃ, instr. abl. pañcahi, loc. pañcasu; often used in compositional form pañca° (cp. Ved. pañcāra with 5 spokes i.16413; Gr. πέντε βολοί, Lat. quinquennis etc.). - 1. Characteristics of No. 5 in its use, with ref. to lit. & fig. application. "Five" is the number of "comprehensive and yet simple" unity or a set; it is applied in all cases of a natural and handy comprehension of several items into a group, after the 5 fingers of the hand, which latter lies at the bottom of all primitive expressions of No. 5 (see also below pañc’ angulika. The word for 5 itself in its original form is identical with the word for hand *prGq, cp. Lat. com°, decem, centum etc.) - °**kāmaguṇā pleasures of the 5 senses** (=tag-gocarāni pañc’ āyatanāni gahitāni honti SnA 211). - °**macchariyāni 5 kinds of selfishness: āvāsa° kula° lābha° vaṇṇa° dhamma° . °rajāni defilements: rūpa°, sadda° etc. (of the 5 senses) Nd1 505; SnA 574.**
- **Cāreti** [Denom. fr. cara; cp. carati] **to set going, to pasture, feed, preserve: indriyāni c. to feast one’s senses** (cp. Ger. "augenweide") PvA 58; khamtiṃ c. to feed meekness DA i.277; olambakaṃ cārento drooping J i.174; Pass. ppr. cāriyamāna being handed round J iv.2 (not vā°) - pp. carita. - Cp. vi°.

3.5 Etymology of having a say over senses of the body . . .

According to the Pali Text Society’s Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the online Pali dictionary at Univ. of Chicago, *these words in pali might be of immense use, while trying to grasp the exposition in section 2.3 -*

- **Aggi** [Vedic agni = Lat. ignis. Besides the contracted form aggi we find the diaeretic forms gini (q. v.) and aggini (see below)] fire. - 1. **fire, flames, sparks; conflagration**, Vin ii.120 (fire in bathroom); M i.487 (anāhāro nibbuto f. gone out for lack of fuel); S iv.185, 399 (sa - upādāno jalati provided with fuel blazes); Sn 62; Dh 70 (= asaniaggi DhA iii.71); J i.216 (sparks), 294 (pyre); ii.102; iii.55; iv.139; VvA 20 (aggimhi tāpanaṃ + udake temaṃ). - The var. phases of lighting and extinguishing the fire are given at A iv.45: aggim ujjaleti (kindle, make burn), ajjuhekkhati (look after, keep up), nib- bāpeti (extinguish, put out), nikkhipati (put down, lay). Other phrases are e. g. aggim jāleti (kindle) J ii.44; gaṇhāti (make or take) J i.494 (cp. below b); deti (set light to) J i.294; nibbāpeti (put out) It 93; Sdhp 552. aggi nibbāyati the f. goes out S ii.85; M i.487; J i.212 (udake through water); Miln 304. aggi nibbuto the f. is extinguished (cp. °nibbāna) J i.61; Miln 304. agginā dahati to burn by means of fire, to set fire to A i.136, 199; PvA 20. udar° the fire supposed to regulate digestion PvA 33; cp. Dial. ii.208, note 2; kapp°uṭṭhān° **the universal conflagration** J iii.185; dāv° a wood or jungle fire J i.212; naḷ° the burning of a reed J vi.100; padīp° fire of a lamp Miln 47. 2. the sacrificial fire: In one or two of the passages in the older texts this use of Aggi is ambiguous. It may possibly be intended to denote the personal Agni, the fire - god. But the commentators do not think so, and the Jātaka commentary, when it means Agni, has the phrase Aggi Bhagavā the Lord Agni, e. g. at J i.285, 494; ii.44. The ancient ceremony of kindling a holy fire on the day the child is born and keeping it up throughout his life, is also

referred to by that commentary e. g. J i.285; ii.43. Aggim paricarati (cp. °paricāriyā) to serve the sacred fire Vin i.31 (jaṭilā aggī paricaritukāmā); A v.263, 266; Th 2, 143 (= aggihuttaṃ paric° ThA 136); Dh 107; J i.494; DhA ii.232. aggim juhati (cp. °homa, °hutta) to sacrifice (in)to the fire A ii.207; often combd. with aggihuttaṃ paricarati, e. g. S i.166; Sn p. 79. aggim namati & santappeti to worship the fire A v.235. aggissa (gen.) paricāriko J yi.207 (cp. below °paricārika); aggissa ādhānaṃ A iv.41. - 3. (ethical, always - °) *the fire of burning, consuming, feverish sensations*. Freq. in standard set of 3 fires, viz. rāg°, dos°, moh°, or the fires of lust, anger and bewilderment. The number three may possibly have been chosen with reference to the three sacrificial fires of Vedic ritual. At S iv.19; A iv.41 sq. there are 7 fires, the 4 last of which are āhuneyy°, gahapat°, dakkhiṇeyy°, kaṭṭh°. But this trinity of cardinal sins lies at the basis of Buddhist ethics, & the fire simile was more probably suggested by the number. D iii.217; It 92, Vbh 368. In late books are found others: *ind° the fire of the senses* PvA 56; dukkh° the glow of suffering ib. 60; bhavadukkh° of the misery of becomings Sdhp. 552; vippaṭisār° burning remorse PvA 60; sok° burning grief ib. 41. Note. The form aggini occurs only at Sn 668 & 670 in the meaning of "pyre", and in combn. with sama "like", viz. aggini - samaṃ jalitaṃ 668 (= samantato jali taṃ aggim Sn A 480); aggini - samāsu 670 (= aggisamāsu Sn A 481). The form agginī in phrase niccagginī can either be referred to gini (q. v.) or has to be taken as nom. of aggini (in adj. function with īmetri causa; otherwise as adj. agginim), meaning looking constantly after the fire, i. e. careful, observant, alert.

- **Abhibhāyatana** (nt.) [abhibhū + āyatana] *position of a master or lord, station of mastery. The traditional account of these gives 8 stations or stages of mastery over the senses* (see Dial. ii.118; Exp. i.252), detailed identically at all the foll. passages, viz. D ii.110; iii.260 (& 287); M ii.13; A i.40; iv.305, 348; v.61. Mentioned only at S iv.77 (6 stations); Ps i.5; Nd2 466 (as an accomplishment of the Bhagavant); Dhs 247.
- **Kanta**¹ [Sk. kānta, pp. of kāmeti] - 1. (adj.) in special sense an attribute of worldly pleasure (cp. kāma, kāmaguṇā): pleasant, lovely, enjoyable; freq. in form. iṭṭhā kantā manāpā, referring to the pleasures of the senses S i.245; ii.192; iv.60, 158, 235 sq.; v.22, 60, 147; A ii.66 sq.; M i.85; Sn 759; It 15; Vbh 2, 100, 337; bāla° (lovely in the opinion of the ignorant) Sn 399.- D ii.265; iii.227 (ariya°); J iii.264; v.447; with ref. to the fruit of action as giving pleasure:°phala Kvu 35, 211, PvA 277 (hatthi -) k° pleasing to elephants; of manta DhA i.163; of viṇā J vi.255, 262; DhA i.163. - 2. beloved by, favourite of, charming J vi.255, 262; DhA i.163. - 3. (n.) the beloved one, the husband J vi.370 (wrongly written kan tena); of a precious stone Miln 118; Sdhp 608, cp. suriya°, canda° - kantā (f.) the beloved one, the wife J v.295; kantena (instr.) agree- ably, with kind words A ii.213; J v.486 (where porisādassa kante should be read as porisādassak' ante). - a° undesired, disagreeable, unpleasant, in same form as kanta, e. g. D ii.192; in other combn J v.295; Vbh 100; Nett 180; PvA 193. - akantena with unpleasant words A ii.213. - kantatara compar. J iii.260.
- **Kata** (& sometimes kaṭa) [pp. of karoti] *done, worked, made*. Extremely rare as v. trs. in the common meaning of E. make, Ger. machen, or Fr. faire (see the cognate kapp and jan, also uppajjati & vissajjati); its proper sphere of application is either ethical (as pāpaṃ, kusalaṃ, kammaṃ: cp. ii.1 b) or in such combinations, where its original meaning of "built, prepared, worked out" is still preserved (cp. i.1 a nagara, and 2 a). °*indiya trained in his senses* Th 1, 725

- **Okkhipati** [ava + khipati; Sk. avakṣipati] *to throw down or out, cast down, drop; fig. usually appld. to the eyes = cast down, hence transferred to the other senses and used in meaning "keep under, restrain, to have control over"* (cp. also avakkhāyati); aor. °khipi A iv.264 (indriyāni); ger. °khipitvā Vin iv.18 (id.). - pp. avakkhitta & okkhitta (q. v.).
- **Gutta** [Sk. gupta, pp. of gup in med. - pass. sense, cp. gopeti]. - I. as pp. *guarded, protected*. - (a) lit. nagaraṃ guttaṃ a *well - guarded city* Dh 315=Th 1, 653, 1005; Devinda° protected by the Lord of gods Vv 308. - (b) fig. (med.) *guarded, watchful, constrained; guarded in, watchful as regards* . . . (with loc.) S iv.70 (agutta & sugutta, with danta, rakkhita); A iii.6(atta° self - controlled); Sn 250 (sotesu gutto+ vijitindriyo), 971 (id.+yatacārin); Dh 36 (cittam). - II. as n. agent (=Sk. goptr, cp. kata in kāla - kata= kālaṃ kartr) *one who guards or observes, a guardian, in Dhammassa gutta* Dh 257, observer of the Norm (expl. DhA iii.282: dhammojapaññāya samannā-gata), cp. dhammagutta S i.222. - **indriya one whose senses are guarded; with well-guarded senses** Sn 63 (+rakkhita - mānasāno; expl. SnA: chassu indriyesu gopitindriyo); Nd2 230; Vv 5015; Pv iv.132;
- **Cakkhu** (nt.) [Vedic cakṣuḥ, etym. not clear, as redupl. perhaps to īks, akṣa eye, kṣaṇa moment, or as intens. to cit, cp. cinteti, & see Walde, Lat. Wtb. under inquam] the eye (nom. sg. cakkhum Vin i.34; S i.115; M iii.134, etc.). - I. The eye as organ of sense - (a) psychologically: cakkhunā rūpaṃ disvā "seeing visible object (shape) with the eye" (Nd2 on rūpa q. v.) is the defin. of this first & most important of the senses (cp. Pv ii.61 dakkhiṇa c.=the most valuable thing): the psychology of sight is discussed at DA i.194 sq., and more fully at Dhs 597 sq. (see DhsA 306 sq; Dhs trsl. 173 sq.); cp. cak khunā puriso ālokati rūpagatāni Nd2 234. In any enumeration of the senses cakkhu heads the list, e. g. Vin i.34; D i.21; ii.308, 336 sq.; iii.102, 225, 244 sq.; 269; Nett 28. - See rūpa. Also combd. with sota: M i.318; iii.264; A i.281. - cakkhusmim haññati rūpehi S iv.201; hata° A i.129. passāmi naṃ manasā cakkhunā va "I see him with my mind as with my eye" Sn 1142. - Vin i.184; S i.32, 199; iv.123; Dh 360; J iv.137; DA i.183; Nett 191. Vism 444 sq. As adj. (-°) seeing, having or catching sight of: eka° (dvi°) one - eyed (two°) A i.128 sq.; āmisa° seeing an object of sensual enjoyment S ii.226; iv.159; J v.91 (=kilesalola). acakkhu blind A iii.250, 256; Ps i.129. - (b) ethically: as a "sense" belonging to what is called "body" (kāya) it shares all the qualities of the latter (see kāya), & is to be regarded as an instr. only, i. e. the person must not value it by itself or identify himself with it. Subduing the senses means in the first place acquiring control over one's eyes (cp. okkhitta cakkhu, with down - cast eyes Sn 63, 411, 972; Pv iv.344; & indriyesu guttadvāra; °indriya). In this connection the foll. passages may be mentioned: Vin i.34; D i.70; S iv.123; ii.244 (aniccaṃ, etc.); iii.255 (do.) iv.81, 128 (na tumhākaṃ); Ps I.132 (aniccattham). Numerous others see under rūpa. - II. The eye as the most important channel of mental acquiring, as faculty of perception & apperception; insight, knowledge (cp. veda, ο λ δ α to vid, to see). In connection with ñāṇa (γ η ω σ ι ζ) it refers to the apperception of the truth (see dhamma - cakkhu): intuition and recognition, which means perfect understanding (cp. the use of the phrase jānāti passati "to know and to see"=to understand clearly). See e. g. S ii.7 - 11, 105; iv.233; v.179; 258; 422 sq. Most frequently as **dhama° "the eye of the truth," said of the attainment of that right knowledge which leads to Arahantship, in phrase virajam vitamalam dh - cakkhum uppajati** Vin i.16; D i.86, 110; S ii.134 sq.; iv.47; 107; v.467; A iv.186; Ps ii.150 sq.; 162; Miln 16. Similarly paññā°, It 52; ariya° M i.510. - III. *The eye as the instr. of supersensuous perception, "clear" sight,*

clairvoyance. This is the gift of favoured beings whose senses are more highly developed than those of others, and who through right cognition have acquired the two "eyes" or visionary faculties, termed dibba-cakkhu & buddha-cakkh It 52; D ii.38 resp. They are most completely described at Nd2 235 (under cakkhumā), & the foll. categories of the range of application of cakkhu are set forth: 1. *maṃsa-cakkhu*: the physical eye which is said to be exceptionally powerful & sensitive. See Kv iii.7 (trans. p. 149 ff.). Vism 428 (maṃsa° 2 ñāṇa°). - 2. *dibba°*: the deva - eye, the eye of a seer, all-pervading, & seeing all that proceeds in hidden worlds.- 3. *paññā°*: the eye of wisdom; he who knows all that can be known (jānaṃ passaṃ recognizing & seeing, i. e. of perfect understanding; cakkhubhūta ñāṇa° dhamma° brahma°). - 4. *buddha°*: the eye of a Buddha or of complete intuition, i. e. of a person who "sees the heart of man," of a being realizing the moral state of other beings and determined to help them on the Path to Right Knowledge. - 5. *samanta°*: (a summary account of Nos. 1 - 4, & in all Scripture - passages a standing Ep. of Gotama Buddha, see below), the eye of all round knowledge, the eye of a Tathāgata, of a being perfected in all wisdom. - Out of these are mentioned & discussed singly or in sets: (Nos. 1 - 5): DhA 306; SnA 351; (Nos. 1 - 3:) It 52=Kvu 251 sq. (It 52=Kvu 254); (dibba:) Vin i.8, 288; ii.183; iii.5; D i.82, 162; iii. 52, iii. 281; M i.213; S i.144, 196; ii.122, 213, 276; iv.240; v.266, 305; A i.165, 256, 281 sq.; iii.19, 29, 418; iv.85, 141, 178, 291; v.13, 35, 68, 200, 211, 340; J iii.346; Ps i.114; ii.175; Vbh 344; PvA 5. - (paññā°) S iv.292; v.467, A i.35; DhA iii.174, 175. - (buddha°) Vin i.6; S i.138; Ps ii.33; PvA 61. - (samanta°) S i.137=Nd² 235⁴; Sn 345, 378, 1063, 1069, 1090, 1133; Ps ii.31=Nd² 235⁵.

- **Jita** [pp. of jayati, conquer] *conquered, subdued, mastered: (nt.) victory.* jītā me pāpakā dhammā Vin i.8; - Dh 40, 104 (attā jitaṃ seyyo for attā jito seyyo see DhA ii.228), 105, 179; Vv 6427 (**jitindriya one whose senses are mastered, cp. guttindriya**). - Cp. vi°.
- **Tapassin** (adj. - n.) [tapas+vin; see tapati & tapa] *one devoted to religious austerities, an ascetic* (non - Buddhist; **WHOEVER WALKS ANY PATH TO COME OUT OF MISERY has to do TAPA OR AUSTERITIES TO RESTRAIN ONESELF - NOTHING TO WITH (non)Buddhists. Siddhartha had done TAPA from many previous life times, as shared in the Jataka**). Fig. *one who exercises self - control & attains mastery over his senses* Vin i.234=A iv.184 (tapassī samaṇo Gotamo); D iii.40, 42 sq., 49; S i.29; iv.330, 337 sq.; M i.77; Sn 284 (isayo pubbakā āsum saññatattā tapassino); Vv 2210; Pv i.32 (°rūpa, under the appearance of a "holy" man: samaṇa - patirūpaka PvA 15); ii.614 (=saṃvāraka PvA 98; tapo etesaṃ atthī ti ibid.).
- **Nirodha** [BSk. nirodha, to nirundhati, cp. nirujjhati & niruddha] *oppression, suppression; destruction, cessation, annihilation (of senses, consciousness, feeling & being in general: sankhārā)*. Bdgh's expln of the word is: "ni - saddo abhāvaṃ, rodha - saddo ca cāraṇaṃ dīpeti Vism 495. - N. in many cases is synonymous with nibbāna & parinibbāna; it may be said to be even a stronger expression as far as the active destruction of the causes of life is concerned. Therefore frequently combd with nibbāna in formula "sabbasankhāra - samatho . . . virāgo nirodho nibbānaṃ," e. g. S i.136; It 88. Nd2 s. nibbāna (see nibbāna iii.6). Also in combn with nibbidā, e.g. S iii.48, 223; iii.163 sq.; v.438. - The opposite of nirodha is samudaya, cp. formula "yaṃ kiñci samudaya - dhammaṃ sabbaṃ taṃ nirodha - dhammaṃ" e. g. Nd2 under sankhārā & passim. (a) Vin i.1, 10; D ii.33, 41, 57 sq., 112; iii.130 sq., 136

sq., 226 sq.; J i.133; ii.9 sq., 223; iii.59 sq., 163; v.438; M i.140, 263, 410; A i.299; iv.456 (=āsavānaṃ parikkhaya); Th 2, 6 (=kilesanīrodha ThA 13), 158; It 46=Sn 755 (nīrodhe ye vimuccanti te janā maccuhāyino); It 62=Sn 754; Sn 731, 1037; Ps i.192; ii.44 sq., 221; Pug 68; Vbh 99 sq., 229; Nett 14, 16 sq.; Vism 372; VvA 63; PvA 220 (jīvitassa). - (b) (as -°): anupubba° D iii.266; A iv.409, 456; abhisañña° D i.180; asesavirāga° S ii.4, 12; iv.86; v.421 sq.; A i.177; ii.158, 161; upādāna° S iii.14; kāma° A iii.410 sq.; jāti° S iv.86; taṇhā° D iii.216; dukkha° D iii.136; S iii.32, 60; iv.4 sq., 14, 384; A i.177; nandi° S iii.14; iv.36; bhava° (=nibbāna) S ii.117; iii.14; A v.9; Ps i.159; sakkāya° D iii.240; S v.410; A ii.165 sq.; iii.246, 325 sq.; v.238 sq.; saññāvedayita° D iii.262, 266; S iv.217, 293 sq.; v. 213 sq.; A i.41; iii.192; iv.306; v.209.

- **Paccakkha** (adj.) [paṭi+akkha³, cp. Ved. pratyakṣa] *“before the eye,” perceptible to the senses, evident, clear, present* DhsA 254; PvA 125; Sdhp 416. Often in obl. cases, viz. instr.°ena personally J i.377; abl.°ato from personal experience J v.45, 195, 281; appaccakkhāya without seeing or direct perception, in expln of paccaya at Vism 532; also in phrase paccakkhatoṇatvā having seen or found out for himself, knowing personally J i.262; iii.168.
- **Samādhi** [fr. saṃ+ā+dhā] 1. *concentration; a concentrated, self - collected, intent state of mind and meditation, which, concomitant with right living, is a necessary condition to the attainment of higher wisdom and emancipation.* In the Subha - suttanta of the Dīgha (D i.209 sq.) samādhi - khandha (“section on concentration”) is the title otherwise given to the cittasampadā, which, in the ascending order of merit accruing from the life of a samaṇa (see Sāmaññaphala - suttanta, and cp. Dial. i.57 sq.) stands between the sīla-sampadā and the paññā-sampadā. In the Ambaṭṭha - sutta the corresponding terms are sīla, caraṇa, vijjā (D. i.100). Thus *samādhi would comprise (a) the guarding of the senses (indriyesu gutta - dvārata), (b) self - possession (sati - sampajañña), (c) contentment (santutṭhi), (d) emancipation from the 5 hindrances (nīvaraṇāni), (e) the 4 jhānas.* In the same way we find samādhi grouped as one of the sampadās at A iii.12 (sīla°, samādhi°, paññā°, vimutti°), and as samādhi-khandha (with sīla° & paññā°) at D iii.229 (+vimutti°); A i.125; ii.20; iii.15; v.326; Nd1 21; Nd2 p. 277 (s. v. sīla). It is defined as cittassa ekaggatā M i.301; Dhs 15; DhsA 118; cp. Cpd. 89 n. 4; identified with avikkhepa Dhs 57, and with *samatha Dhs 54. - sammā° is one the constituents of the eightfold ariya - magga*, e. g. D iii.277; VbhA 120 sq. - See further D ii.123 (ariya); Vin i.97, 104; S i.28; Nd1 365; Miln 337; Vism 84 sq. (with definition), 289 (+vipassanā), 380 (°vipphārā iddhi); VbhA 91; DhA i.427; and on term in general Heiler, Buddhistische Versenkung 104 sq. - 2. *Description & characterization of samādhi: Its four nimittas or signs are the four satipaṭṭhānas* M i.301; *six conditions and six hindrances* A iii.427; other hindrances M iii.158. The *second jhāna is born from samādhi* D ii.186; *it is a condition for attaining kusalā dhammā* A i.115; Miln 38; *conducive to insight* A iii.19, 24 sq., 200; S iv.80; *to seeing heavenly sights* etc. D i.173; *to removing mountains etc.* A iii.311; *removes the delusions of self* A i.132 sq.; *leads to Arahantship* A ii.45; the ānantarika s. Sn 226; *cetosamādhi (rapture of mind)* D i.13; A ii.54; iii.51; S iv.297; citta° id. Nett 16. *dhammasamādhi almost identical with samatha* S iv.350 sq. - *Two grades of samādhi distinguished, viz. upacāra - s. (preparatory concentration) and appanā - s. (attainment concentration)* DA i.217; Vism 126; Cpd. 54, 56 sq.; *only the latter results in jhāna; to these a 3rd (preliminary) grade is added as khaṇika° (momentary)* at Vism 144. - *Three kinds of s. are distinguished, suññata or empty, appaṇihita or aimless, and animitta or signless* A i.299; S iv.360; cp. iv.296;

Vin iii.93; Miln 337; cp. 333 sq.; DhsA 179 sq., 222 sq., 290 sq.; see Yogāvacara's Manual p. xxvii; samādhi (tayo samādhi) is savitakka savicāra, avitakka vicāramatta or avitakka avicāra D iii.219; Kvu 570; cp. 413; Miln 337; DhsA 179 sq.; *it is fourfold chanda -, viriya -, citta -, and vīmaṁsā - samādhi* D ii.213; S v.268. - *Another fourfold division is that into hāna - bhāgiya, ṭhiti°, visesa°, nibbedha°* D iii.277 (as "dhammā duppaṭivijjhā").

- **Samudda** [cp. Vedic samudra, fr. sam+udra, water] *a (large) quantity of water*, e. g. the Ganges; the sea, the ocean D i.222; M i.493; A i.243; ii.48 sq.; iii.240; D iii.196, 198; S i.6, 32, 67; J i.230; iv.167, 172; Dh 127; Nd1 353; SnA 30; PvA 47, 104, 133, 271; explained by adding sāgara, S ii.32; *four oceans* S ii.180, 187; ThA 111. Often characterized as mahā° the great ocean, e. g. Vin ii.237; A i.227; ii.55; iii.52; iv.101; SnA 371; DhA iii.44. *Eight qualities*: A iv.198, 206; popular etymology Miln 85 sq. (viz. "yattakaṁ udakaṁ tattakaṁ loṇaṁ," and vice versa); *the eye etc. (the senses), an ocean which engulfs all beings* S iv.157 (samudda=mahā udakarāsi). - Cp. sāmuddika.
- **Vasa** (m. & nt.) [cp. Vedic vaśa; vaś to be eager, to desire] *power, authority, control, influence* S i.43, 240 (kodho vo vasam āyātu: shall be in your power; vasa=āṇāpavattana K.S. i.320); M i.214 (bhikkhu cittaṁ vasaṁ vatteti, no ca cittassa vasena vattati: he brings the heart under his control, but is not under the influence of the heart); Sn 297, 315, 578, 586, 968; Sdhp 264. - The instr. vasena is used as an adv. in meaning "on account of, because" e. g. mahaggha - vasena mahāraha "costly on account of its great worth" PvA 77; cp. J i.94; PvA 36 (putta°); Mhvs 33, 92 (paṭisanthāra°). - Freq. in phrase vase (loc.) vattati to be in somebody's power J v.316 (te vase vattati), cp. M i.214 (cittassa vasena vattati) & 231 (vatteti te tasmim vasa have you power over that?); trs. vase vatteti to get under control, to get into one's power J iv.415 (attano vase vattetvā); v.316 (rājāno attano v. v.); DhA ii.14 (rājānaṁ attano v. v.), cp. M i.214 (vasan vatteti) & PvA 89 (vasaṁ vattento). - Note. The compn form in connection with kṭ and bhū is vasi° (q. v.). - **vattin-** 1. (*act., i. e. vatteti*) *having highest power, domineering, autocrat, (all -)mighty; fig. having self-mastery, controlling one's senses* D i.247; ii.261; A ii.24; It 122; Th 2. 37; Pv ii.333; Miln 253; DA i.111, 114, 121; SnA 133 (°bhavana). - 2. (*pass.; i. e. vattati*) *being in one's power, dependent, subject* J iii.224; v.316; ThA 226 (read vattino for °vattito!).
- **Vāta** [Vedic vāta, of vā; cp. Sk. vāti & vāyati to blow, vāyu wind; Lat. ventus, Goth. winds=wind; Ohg. wājan *to blow*, Oir. feth air; Gr. α ῥ η μ ι to blow, α ῥ η ι η ς wind, Lith. *áudra storm etc.*] *wind*. There *exists a common distinction of winds into 2 groups: "internal" and "external" winds*, or the ajjhattikā vāyo - dhātu (wind category), and the bāhirā. They are discussed at Vbh 84, quoted at MA 30, 31, and expld in detail at VbhA 70 sq.; Vism 350. The bāhirā also at Nd2 562, and in poetical form at S iv.218. - The *internal winds* (see below 2) comprise the foll.: uddhangamā vātā, adhogamā, kucchisayā, koṭṭhāsasayā, angam - ang' - ānusārino, satthakā, khurakā, uppalakā, assāso, passāso, i. e. *all kinds of winds (air) or drawing pains (rheumatic?) in the body, from hiccup, stitch and stomach - ache up to breathing. Their complement are the external winds* (see below 1), viz. puratthimā vātā, pac-chimā, uttarā, dakkhiṇā (from the 4 quarters of the sky), sarajā arajā, sītā uṇhā, parittā adhimattā, kālā, verambha°, pakkha°, supaṇṇa°, tālavanta°, vidhūpana. ° These are characterized according to direction, dust, temperature, force, height & other causes (like fanning etc.). - 1. wind (of the air) S iv.218 (vātā ākāse vāyanti); Sn 71, 348, 591 (vāto

tūlaṃ va dhamsaye), 622, 1074; J i.72; Pug 32; Vism 31. adhimatta v. S iv.56; mahā° S ii.88; A i.136, 205; ii.199; iv.312; *veramba°* (*winds blowing in high regions*: upari ākāse S ii.231) A i.137; Th 1, 598; J vi.326. - 2. *"winds" of the body, i. e. pains caused by (bad) circulation, sometimes simply (uncontrolled) movements in the body, sometimes rheumatic pains, or sharp & dragging pains in var. parts of the body* Nett. 74. Also *applied to certain humours, supposed to be caused by derangements of the "winds" of the body* (cp. Gr. χ u μ ó ς ; or *E. slang "get the wind up"*), *whereas normal "winds" condition normal health*: Pv ii.61 (tassa vātā balīyanti: *bad winds become strong, i. e. he is losing his senses*, cp. PvA 94: ummāda - vātā). - anga° Pain in the limbs (or joints), rheumatism Vin i.205; udara° belly ache J i.393, 433; DhA iv.129; kammaja° birth - pains Vism 500; kucchi° pains in the abdomen (stomach) VbhA 5; piṭṭhi° pains in the back ibid. - 3. (fig.) atmosphere, condition, state; or as pp. (of vāyati) scented (with), full of, pervaded (by), at Vin i.39 (vijana° pervaded by loneliness, having an atmosphere of loneliness; Kern. Toev. s. v. vāta wrongly "troop, crowd." The same passage occurs at D iii.38, where Rh. D., Dial. iii.35, trsls "where the breezes from the pastures blow"; with expln vijana= vṛjana [see vajati], hardly justified. In same connection at A iv.88); Miln 19 (isi° - parivāta scented with an atmosphere of Sages; Rh. D. differently: "bringing down the breezes from the heights where the Sages dwell"; forced). - On vāta in similes see J.P.T.S. 1907, 135.

- **Mudu** (adj.) [Vedic mṛdu, fr. mṛd: see maddati; cp. Lat. mollis (fr. *molduis); Gr. $\acute{\alpha}$ μ α λ δ $\acute{\upsilon}$ ν ω to weaken, Cymr. blydd soft] *soft, mild, weak, tender* D ii.17=iii.143 (+talūṇa); A ii.151 (*pañcindriyāni mudūni, soft, blunt, weak*: opp. tikkha); S ii.268 (°talūṇa - hatthapādā); Sn 447 (=muduka SnA 393); Th 1, 460 (=loving); Pv i.92; Vism 64; PvA 46, 230. Compar. mudutara S v.201. - **indriya** (mud°) *weak, slow minded, of dull senses* Ps i.121=ii.195; Vism 87
- **Rakkhita** [pp. of rakkhati] guarded, protected, saved S iv.112 (rakkhitena kāyena, rakkhitāya vācāya etc.); A i.7 (cittaṃ r.); Sn 288 (dhamma°), 315 (gottā°); VvA 72 (mātu°, pitu° etc.); PvA 61, 130. - Note. rakkhitaṃ karoti at Mhvs 28, 43 Childers trsls *"take under protection,"* but Geiger reads rakkhike and trsls *"appoint as watchers."* - **atta** *one who guards his character* S i.154; J i.412; SnA 324. - **indriya** *guarding one's senses* Sn 697. - **mānasāna** *guarding one's mind* Sn 63 (=gopitamānasāno - rakkhita - citto Nd2 535).
- **Vijita** [pp. of vijayati] 1. *conquered, subdued, gained, won* Sn 46; SnA 352; DA i.160; PvA 75, 76, 161. - Cp. nijjita. - 2. (nt.) *conquered land, realm, territory, kingdom* J i.262; Vv 8120 (=desa VvA 316); DhA i.386. - anga at Pv iii.117 (PvA 176) read vījit. °- **indriya** *one who has conquered his senses* Sn 250. - sangāma by whom the battle has been won, victorious D ii.39; It 76; Nd2 542; Pug 68.
- **Visaya** [cp. Sk. viśaya, fr. vi+śī] 1. *locality, spot, region; world, realm, province, neighbourhood* Sn 977. Often in foll. combns: petti° (or pittī°) and *pettika (a) the world of the manes or petas* M i.73; S iii.224; v.342, 356 sq.; A i.37, 267; ii.126 sq.; iii.211, 339, 414 sq.; iv.405 sq.; v.182 sq.; Pv ii.22; ii.79; J i.51; PvA 25 sq., 59 sq., 214. (b) *the way of the fathers, native or proper beat or range* D iii.58; S v.146 sq.; A iii.67; J ii.59. Yama° the realm of Yama or the Dead Pv ii.82 (=petaloka PvA 107). - 2. *reach, sphere (of the senses), range, scope; object, characteristic, attribute* (cp. Cpd. 143 n. 2) S v.218 (gocara°); Nett 23 (iddhi°); Miln 186, 215, 316; Vism 216 (visayī bhūta), 570=VbhA 182 (mahā° & appa°); KhA 17; SnA 22, 154

- (buddha°), 228 (id.); PvA 72, 89. - avisaya not forming an object, a wrong object, indefinable A v.50; J v.117 (so read for °ara); PvA 122, 197. - 3. object of sense, sensual pleasure SnA 100.
- **Samvuta** [pp. of samvarati] 1. *closed* D i.81. - 2. *tied up* J iv.361. - 3. *restrained, governed, (self -)controlled, guarded* D i.250; iii.48, 97; S ii.231; iv.351 sq.; A i.7 (cittam); ii.25; iii.387; It 96, 118; Sn 340 (indriyesu); Dh 340; DA i.181. asamvuta unrestrained S iv.70; A iii.387; Pug 20, 24; in phrase asamvuṭṭā lokantarikā andhakārā (the world - spaces which are dark &) ungoverned, orderless, not supported, baseless D ii.12. - su° well controlled Vin ii.213; iv.186; S iv.70; Sn 413; Dh 8. -atta self - controlled S i.66. *-indriya having the senses under control* It 91; Pug 35. -kārin M ii.260.
 - **Santa**°1 [pp. of sammati°1] *calmed, tranquil, peaceful, pure* D i.12; Vin i.4; S i.5; A ii.18; Sn 746; Pv iv.134 (=upasanta - kilesa PvA 230); Miln 232, 409; Vism 155 (°anga; opp. oḷārik°anga); DhA ii.13; iii.83. - nt. peace, bliss, nibbāna S iv.370. *-indriya one whose senses are tranquil* A ii.38; Sn 144; Vin i.195; J i.506;
 - **Samappita** [pp. of samappeti] 1. *made over, consigned* Dh 315; Sn 333; Th 2, 451. - 2. *endowed with* (-°), *affected with, possessed of* J v.102 (kaṇṭakena); Pv iv.16 (=allīna PvA 265); PvA 162 (soka - salla° - hadaya); Vism 303 (sallena). - *yasabhoga° possessed of fame & wealth* Dh 303; *dukkhena afflicted with pain* Vv 523; *pañcehi kāmagaṇehi s. endowed with the 5 pleasures of the senses* D i.36, 60; Vin i.15; DA i.121.
 - **Padhāna** (nt.) [fr. pa+dhā, cp. padahati] *exertion, energetic effort, striving, concentration of mind* D iii.30, 77, 104, 108, 214, 238; M ii.174, 218; S i.47; ii.268; iv.360; v.244 sq.; A iii.65 - 67 (5 samayā and 5 asamayā for padhāna), 249; iv.355; v.17 sq.; Sn 424, 428; It 30; Dh 141; J i.90; Nd2 394 (=virīya); Vbh 218 (citta - samādhi p° etc.); Nett 16; DA i.104; DhA i.85 (mahā - padhānam padahitvā); ThA 174; PvA 134. Padhāna is fourfold, viz. samvara°, pahāna°, bhā- vana°, *anurakkhaṇā°* or *exertion consisting in the restraint of one's senses, the abandonment of sinful thoughts, practice of meditation & guarding one's character*. These 4 are mentioned at D iii.225; A ii.16; Ps i.84; ii.14 sq., 56, 86, 166, 174; Ud 34; Nd1 45, 340; Sdhp 594. - Very frequently termed sammappadhāna [cp. BSk. samyak - pradhāna MVastu iii.120; but also samyakprahāṇa, e. g. Divy 208] or "right exertion," thus at Vin i.22; S i.105; iii.96 (the four); A ii.15 (id.); iii.12; iv.125; Nd1 14; Ps i.21, 85, 90, 161; SnA 124; PvA 98. - As padahana at Ps i.17, 21, 181.
 - **Pīṇita** [pp. of pīṇeti] pleased, gladdened, satisfied Vv 1613 (=tuṭṭha VvA 84); Miln 238, 249, 361; usually in phrase pīṇitindriya with satisfied senses, with joyful heart M ii.121; PvA 46, 70.
 - **Bhindati** [bhid, Sk. bhinatti; cp. Lat. findo to split, Goth. beitan=Ger. beissen. Def. at Dhṭp 381, 405 by "vidāraṇe" i. e. splitting] *to split, break, sever, destroy, ruin*. In two bases: *bhid (with der. *bhed) & *bhind. - (a) *bhid: aor. 3rd sg. abhida (=Sk. abhidat) D ii.107; J iii.29 (see also under abhida); abhidā J i.247; ii.163, 164. - fut. bhecchati (Sk. bhetsyati) A i.8. - ger. bhetvā (Sk. bhittvā) Th 1, 753; Sn 62 (v. l. BB bhittvā). - grd. bhejja: only neg. abhejja (q. v.). See also der. bheda, bhedana. - pp. bhinna & Pass. bhijjati. - (b) *bhind: pres. bhindati Nd1 503; DhA i.125 (katham bh. to break a promise); Sdhp 47. - ppr. bhin-danto

Mhvs 5, 185. - Pot. bhinde Vism 36 (sīlasamvaran). - fut. bhindissati Vin ii.198. - aor. bhindi J i.467 (mitta - bhāvaṃ), & abhindi A iv.312 (atta - sambhavaṃ). - ger. bhinditvā J i.425, 490; PvA 12; also in phrase **indriyāni bhinditvā breaking in one's senses, i. e. mastering, controlling them** J ii.274; iv.104, 114, 190. - Caus. I. bhedeti: see vi°. Caus. II. **bhindāpeti to cause to be broken** J i.290 (sīlaṃ); vi.345 (pokkharāṇim) and bhedāpeti Vin iii.42. - See also bhindana.

- **Muta** [for mata, cp. Geiger. P.Gr. § 18] thought, supposed, imagined (i. e. received by other vaguer sense impressions than by sight & hearing) M i.3; Sn 714 (=phusan' araham SnA 498), 812; J v.398 (=anumata C.); Vbh 14, 429 sq. - Often in set diṭṭha suta muta what is seen, heard & thought (? more likely "felt," cp. Nd2 298: diṭṭha=cakkhunā d., sutam=sotena s., mutam=ghānena ghāyitam, jivhāya sāyitam, kāyena phuṭṭam, and viññātam=manasā v.; so that from the interpretation it follows that d. s. m. v. **refer to the action (perception) of the 6 senses, where muta covers the 3 of taste, smell & touch, and viññāta the function of the manas**) S i.186 (K.S. i.237 note); iv.73; Th i.1216. Similarly the **psychol. analysis of the senses** at Dhs 961: rūp' āyatanam diṭṭham; sadd - āyat. sutam; gandh°, ras°, phoṭṭhabb° mutam; sabbam rūpam manasā viññātam. See on this passage Dhs trsl. § 961 note. In the same sense DhsA 388 (see Expositor, ii.439). - D iii.232; Sn 790 (cp. Nd1 87 sq. in extenso) 793, 798, 812, 887, 901, 914, 1086, 1122. Thus quite a main tenet of the old (popular) psychology.

3.6 Etymology of the uncontrolled . . .

According to the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the online Pali dictionary at Univ. of Chicago, **these words in pali might be of immense use, while trying to grasp the exposition in section 2.3** -

- **Asamāhita** (adj.) [a + samāhita] **not composed, uncontrolled, not firm** It 113 (opp. susamāhita); Dh 110, 111; Pug 35.
- **Caṇḍa** (adj.) [Sk. caṇḍa] **fierce, violent; quick - tempered, uncontrolled, passionate** Vin ii.194 (hatthi); D. i.90 (=māṇa - nissita - kopa - yutta DA i.256); S i.176; ii.242; A ii.109=Pug 47 (sakagava°); J i.450; ii.210, 349; Vism 343, 279 (°sota, **fierce current**), (°hatthi); DhA iv.9 (goṇa) 104; Sdhp 41, 590, 598. - f. caṇḍī M i.126; J ii.443; iii.259; Pv ii.34 (=kodhanā PvA 83). - Compar. caṇḍatara S ii.242. - In cpds. caṇḍi°, see caṇḍikata & caṇḍitta.
- **Pākata** (adj.) [=pakata; on ā for a see Geiger, P.Gr. §331. Cp. Sk. prakāṣa Halāyudha. The spelling is sometimes pākāṣa] 1. **common, vulgar, uncontrolled**, in phrase **pākat-indriya of uncontrolled mind** S i.61 (=samvarābhāvena gihikāle viya vivaṭa - indriya K.S. 320), 204; iii.93; v.269; A i.70, 266, 280; iii.355, 391; Th 1, 109 (C. asamvuta, see Brethren 99); Pug 35. - At Miln 251 pākata is to be read pāpakā. - 2. **open, common, unconcealed** J i.262 (pākato jāto was found out); Sn A 343; PvA 103 (for āvi). - 3. commonly known, familiar Vism 279; PvA 17 (devā), 23, 78 (su°), 128; VvA 109 (+paññāta); °m karoti to make manifest Vism 287; °bhāva being known DhsA 243; PvA 103. - 4. renowned, well - known DA i.143; PvA 107.

3.7 Etymology of disease . . .

According to the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the online Pali dictionary at Univ. of Chicago, *these words in pali might be of immense use, while trying to grasp the exposition in section 2.3* -

- **Roga** [Vedic roga: ruj (see rujati), cp. Sk. rujā breakage, illness] illness, disease. - The defn of roga at J ii.437 is "roga rujana - sabhāvattaṃ." There are many diff. enumerations of rogas and sets of standard combns, of which the foll. may be mentioned. At sn 311 (cp. D iii.75) *it is said that in old times there were only 3 diseases, viz. icchā, anasanaṃ, jarā, which gradually, through slaughtering of animals, increased to 98.* Bdgh at SnA 324 hints at *these 98 with "cakkhu - rog' adinā - bhedenā."* *Beginning with this (cakkhuroga affection of the eye) we have a list of 34 rogas* at Nd1 13 (under pākāṭa - parissayā or open dangers=Nd1 360=Nd2 420) & Nd2 3041 B, viz. *cakkhu° & the other 4 senses, sīsā°, kaṇṇā°, mukha°, danta°; kāsa, sāsa, pināsa, ḍāha, jara; kucchiroga, mucchā, pakkhandikā, sūlā, visūcikā; kuṭṭham, gaṇḍo, kilāso, soso, apamāro; daddu, kaṇḍu, kacchu, rakhasā, vitacchikā, lohita - pittaṃ, madhumeho, amsā, piḷakā, bhagandalā. This list is followed by list of 10 ābādhas & under "dukkha" goes on with var. other "ills," which however do not make up the number 98.* The same list is found at A v.110. The 10 ābādhas (Nd2 3041 C.) occur at A ii.87 & Miln 308 (as āgantuka - rogā). The 4 "rogas" of the Sun (miln 273, cp. Vin ii.295) are: *abbha, mahikā, megha, Rāhu.* - Another mention of roga together with plagues which attack the corn in the field is given at J v.401, viz. visa - vāta; mūsika - salabha - suka - pāṇaka; setatṭhika - roga etc., i. e. hurtful winds, mice, moths & parrots, mildew. - The combn roga, gaṇḍa, salla is sometimes found, e. g. M ii.230; Vism 335. Of other single rogas we mention: *kucchi° (stomach - ache) J i.243; ahivātaka° Vin i.78; J ii.79; iv.200; DhA i.231; paṇḍu° jaundice Vin i.206; J ii.102; DhA i.25; tiṇapupphaka° hay - fever Miln 216.* - See also *ātanka & ābādha.* On roga in similes see J.P.T.S. 1907, 130. - D i.11, 73; iii.182; S iii.32; iv.64; A ii.128, 142 sq.; iv.289; Nd1 486; Vism 236 (*as cause of death*), 512 (*in simile*); VbhA 88 (*in sim. of dukkha etc.*); ThA 288; VvA 6 (*rogena phutṭha*), 75 (*sarīre r. uppajji*); PvA 86 (*kacchu°*), 212 (*rogena abhibhūta*). - Opp. aroga health: see sep.
- **Rogin** (adj.) [fr roga] having a disease, suffering from (-°); one who has a disease Vism 194 (ussanna - vyādhi dukkhassa); Sdhp 86. - paṇḍu° one who has the jaundice J ii.285; iii.401.

4 ⊕ The Tongue Seal, i.e **Jivhā-Muddā / Khecari-Mudrā** (Pali / Sanskrit)

4.1 Etymology of Jivhā and Muddā . . .

According to the Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary by Davids and Stede (1921-1925) OR the online Pali dictionary at Univ. of Chicago, *these words in pali might be of immense use, while trying to grasp the tongue seal 2.3* -

- **Jivhā** (f.) [Vedic jihvā, cp. Lat. lingua (older dingua); Goth. tuggo; Ohg. zunga; E. tongue] *the tongue.* - (a) physically: Vin i.34; A iv.131; Sn 673, 716; Dh 65, 360; J ii.306; PvA 99 (of Petas: visukkha - kanthaṭṭha j.), 152. - Of the tongue of the mahāpurusha which could

touch his ears & cover his forehead: Sn 1022; p. 108; & pahūta - jivhatā the characteristic of possessing a prominent tongue (as the 27th of the 32 Mahāpurisa - lakṣhaṇāni) D i.106=Sn p. 107; D ii.18.- dujjivha (adj.) *having a bad tongue (of a poisonous snake)* A iii.260. - (b) psychologically: *the sense of taste*. It follows after ghāna (smell) as the *4th sense in the enum of sense - organs* (jivhāya rasam sāyati Nd2 under rūpa; jivhā - viññeyya rasa D i.245; ii.281; M ii.42) Vin i.34; D iii.102, 226; M i.191; Vism 444.

- **Muddā** (f.) [cp. (late?) Sk. mudrā] 1. *a seal, stamp, impression; - rāja° the royal seal* DhA i.21. Also with ref. to the State Seal at Miln 280, 281 in cpds. muddakāma (amacca) & mudda - paṭilābha. - 2. the art of calculation mentioned as a noble craft (ukkaṭṭham sippam) at Vin iv.7 (with gaṇanā & lekhā), as the first of the sippāni (with gaṇanā) at M i.85=Nd2 199. Further at Miln 3, 59, 78 sq., 178. Cp. BSk. mudrā in same sense (e. g. at Divy 3, 26, 58 in set lipyā, sankhyā, gaṇanā, m.). Bdgh's expln of muddā D i.11 m.+gaṇanā (see DA i.95) as "hattha - muddā - gaṇanā" is doubtful; since at Miln 78 sq. muddā & gaṇanā are two quite diff. things. See also Franke, Dīgha trsl. p. 18, with note (he marks muddā "Finger - Rechnen" with?); and cp. Kern, Toev. i.166 s. v. muddā. The Dial. i.21 trsl. "counting on the fingers" (see Dial. i.21, 22 with literature & more refs.). - hattha° is signlanguage, gesture (lit. hand - arithmetic), a means of communicating (question & answer) by signs, as clearly evident fr. J vi.364 (hattha - muddāya nam pucchissāmi . . . muṭṭhim akāsi, sā "ayaṃ me . . . pucchati" ti ñatvā hattham vikāsesi, so ñatvā . . . ; he then asks by word of mouth). - hattha-muddam karoti to make a sign, to beckon J iii.528; cp. Vin v.163: na hatthavikāro kātabbo, na hattha - muddā dassetabbā.

4.2 The Tongue Seal

Figure 1: Image of Khecari-Mudrā / Jivhā-Muddā, with 4 stages, a part of Haṭha yoga, were practitioners use UNNATURAL method of gradually severing the frenulum of the tongue with a sharp implement over a period of months to stretch the length of the tongue to be reflexed and brought up to the hard palate, and then later until it can be turned back so as to reach inside the nasal cavity, and supposedly manipulate the flow of bindu. Image by Ananda Kriya Sangha, 2020, from Commons (2025), available under Creative Commons CC0 1.0 with license @ Universal Public Domain Dedication

Figure 1 shows the tongue seal in 4 stages. However, the Buddha only talked about the first stage, which is natural and simple to practice, in my limited perspective.

4.3 The Buddha on tongue. . .

In, Majjhima Nikāya 20, Vitakkasaṅḥānasutta (How to Stop Thinking), translation by Bhikkhu Sujato, -

“Adhicittamanuyuttana, bhikkhave, bhikkhunā pañca nimittāni kālena kālaṃ manasi kātābbāni.

“Mendicants, a mendicant committed to the higher mind should focus on five subjects from time to time.

Katamāni pañca?

What five?

Idha, bhikkhave, bhikkhuno yaṃ nimittaṃ āgamma yaṃ nimittaṃ manasikaroto uppajjanti pāpakā akusalā vitakkā chandūpasamhitāpi dosūpasamhitāpi mohūpasamhitāpi, tena, bhikkhave, bhikkhunā tamhā nimittā aññaṃ nimittaṃ manasi kātābbaṃ kusālūpasamhitāṃ.

Take a mendicant who is focusing on some subject that gives rise to bad, unskillful thoughts connected with desire, hate, and delusion. That mendicant should focus on some other subject connected with the skillful.

Tassa tamhā nimittā aññaṃ nimittaṃ manasikaroto kusālūpasamhitāṃ ye pāpakā akusalā vitakkā chandūpasamhitāpi dosūpasamhitāpi mohūpasamhitāpi te pahīyanti te abbatthāṃ gacchanti.

As they do so, those bad thoughts are given up and come to an end.

Tesaṃ pahānā ajjhattameva cittaṃ santiṭṭhati sannisīdati ekodi hoti samādhiyati.

Their mind becomes stilled internally; it settles, unifies, and becomes immersed in samādhi.

Seyyathāpi, bhikkhave, dakkho palagaṇḍo vā palagaṇḍantevāsī vā sukhumāya āṇiyā oḷārikāṃ āṇim abhinīhaneyya abhinīhareyya abhinivatteyya;

It’s like a deft carpenter or their apprentice who’d knock out or extract a large peg with a finer peg.

Tassa ce, bhikkhave, bhikkhuno tesampi vitakkānaṃ vitakkasaṅkhārasaṅḥānaṃ manasikaroto uppajjanteva pāpakā akusalā vitakkā chandūpasamhitāpi dosūpasamhitāpi mohūpasamhitāpi.

Now, suppose that mendicant is focusing on stopping the formation of thoughts, but bad, unskillful thoughts connected with desire, hate, and delusion keep coming up.

Tena, bhikkhave, bhikkhunā dantebhidantamādhāya jivhāya tāluṃ āhacca cetasā cittaṃ abhiniggaṇhitābbaṃ abhinippīletābbaṃ abhisantāpetābbaṃ.

With teeth clenched and tongue pressed against the roof of the mouth, they should squeeze, squash, and crush mind with mind.

Tassa dantebhidantamādhāya jivhāya tāluṃ āhacca cetasā cittaṃ abhiniggaṇhato abhinippīlayato abhisantāpayato ye pāpakā akusalā vitakkā chandūpasamhitāpi dosūpasamhitāpi mohūpasamhitāpi te pahīyanti te abbatthāṃ gacchanti.

As they do so, those bad thoughts are given up and come to an end.

Tesaṃ pahānā ajjhattameva cittaṃ santiṭṭhati sannisīdati ekodi hoti samādhiyati.

Their mind becomes stilled internally; it settles, unifies, and becomes immersed in samādhi.

Seyyathāpi, bhikkhave, balavā puriso dubbalataram purisam sīse vā gale vā khandhe vā gahetvā abhiniggaṇheyya abhinippīḷeyya abhisantāpeyya;

It's like a strong man who grabs a weaker man by the head or throat or shoulder and squeezes, squashes, and crushes them.

Ayam vuccati, bhikkhave, bhikkhu vasi vitakkapariyāyapathesu.

This is called a mendicant who is a master of the ways of thought.

Yam vitakkaṃ ākaṅkhissati taṃ vitakkaṃ vitakkessati, yaṃ vitakkaṃ nākaṅkhissati na taṃ vitakkaṃ vitakkessati.

They will think what they want to think, and they won't think what they don't want to think.

Acchecchi taṇhaṃ, vivattayi saṃyojanaṃ, sammā mānābhisamayā antamakāsi dukkhassā'ti.

They've cut off craving, untied the fetters, and by rightly comprehending conceit have made an end of suffering."

Idamavoca bhagavā.

That is what the Buddha said.

In, Majjhima Nikāya 36 (Middle Discourses), Mahāsaccakasutta (The Longer Discourse With Sacca), translation by Bhikkhu Sujato, -

Tassa mayhaṃ, aggivessana, etadahosi:

Then it occurred to me,

'nāyaṃ dhammo nibbidāya na virāgāya na nirodhāya na upasamāya na abhiññāya na sambodhāya na nibbānāya saṃvattati, yāvadeva nevasaṅṅānāsāṅṅāyatanūpapattiyā'ti.

'This teaching doesn't lead to disillusionment, dispassion, cessation, peace, insight, awakening, and extinguishment. It only leads as far as rebirth in the dimension of neither perception nor non-perception.'

So kho ahaṃ, aggivessana, taṃ dhammaṃ analaṅkaritvā tasmā dhammā nibbija apakkamim.

Realizing that this teaching was inadequate, I left disappointed.

So kho ahaṃ, aggivessana, kiṅkusalagavesī anuttaraṃ santivarapadaṃ pariyesamāno magadhesu anupubbena cārikaṃ caramāno yena uruvelā senānigamo tadavasariṃ.

I set out to discover what is skillful, seeking the supreme state of sublime peace. Traveling stage by stage in the Magadhan lands, I arrived at Senānigama in Uruvelā.

Tatthaddasaṃ ramaṇīyaṃ bhūmibhāgaṃ, pāsādikañca vanasaṅḍaṃ, nadiñca sandantiṃ setakaṃ supatitthaṃ ramaṇīyaṃ, samantā ca gocaragāmaṃ.

There I saw a delightful park, a lovely grove with a flowing river that was clean and charming, with smooth banks. And nearby was a village to resort to for alms.

Tassa mayhaṃ, aggivessana, etadahosi:

Then it occurred to me,

'ramaṇīyo vata bho bhūmibhāgo, pāsādiko ca vanasaṅḍo, nadī ca sandati setakā supatitthā ramaṇīyā, samantā ca gocaragāmo.

'This park is truly delightful, a lovely grove with a flowing river that's clean and charming, with smooth banks. And nearby there's a village to resort to for alms.

Alaṃ vatidaṃ kulaputtassa padhānatthikassa padhānāyā'ti.

This is good enough for striving for a gentleman wanting to strive.'

So kho ahaṃ, aggivessana, tattheva nisīdim

So I sat down right there, thinking:

‘alamidaṃ padhānāyā’ti.

‘This is good enough for striving.’

Apissumaṃ, aggivessana, tisso upamā paṭibhaṃsu anacchariyā pubbe assutapubbā.

And then these three similes, which were neither supernaturally inspired, nor learned before in the past, occurred to me.

Seyyathāpi, aggivessana, allaṃ kaṭṭhaṃ sasnehaṃ udake nikkhattaṃ.

Suppose there was a green, sappy log, and it was lying in water.

Atha puriso āgaccheyya uttarāraṇiṃ ādāya:

Then a person comes along with a drill-stick, thinking

‘aggim abhinibbattessāmi, tejo pātukarissāmi’ti.

to light a fire and produce heat.

Taṃ kiṃ maññasi, aggivessana,

What do you think, Aggivessana?

api nu so puriso amuṃ allaṃ kaṭṭhaṃ sasnehaṃ, udake nikkhattaṃ, uttarāraṇiṃ ādāya abhimanthento aggim abhinibbatteyya, tejo pātukareyya’ti?

By drilling the stick against that green, sappy log lying in the water, could they light a fire and produce heat?”

”No hidaṃ, bho gotama”.

“No, worthy Gotama.

”Taṃ kissa hetu”?

Why not?

”Aduñhi, bho gotama, allaṃ kaṭṭhaṃ sasnehaṃ, tañca pana udake nikkhattaṃ.

Because it’s a green, sappy log, and it’s lying in the water.

Yāvadeva ca pana so puriso kilamathassa vighātassa bhāgi assā’ti.

That person will eventually get weary and frustrated.”

“Evameva kho, aggivessana, ye hi keci samaṇā vā brāhmaṇā vā kāyena ceva cittena ca kāmehi avūpakaṭṭhā viharanti, yo ca nesari kāmesu kāmacchando kāmasneho kāmamucchā kāmapipāsā kāmapariḷāho, so ca ajjhattaṃ na suppahīno hoti, na suppatippassaddho, opakkamikā cepi te bhonto samaṇabrāhmaṇā dukkhā tippā kharā kaṭukā vedanā vedayanti, abhabbāva te nānāya dassanāya anuttarāya sambodhāya.

“In the same way, there are ascetics and brahmins who don’t live withdrawn in body and mind from sensual pleasures. They haven’t internally given up or stilled desire, affection, infatuation, thirst, and passion for sensual pleasures. Regardless of whether or not they feel painful, sharp, severe, acute feelings due to overexertion, they are incapable of knowledge and vision, of supreme awakening.

No cepi te bhonto samaṇabrāhmaṇā opakkamikā dukkhā tippā kharā kaṭukā vedanā vedayanti, abhabbāva te nānāya dassanāya anuttarāya sambodhāya.

Ayaṃ kho maṃ, aggivessana, paṭhamā upamā paṭibhāsi anacchariyā pubbe assutapubbā.

This was the first example that occurred to me.

Aparāpi kho maṃ, aggivessana, dutiyā upamā paṭibhāsi anacchariyā pubbe assutapubbā.

Then a second example occurred to me.

Seyyathāpi, aggivessana, allaṃ kaṭṭhaṃ sasnehaṃ, ārakā udakā thale nikkhattaṃ.

Suppose there was a green, sappy log, and it was lying on dry land far from the water.

Atha puriso āgaccheyya uttarāraṇim ādāya:

Then a person comes along with a drill-stick, thinking

*‘aggim abhinibbattessāmi, tejo pātukarissāmi’*ti.

to light a fire and produce heat.

Tam kim maññasi, aggivessana,

What do you think, Aggivessana?

api nu so puriso amum allam kaṭṭham sasneham, ārakā udakā thale nikkhittam, uttarāraṇim ādāya abhimanthento aggim abhinibbatteyya tejo pātukareyyā”ti?

By drilling the stick against that green, sappy log on dry land far from water, could they light a fire and produce heat?”

“No hidam, bho gotama”.

“No, worthy Gotama.

“Tam kissa hetu”?

Why not?

“Aduñhi, bho gotama, allam kaṭṭham sasneham, kiñcāpi ārakā udakā thale nikkhittam.

Because it’s still a green, sappy log, despite the fact that it’s lying on dry land far from water.

*Yāvadeva ca pana so puriso kilamathassa vighātassa bhāgi assā”*ti.

That person will eventually get weary and frustrated.”

“Evameva kho, aggivessana, ye hi keci samaṇā vā brāhmaṇā vā kāyena ceva cittena ca kāmehi vūpakatthā viharanti, yo ca nesam kāmesu kāmacchando kāmasneho kāmamucchā kāmapiṇṇā kāmapiṇṇāho so ca ajjhattam na suppahīno hoti, na suppaṭippassaddho, opakkamikā cepi te bhonto samaṇabrāhmaṇā dukkhā tībā kharā kaṭukā vedanā vedayanti, abhabbāva te nāṇāya dassanāya anuttarāya sambodhāya. No cepi te bhonto samaṇabrāhmaṇā opakkamikā dukkhā tībā kharā kaṭukā vedanā vedayanti, abhabbāva te nāṇāya dassanāya anuttarāya sambodhāya.

“In the same way, there are ascetics and brahmins who live withdrawn in body and mind from sensual pleasures. But they haven’t internally given up or stilled desire, affection, infatuation, thirst, and passion for sensual pleasures. Regardless of whether or not they suffer painful, sharp, severe, acute feelings due to overexertion, they are incapable of knowledge and vision, of supreme awakening.

Ayam kho mam, aggivessana, dutiyā upamā paṭibhāsi anacchariyā pubbe assutapubbā

This was the second example that occurred to me.

Aparāpi kho mam, aggivessana, tatiyā upamā paṭibhāsi anacchariyā pubbe assutapubbā.

Then a third example occurred to me.

Seyyathāpi, aggivessana, sukkham kaṭṭham koḷāpaṇam, ārakā udakā thale nikkhittam.

Suppose there was a dried up, withered log, and it was lying on dry land far from the water.

Atha puriso āgaccheyya uttarāraṇim ādāya:

Then a person comes along with a drill-stick, thinking

*‘aggim abhinibbattessāmi, tejo pātukarissāmi’*ti.

to light a fire and produce heat.

Tam kim maññasi, aggivessana,

What do you think, Aggivessana?

api nu so puriso amum sukkham kaṭṭham koḷāpaṇam, ārakā udakā thale nikkhittam, ut-

tarāraṇiṃ ādāya abhimanthento aggim abhinibbatteyya, tejo pātukareyyā”ti?

By drilling the stick against that dried up, withered log on dry land far from water, could they light a fire and produce heat?”

“Evam, bho gotama”.

“Yes, worthy Gotama.

“Tam kissa hetu”?

Why is that?

“Aduñhi, bho gotama, sukkham kaṭṭham koḷāpaṃ, tañca pana ārakā udakā thale nikkhit-tan”ti.

Because it’s a dried up, withered log, and it’s lying on dry land far from water.”

“Evameva kho, aggivessana, ye hi keci samaṇā vā brāhmaṇā vā kāyena ceva cittena ca kāmehi vūpakaṭṭhā viharanti, yo ca nesam kāmesu kāmacchando kāmasneho kāmamucchā kāmapiṇṇā kāmapiṇṇā, so ca ajjhataṃ supphāṇo hoti suppaṭippassaddho, opakkamikā cepi te bhonto samaṇabrāhmaṇā dukkhā tikkhā kharā kaṭukā vedanā vedayanti, bhaddhāva te nāṇāya dassanāya anuttarāya sambodhāya. No cepi te bhonto samaṇabrāhmaṇā opakkamikā dukkhā tikkhā kharā kaṭukā vedanā vedayanti, bhaddhāva te nāṇāya dassanāya anuttarāya sambodhāya.

“In the same way, there are ascetics and brahmins who live withdrawn in body and mind from sensual pleasures. And they have internally given up and stilled desire, affection, infatuation, thirst, and passion for sensual pleasures. Regardless of whether or not they suffer painful, sharp, severe, acute feelings due to overexertion, they are capable of knowledge and vision, of supreme awakening.

Ayaṃ kho maṃ, aggivessana, tatiyā upamaṃ paṭibhāsi anacchariyā pubbe assutapubbā.

This was the third example that occurred to me.

Imā kho maṃ, aggivessana, tisso upamaṃ paṭibhāsu anacchariyā pubbe assutapubbā.

These are the three similes, which were neither supernaturally inspired, nor learned before in the past, that occurred to me.

Tassa mayham, aggivessana, etadahosi:

Then it occurred to me,

‘yannūnāhaṃ dantebhi dantamādhāya, jivhāya tālum āhacca, cetasā cittaṃ abhiniggaṇheyyaṃ abhinippiḷeyyaṃ abhisantāpeyyaṃ’ti.

‘Why don’t I, with teeth clenched and tongue pressed against the roof of my mouth, squeeze, squash, and scorch mind with mind?’

So kho ahaṃ, aggivessana, dantebhi dantamādhāya, jivhāya tālum āhacca, cetasā cittaṃ abhiniggaṇhāmi abhinippiḷemi abhisantāpemi.

So that’s what I did,

Tassa mayham, aggivessana, dantebhi dantamādhāya jivhāya tālum āhacca cetasā cittaṃ abhiniggaṇhato abhinippiḷayato abhisantāpayato kacchehi sedā muccanti.

until sweat ran from my armpits.

Seyyathāpi, aggivessana, balavā puriso dubbalataram purisaṃ sise vā gahetvā khandhe vā gahetvā abhiniggaṇheyya abhinippiḷeyya abhisantāpeyya;

It was like when a strong man grabs a weaker man by the head or throat or shoulder and squeezes, squashes, and crushes them.

evameva kho me, aggivessana, dantebhi dantamādhāya, jivhāya tālum āhacca, cetasā cittaṃ abhiniggaṇhato abhinippiḷayato abhisantāpayato kacchehi sedā muccanti.

In the same way, with teeth clenched and tongue pressed against the roof of my mouth, I squeezed, squashed, and crushed mind with mind until sweat ran from my armpits.

Āraddhaṃ kho pana me, aggivessana, vīriyaṃ hoti asallīnaṃ, upaṭṭhitā sati asammuṭṭhā, sāraddho ca pana me kāyo hoti appaṭippassaddho teneva dukkhappadhānena padhānābhitunnassa sato.

My energy was roused up and unflagging, and my mindfulness was established and lucid, but my body was disturbed, not tranquil, because I'd pushed too hard with that painful striving.

Evarūpāpi kho me, aggivessana, uppannā dukkhā vedanā cittaṃ na pariyādāya tiṭṭhati.

But even such painful feeling did not occupy my mind.

4.4 The practice of the Tongue Seal : a personal account. . .

Now, whenever, i have been unable to meditate OR the events in life demand that i cannot meditate and the mind is out of restrain and running around, OR my senses would OVER WORK (SAY i wanted to watch AS MUCH PROGRAMs on TV, as possible to satisfy my mind via EYES!), then with GENTLENESS, i fold the tongue and do the first stage of the Jivhā-Muddā / Khecarī-Mudrā ONLY (NOTE - WILL NEVER DO the REST of the stages as i DO NOT NEED IT!).

4.4.1 First, how do i practice the Jivhā-Muddā / Khecarī-Mudrā?

1. DON'T FORCE and CLENCH MY TEETH.
2. JUST the gently role the tongue and the tip of the tongue touches the soft palate.
3. There the tongue RESTS gently! NO FORCE! (This comes after years of practice! JUST the 1st stage and it should be enough for whole life! NOT in EXTREMES!)
4. Further, i DO NOT practice this 1st stage, 24 hours a day! As and when i get aware that my mind is running and i can't work or be one pointed in mind, i practice this!
5. Finally, when i was NEW to this Jivhā-Muddā / Khecarī-Mudrā, i couldn't even practice for 5 minutes also . . . (SO DO NOT GET FRUSTRATED! YOUR MIND and YOUR SENSES will NOT ALLOW you to settle and CALM DOWN!)
6. Thus, i started practicing SLOWLY and STEADILY, say 5 minutes a day to say 1 hour a day!
7. AT ADVANCED level, monks and nuns are known to remain in the 1st stage of Jivhā-Muddā / Khecarī-Mudrā for majority of the day!
8. NOTE - THERE is NO FORCE! DO NOT FORCE! Just a GENTLE awareness and effort of the tongue touching the soft palate above, and that is ENOUGH . . . Kept it like that, as long as i could! If it became UNCOMFORTABLE, then i would RELEASE the Jivhā-Muddā / Khecarī-Mudrā! . . . Later on, i would again start the practice!
9. Lastly, the observation of the natural breath or Anapana, starts happening NATURALLY. To the FOCUSED mind, the flow of the breath comes to awareness . . . Though NOT DEEP, HOWEVER, one is aware that Anapana is happening! (whatever the duration of observation)

4.4.2 *What happens or happened due to the practice of Jivhā-Muddā / Khecarī-Mudrā?*

- First of all, there is a RUSH of saliva in the mouth! All i do it GULP the saliva. (So, suppose you are on a long walk and become thirsty, what do you do? Sometimes, when water is not there, you just swallow the saliva. That is a natural process!)
- Next, the sense of taste comes into awareness and IMMEDIATELY the entire mind is within the region of the part where the tip of the tongue touches the soft palate above.
- As i continue doing this, SLOWLY and STEADILY, the mind CONVERGES to ONE POINT-EDNESS and STOPS RUNNING around!
- Further, longer duration of practice, leads to this BANDWIDTH of awareness, EXPANDING SLOWLY and and STEADLILY, where the whole of head, then the neck and down below comes into AWARENESS! NOT that it is not there, HOWEVER, before i was UNAWARE and by practice of Jivhā-Muddā / Khecarī-Mudrā, there is GENTLE awareness of the WHOLE body!
- FINALLY, as one's mind becomes STILL, even while working, the SENSATIONS in the body come to awareness, . . . SLOWLY and STEADILY! (This might TAKE YEARS of regular practice!)

4.4.3 *What do i do with what happens while practicing Jivhā-Muddā / Khecarī-Mudrā?*

- As all the body and sensations start coming to awareness, while practicing the Jivhā-Muddā / Khecarī-Mudrā, there is just OBSERVATION or WATCH (Anupassanā in Pali) of the RIVER that is FLOWING, CALLED the BODY and SENSATIONS!
- i DO NOT HOLD ON to the RIVER that is FLOWING! This is vipassanā or DEVELOPING INSIGHT in ACTION! (HOWEVER, this requires years of practice! i need to HAMMER OUT everyday! That is how it is!)
- NOTE - Sometimes EXTREME PRESSURE will build in the mind as if it has turned into STONE or body might become STIFF. During those moments, BREATHE. Just SHIFT the awareness to BREATHING, while maintaining the Jivhā-Muddā / Khecarī-Mudrā.
- Lastly, INCREASE the QUALITY of the BANDWIDTH of the PRACTICE! Be it meditation or this mudra!
- What will happen is, you WILL/MIGHT get a REIGN over your senses and mind, by WATCHING the RIVER flow and deciding when to RESPOND AND NOT TO REACT! To begin with at a very minute level! So before, if you were a high velocity bullet train hurtling down at full speed, now you might just start bicycling . . . (figuratively)

4.4.4 *A practical example (say, during driving / walking / sitting) while practicing Jivhā-Muddā / Khecarī-Mudrā?*

- In any of the above, just practice the Jivhā-Muddā / Khecarī-Mudrā in GENTLENESS!

- *Watch the flow of the RIVER called BODY, SENSATIONS and MIND, as it is, i.e yathābhūtam.*
- *IRRESPECTIVE of the conditioning (pleasant / unpleasant / neutral) of the STATE and the FLUX of the above RIVER, DO NOT HOLD or GRASP anything! LET the RIVER FLOW, WHILE REPOSING in the stillness of awareness . . .*
- *It is a long journey over many life times! TAKE IT SLOW!*
- *As Jetsun Milarepa said - Hasten slowly and ye shall soon arrive!*

4.4.5 WARNING REPETITION!

- *Practice in MODERATION (ie. Majjhimā Paṭipadā, or the Middle Way/Path) and the SIMPLE STAGE ONLY! DANGEROUS WITHOUT GUIDANCE for ADVANCED STAGES!*
- *i NEVER practised beyond stage 1 so TECHNICALLY, i DO NOT KNOW about the other 3 stages. AM happy with the 1st stage of the Tongue Seal only! You have to see for yourself!*

5 ⊕ Contentment (mainly of heart) i.e Santuṭṭhi

5.1 The Buddha on contentment. . .

To reiterate, as recorded in the Khuddakanikāya, Dhammapada, Sukhavagga, Ñātikalahavūpasamanavatthu, Pasenadikosavavatthu, **above all, the MOST IMPORTANT is CONTENTMENT of HEART**, is a requisite, from time to time, in daily life! As the Buddha said -

Ārogyaparamā lābhā, . . .

Absence of illness, . . .

is the highest / most excellent, receiving / getting / acquisition / gain / possession . . .

Santuṭṭhiparamāṃ dhanāṃ, . . .

Satisfaction / contentment (mainly of heart), . . .

is the highest / most excellent, receiving / getting / acquisition / gain / possession . . .

Vissāsaparamā ñāti . . .

Trust / confidence / intimacy / mutual agreement (mainly the truth or dhamma) is a relation / relative, . . .

is the highest / most excellent, receiving / getting / acquisition / gain / possession . . .

Nibbānaṃ paramāṃ sukhaṃ!

The quenching or putting out of fire by other means of extinction than by blowing (which latter process rather tends to incite the fire than to extinguish it) is wellbeing / happiness / ease, . . .

is the highest / most excellent, receiving / getting / acquisition / gain / possession!

and in Saṃyutta Nikāya 1.10, Naḷavagga (A Reed), Araññasutta (Forest), it is said -

Atītaṃ nānusocanti,

They do not lament over the past,

nappajappanti nāgataṃ,
they yearn not for what is to come,
paccuppanna yāpentī,
they maintain themselves in the present,
tena vaṇṇo pasīdati.
thus their complexion is serene.

5.2 A poetry for all of you. . .

*Like the ocean's silence
filled with an ancient nectar,
called Nirvana,
the heart is content &
the mind still . . .
No thoughts of birth,
neither that of death,
no want to go for,
no search to go on,
no journey to be taken,
and no effort to be put forth . . .
Nothing to say,
nothing to do,
and nothing to become,
just to sit still,
and be . . .
Thus by grace have i found a way,
were the heart is content,
and the mind still
that if death comes now,
i am ready to go . . .
May those above,
live with a content heart,
may those below,
live with a heart content,
may all around,
find contentment in their hearts,
wherever i walk,
as long as life remains . . .
just sit still and be*

Daily, make it a practice to say to yourself - "Content is my heart! I need nothing right now!" Just a few moments and fill your heart with contentment! Only your practice will tell you, what it might lead to . . . in the journey of life, though work to complete the task you need to do in this life!

6 A place to meditate . . . common in India

6.1 The Buddha on secluded place of meditation . . .

In, Majjhima Nikāya 36, Mahāsaccakasutta (The Longer Discourse With Saccaka), translations by Bhikkhu Sujato, the Buddha reflects as follows -

Tassa mayham, aggivessana, etadahosi:

Then it occurred to me,

‘nāyam dhammo nibbidāya na virāgāya na nirodhāya na upasamāya na abhiññāya na sambodhāya na nibbānāya saṁvattati, yāvadeva nevasaññānāsaññāyatanūpapattiyā’ ti.

‘This teaching doesn’t lead to disillusionment, dispassion, cessation, peace, insight, awakening, and extinguishment. It only leads as far as rebirth in the dimension of neither perception nor non-perception.’

So kho aham, aggivessana, taṁ dhammaṁ analaṅkaritvā tasmā dhammā nibbijja apakkamim.

Realizing that this teaching was inadequate, I left disappointed.

So kho aham, aggivessana, kiṅkusalagavesī anuttaraṁ santivarapadaṁ pariyesamāno magadhesu anupubbena cārikaṁ caramāno yena uruvelā senānigamo tadavasariṁ.

I set out to discover what is skillful, seeking the supreme state of sublime peace. Traveling stage by stage in the Magadhan lands, I arrived at Senānigama in Uruvelā.

Tatthaddasaṁ ramaṇīyaṁ bhūmibhāgaṁ, pāsādikaṅca vanasaṅgaṁ, nadiṅca sandantiṁ setakaṁ supatitthaṁ ramaṇīyaṁ, samantā ca gocaraḡamaṁ.

There I saw a delightful park, a lovely grove with a flowing river that was clean and charming, with smooth banks. And nearby was a village to resort to for alms.

Tassa mayham, aggivessana, etadahosi:

Then it occurred to me,

‘ramaṇīyo vata bho bhūmibhāgo, pāsādiko ca vanasaṅgo, nadī ca sandati setakā supatitthā ramaṇīyā, samantā ca gocaraḡamo.

‘This park is truly delightful, a lovely grove with a flowing river that’s clean and charming, with smooth banks. And nearby there’s a village to resort to for alms.

Alaṁ vatidaṁ kulaputtassa padhānatthikassa padhānāyā’ ti.

This is good enough for striving for a gentleman wanting to strive.’

So kho aham, aggivessana, tattheva nisīdim

So I sat down right there, thinking:

‘alamidaṁ padhānāyā’ ti.

‘This is good enough for striving.’

then again . . .

Na kho panāhaṁ imāya kaṭukāya dukkarakārikāya adhigacchāmi uttari manussadhammā alamariyañānadassanavisesaṁ.

But I have not achieved any superhuman distinction in knowledge and vision worthy of the noble ones by this severe, grueling work.

Siyā nu kho añño maggo bodhāyā’ ti?

Could there be another path to awakening?’

Tassa mayham, aggivessana, etadahosi:

Then it occurred to me,

‘abhijānāmi kho panāhaṃ pitu sakkassa kammante sītāya jambucchāyāya nisinno vivicceva kāmehi vivicca akusalehi dhammehi savitakkaṃ savicāraṃ vivekajaṃ pītisukhaṃ paṭhamaṃ jhānaṃ upasampajja viharitā.

‘I recall sitting in the cool shade of a black plum tree while my father the Sakyan was off working. Quite secluded from sensual pleasures, secluded from unskillful qualities, I entered and remained in the first absorption, which has the rapture and bliss born of seclusion, while placing the mind and keeping it connected.

Siyā nu kho eso maggo bodhāyā’ti?

Could that be the path to awakening?’

Tassa mayhaṃ, aggivessana, satānusāri viññāṇaṃ ahoṣi:

Stemming from that memory came the understanding:

‘eseva maggo bodhāyā’ti.

‘That is the path to awakening!’

So kho ahaṃ, aggivessana, oḷārikaṃ āhāraṃ āhāretvā, balaṃ gahetvā, vivicceva kāmehi vivicca akusalehi dhammehi savitakkaṃ savicāraṃ vivekajaṃ pītisukhaṃ paṭhamaṃ jhānaṃ upasampajja vihāsim.

After eating solid food and gathering my strength, quite secluded from sensual pleasures, secluded from unskillful qualities, I entered and remained in the first absorption, which has the rapture and bliss born of seclusion, while placing the mind and keeping it connected.

And thus began his journey . . . the journey of Siddhartha in his final life to that of Buddha!

6.2 The Snapshot of a place where one could meditate . . . quite common in India

These images in figure 2, figure 3 and figure 4, should speak for itself. In India, you will find such constructions in plethora!

Figure 2: A tree protected by a concrete structure! One can sit under the tree and meditate in the shade!

Figure 3: The shade of the tree and the surroundings!

WHAT TROUBLES OR BURNS OR CONSUMES YOU INSIDE OUT . . . ?

Figure 4: Another view of the tree in figure 2

7 For those interested . . . a personal account

- *Please read through the following webpage on [how meditation helped me scientific & spiritual research](#).*
- *Further, to navigate through, please use my [TREE-STRUCTURE LINK](#) available @ [Linktr web-page](#).*
- *This MIGHT help you find material of your choice and topic of interest, for further exploration, IN CASE interest arises!*

8 Conclusion

In retrospect, in these negligible 20 years of my journey through meditations and whatever limited i could grasp, i would say that the readers of the article MUST evaluate based on personal experiential knowledge of the meditations. NOT BECAUSE i have said so! Your personal experiential knowledge in meditation IN TANDEM with the (say, here) evaluation of my research work on the teachings of the Buddha, IS THE REQUIREMENT, IF interest and time permits. Also, one should be careful of what one is reading and is published in top international journals and evaluate with personal wisdom and insight developed via meditations, continued over long periods of time in one's life!

In this, i will not conclude! Your journey is your own and you need to see if you have benefitted from what has been shared, by any teacher/monk/nun, irrespective of their personal attainments! In short, JUST DON'T GET MESMERISED! Your heart will tell you who is what, in the long run and further, DON'T JUMP into quick conclusions and get stuck in words! Grasp the essence behind the frequencies of the words that have been used to share the knowledge!

In the end, i would quote here the teachings of the Buddha himself, as follows -

8.1 regarding development of wisdom and meditation . . .

In the Khuddakanikāya, Dhammapada, Maggavagga, Pañcasatabhikkhuvatthu, Poṭṭhīlattheravatthu -

*Yogā ve jāyati bhūri,
ayogā bhūrisaṅkhayo;
Etaṃ dvedhāpathaṃ ñatvā,
bhavāya vibhavāya ca;
Tathāttānaṃ niveseyya,
yathā bhūri pavaḍḍhati.*

From meditation springs wisdom,
without meditation, wisdom ends.
Knowing these two paths -
of progress and decline -
you should conduct yourself
so that wisdom grows.

Further, in the Dīgha Nikāya, Mahāparinibbānasutta, The Great Discourse on the Buddha's Extinction -

*Yo imasmim dhammavinaye,
appamatto vihassati;
Pahāya jātisamsāram,
dukkhassantaṃ karissatī”ti.*

Whoever meditates diligently,
in this teaching and training,
giving up transmigration through rebirths,
will make an end to suffering.”

8.2 regarding NOT because someone has said so . . .

In the Aṅguttara Nikāya 3.65, Mahāvagga, Kesamuttisutta (With the Kālāmas of Kesamutta), it is said -

- **Pali** : *”Santi, bhante, eke samaṇabrāhmaṇā kesamuttaṃ āgacchanti.* **English** : “There are, sir, some ascetics and brahmins who come to.
- **Pali** : *Te sakaṃyeva vādaṃ dīpenti jotenti, parappavādaṃ pana khumsenti vambhenti paribhavanti omakkhiṃ karonti.* **English** : They explain and promote only their own doctrine, while they attack, badmouth, disparage, and smear the doctrines of others.
- **Pali** : *Apārepi, bhante, eke samaṇabrāhmaṇā kesamuttaṃ āgacchanti.* **English** : Then some other ascetics and brahmins come to Kesamutta.
- **Pali** : *Tepi sakaṃyeva vādaṃ dīpenti jotenti, parappavādaṃ pana khumsenti vambhenti paribhavanti omakkhiṃ karonti.* **English** : They too explain and promote only their own doctrine, while they attack, badmouth, disparage, and smear the doctrines of others.
- **Pali** : *Tesaṃ no, bhante, amhākaṃ hoteva kaṅkhā hoti vicikicchā :* **English** : So, sir, we’re doubting and uncertain:
- **Pali** : *’ko su nāma imesaṃ bhavataṃ samaṇabrāhmaṇānaṃ saccaṃ āha, ko musā”ti? English* : ‘I wonder who of these respected ascetics and brahmins speaks the truth, and who speaks falsehood?’”
- **Pali** : *”Alañhi vo, kālāmā, kaṅkhituṃ alaṃ vicikicchituṃ.* **English** : ”It is enough, Kālāmas, for you to be doubting and uncertain.
- **Pali** : *Kaṅkhanīyeva pana vo ṭhāne vicikicchā uppanā.* **English** : Doubt has come up in you about an uncertain matter.
- **Pali** : *Etha tumhe, kālāmā, mā anussavena, mā paramparāya, mā itikirāya, mā piṭakasampadānena, mā takkahetu, mā nayahetu, mā ākāraparivattakkena, mā diṭṭhinijjhānakkhantiyā, mā bhabbarūpatāya, mā samaṇo no garūti.* **English** : Please, Kālāmas, don’t go by oral transmission, don’t go by lineage, don’t go by testament, don’t go by canonical authority, don’t rely on

logic, don't rely on inference, don't go by reasoned train of thought, don't go by the acceptance of a view after deliberation, don't go by the appearance of competence, and don't think 'The ascetic is our respected teacher.'

- **Pali** : *Yadā tumhe, kālāmā, attanāva jāneyyātha*: **English** : But when you know for yourselves:
- **Pali** : *'ime dhammā akusalā, ime dhammā sāvajjā, ime dhammā viññugarahitā, ime dhammā samattā samādinnā ahitāya dukkhāya samvattanti'ti, atha tumhe, kālāmā, pajaheyyātha*. **English** : 'These things are unskillful, blameworthy, criticized by sensible people, and when you undertake them, they lead to harm and suffering', then you should give them up.

Pali : Bhavatu Sabba Mangalam

English : May all beings be happy

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